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Blood Establishments – Profit Making or Nonprofit Organizations: EU and Georgia Approaches

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Abstract. The paper intends to introduce the global challenges in blood safety and the EU and Georgia approaches towards this issue. The problem is discussed in the light of blood establishments – the organizations that shall undertake the responsibility for the safety of blood and blood components. The paper aims to scrutinize whether the profit making purpose of blood establishments may prejudice to the safety of blood and blood components. The article aims to answer the question – what is the worldwide importance of this problem? Why blood safety issues are so relevant?

Keywords: Blood establishments, WHO, Global Framework, profitmaking, the EU, Georgia, blood transfusion, blood-related services, blood-related operations, nonprofit organizations.

Introduction

Blood is an inevitable fluid of human body and is vital for life. And the right to life is a fundamental right of human being. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights enshrines the right to life in the Article 3 while the Article 25 broadens the right and declares that “Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family”.¹ High standards required for the health determines the coordination and harmonization of regulatory mechanisms worldwide. In the light of health protection World Health Organization (WHO) that counts 194 member states including EU Member States and Georgia, permanently adopts the framework action plans and recommendations to achieve the integrated healthcare systems. Considering the relevance of the protection

¹ Article 25, Universal Declaration of Human Rights, <https://www.un.org/en/universal-declaration-human-rights> (accessed 30 May 2019).

of health and life, WHO set the priority to implement blood safety measures. Based on the 1975 WHA.28.72 resolution of World Health Assembly (IFRC) WHO in cooperation with the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies has developed A Global Framework for Action setting the goals to be achieved by 2020. According to the Global Framework for Action “Blood transfusion is a core service within health care systems and individuals who donate their blood provide a unique contribution to the health and survival of others. Every country faces an ongoing challenge to collect sufficient blood from safe donors to meet national requirements”.² One of the primary objectives of the Global Framework is to provide necessary guidance in assuring the stable and sufficient supplies of safe blood for transfusion.³ Blood transfusion is a vital process for health protection, surviving lives in emergency cases as well as in surgeries. Blood transfusion may contribute to patients’ recovery and prolongation of their lives. About 234 million operations are performed worldwide every year, with 63 million people undergoing surgery for injuries, more than 31 million for treating cancers.⁴ All these patients are in need of blood transfusion either once or regularly. In this regard, only well-organized blood transfusion systems are viable to meet quality and safety requirements determined by the internationally recognized guidelines. Blood supply is a comprehensive process of collecting, testing, storage and distribution of safe blood and blood components that demands high quality performance at all levels. Due to the lack of blood and blood components worldwide and especially their perishable character makes it essential to demand high safety standards from blood establishments.

One of the goals set by the Global Framework is to encourage voluntary unpaid blood donation worldwide and especially in those countries where the majority of blood supply is obtained through paid

² Towards 100% Voluntary Blood Donation, A Global Framework for Action, World Health Organization, 2010, 7.

³ *Ibid.*, 3.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 9.

donation. It is considered that the safest donors are those donors who donate blood on voluntary unpaid basis. The altruistic character of their behavior and high sense of social responsibility eliminate risks related to the infectious diseases. Unpaid donors do not have any other motivation than a true desire to help others. In contrast, paid donors tend to hide the information about diseases having in mind to receive money. Thus, the paid donation can be extremely detrimental for health and lives of blood recipients. To avoid health complications and fatal results WHO made it as a primary objective to eventually eliminate the paid donation cases by 2020.

EU directives concerning blood safety and quality entirely reflect the pathos of the Global Framework regarding the unpaid donation and the relevance of safe blood and blood components.⁵ EU-Georgia Association Agreement determines the following EU directives to be implemented by Georgia: a) Directive 2002/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 January 2003 setting standards of quality and safety for the collection, testing, processing, storage and distribution of human blood and blood components and amending Directive 2001/83/EC; b) Commission Directive 2004/33/EC of 22 March 2004 implementing Directive 2002/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards certain technical requirements for blood and blood components; c) Commission Directive 2005/62/EC of 30 September 2005 implementing Directive 2002/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards Community standards and specifications relating to a quality system for blood establishments; and d) Commission Directive 2005/61/EC of 30 September 2005 implementing Directive 2002/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards traceability requirements and notification of serious

⁵ "Setting of technical requirements and adaptation to progress should take into account [...] recommendations of the Council of Europe and the WHO". See Directive 2002/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 January 2003 setting standards of quality and safety for the collection, testing, processing, storage and distribution of human blood and blood components, recital 27.

adverse reactions and events.⁶ All these compulsory directives demand high standards of blood establishments by introducing specific quality and safety measures. Directive 2002/98/EC in recital 4 states that “Member States should take measures to promote Community self-sufficiency in human blood or blood components and to encourage voluntary unpaid donations of blood and blood components.” Due to the relevance of the topic Georgia has adopted the Law on the Donation of Blood and its Components before the entry into force EU-Georgia Association Agreement. The law of Georgia focuses on donation development issues and also covers voluntary unpaid donation aspects.⁷

Purpose of Blood Establishments – profit making or altruism?

Above mentioned EU directives alongside with WHO recommendations define the implementation of effective, well-developed organizational structures of blood establishments and the adoption of unpaid voluntary donation programs. The activities of blood establishments are directly related to unpaid voluntary donation. Fostering of the unpaid donation can be achieved by way of mutual trust between donors and blood establishments.⁸ “The sector of blood donation and transfusion services is one of the most sensitive universal social indicators which, within limits, is measurable, and one which tells us something about the quality of relationships and human values prevailing in a society.”⁹ Moreover, blood establishments may have a significant influence on donors’ behavior and transform a single act of donation into a regular activity of the donors and thus contribute to increase blood supply. Hence, the interconnection between these two sectors is obvious and the maintenance of trust

⁶ Annex XXXI, Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union, Volume 57, 30 August, 2014.

⁷ See Law of Georgia on the Donation of Blood and Blood Components at www.matsne.gov.ge (accessed 30 May 2019).

⁸ Gamal Gabra, “Challenges in achieving 100% voluntary blood donation,” Journal compilation © 2009 International Society of Blood Transfusion, 57.

⁹ *Ibid.*

between them is relevant. In this regard, the formation of donors' behavior may be influenced by different factors including organizational forms (governmental organizations, private legal entities, nonprofit organizations, hospital blood banks, etc.) of blood establishments, organizational structures (compulsory quality controlling body involvement) and public image. The research analysis performed in EU Member States and in Norway identified the most reliable blood establishments in these target countries. Pursuant to the Eurobarometer 1993, 34% of donors rely on government based blood transfusion organizations (France, the UK), 23% of donors in Germany and Belgium prefer highly-reputable nongovernmental / humanitarian organizations (e.g. Red Cross) and 21% of donors give priority to blood banks (Norway, Spain). The data reveals the main tendencies in the target countries and gives a clear understanding of: who takes the responsibility for the effective functioning of blood transfusion systems; who provides qualified and safe service – government or the private sector. Pursuant to the survey results there are three major categories of blood establishments within the EU: government-based organizations, humanitarian organizations (Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies) and blood banks. As regards Georgia, the most developed blood establishments are hospital based blood banks.

For the purposes of development of effective blood transfusion services it is essential to understand one important issue: is it fair to commercialize blood transfusion or related services in terms of global challenges of implementation of unpaid donation programs eliminating any remuneration opportunities? The direct answer cannot be found either in the Global Framework or in EU directives and 1994 Communication concerning blood safety and self-sufficiency issues.¹⁰

Despite the fact that donors tend to perform on unpaid basis the costs for collection, testing, processing, storage and distribution of blood

¹⁰ Communication from the Commission on blood safety and self-sufficiency in the European Community, Commission of the European Communities, COM (94) 652 Final, Brussels, 21.12.1994.

and blood components are unavoidable. “These activities must be financed either through the healthcare systems or through normal market procedures.”¹¹ All the activities mentioned above need the involvement of considerable financial and human resources. Collection of blood and blood components is not a mere fact of donation – in order to attract donors at least the proper information has to be distributed. Promotional campaigns intended for broad audience that provide the proper understanding of safe donation, develop the awareness of donation-related obstacles and motivate the donors, requires the proper financing. Hence, the sufficient blood supply is not achievable without a well-organized infrastructure, human resources responsible for blood transfusion, promotional programs and a respective budget. Qualified human resources are essential for reliability and for persuading people to donate as far as unqualified personnel may harm to donor as well as the recipient of blood. Eventually the lack of quality and safety standards may be detrimental for both human life and the reputation of blood establishment. The transfusion safety is especially relevant to avoid the spread of such infectious diseases as HIV or Hepatitis C considering that blood transfusion is one of the sources for transmitting these infections. Thus, the attraction of adequate and consistent number of donors is possible only in terms of safe infrastructure and qualified personnel making the sufficient financing of blood establishments as an essential factor.

One of the crucial problems is maintenance of a consistent number of donors. Enhancement of coordination among donor programs and partner organizations, patients’ associations and those entities involved in blood transfusion and supply activities may effectively contribute to increase blood storage worldwide. Any such donation program and the establishment of coordinated systems require adequate financial resources.

The abovementioned facts illustrate that blood establishments are eligible to support blood donation, transfusion, collecting, testing and other activities in terms of sufficient budgeting. The distribution of blood and

¹¹ *Ibid.*, article 4.5.

blood components and supply of blood to recipients / patients are performed on paid basis. An interesting point is whether this approach is in line with WHO recommendations of achieving 100% unpaid blood donation. There is no direct prohibition of selling blood and blood components neither by WHO recommendations nor by EU acts. Private, commercial establishments responsible for collecting or distribution of blood coexist together with nonprofit, humanitarian organizations within the EU. For instance, German structure of blood donation system stands on three pillars: “1. the Blood Transfusion Services of the Red Cross (Deutsches Rotes Kreuz – DRK; Bayerisches Rotes Kreuz – BRK), 2. University medical hospitals / schools and community hospitals organized as the German Association of Blood Transfusion Centres (Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Ärzte staatlicher und kommunaler Bluttransfusionsdienste – StKB) as well as 3. privately owned ones, organized as an association of independent blood donation services (Verband Unabhängiger Blutspendedienste - VUBD) (Zeiler 2015).”¹² While in France Etablissement Francais du Sang (EFS) has been the only blood transfusion operator since 2000 who is in charge of the whole transfusion chain for the French territory.¹³ This establishment is under the authority of the Ministry of Health.¹⁴ In Spain 17 Regional Blood Transfusion Services operate on an autonomous management; however, they are “fully incorporated into a unique and common Public National Health System, supplying a cohesive blood transfusion care to all citizens, residents and visitors in Spain.”¹⁵ As for the Finnish blood service system, Finnish Blood Service is a nationwide blood service provider in Finland and “is a financially and operationally independent organization within the Finnish Red Cross. It provides Finnish hospitals with all the blood products they need. It is a non-

¹² Erik Stenholm, *Monitoring of blood transfusion operations in EU-countries*, Karolinska University Hospital, Department of Environment, A report within EU's Life+ project PVCfreeBloodBag LIFE10 ENV/SE/037, October 2015.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 11.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 28.

profit organization and focuses on the patients.”¹⁶ As can be seen from what was said above there are no unified or harmonized standards towards blood establishments within the EU. The only unified standards enshrined in EU directives refer to the necessary technical requirements that all blood transfusion operators shall meet in order to operate in this sphere and obtain the license. WHO recommendations also concern only the particular measures to be taken to ensure the effectiveness of the service at issue. However, regardless the fact that there is no direct indication in WHO Global Framework related to the legal form of blood establishments, WHO obligates member states to take a responsibility including financial support for the proper functioning of transfusion chains and organizations.

According to the Global Framework alongside with the state financial support, money donations, inputs of international and humanitarian organizations can serve as the major sources of financing transfusion services. Nothing is mentioned in regard to covering costs by means of selling blood and blood components. This approach of WHO can be considered as the determination of priorities and indirect indication to eliminate the commercialization tendencies of blood and blood components. Though there is no direct prohibition of selling blood. In this regard, profitmaking and the coverage of unavoidable costs shall be distinguished. It has already been said that blood collection, transfusion, storage or other related operations need constant financing and this is normal. On the other hand, profitmaking goes beyond the coverage of necessary charges and is a main purpose of the organization / enterprise. If we accept profitmaking from blood-related services, it can be equally detrimental for the safety and quality of blood as a paid donation when the main purpose of the donor is to receive money. Profitmaking purpose can undermine the trust of unpaid donors towards the blood establishments. Commercial blood establishments deem to collect more blood and blood components and in this case the threat to breach the donor selection criteria and diminish safety and quality standards is absolutely realistic.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, 17.

In support of the global purpose of maintaining sufficient storage of blood and blood components in my view nonprofit organizations can serve as major contributors. These organizations are established for particular, in some sense, altruistic reason and by excluding profit making intention are keen to eventually reach the main goal of saving human lives. As already been mentioned different organizations with different legal forms provide blood transfusion and blood supply services within the EU. There is no indication in Georgian laws or in EU-Georgia Association Agreement to what is an acceptable legal form for enterprises eligible providing blood-related operations. Blood establishments mostly operate as hospital based blood banks in Georgia. In the event of exclusion of profit making purpose, the blood establishments with noncommercial legal forms can be regarded as suitable forms for human blood-related services. Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies as noncommercial, charitable organizations are vivid example of donors' and recipients' confidence and trust.

Different approach is considered by specific group of economists. Pursuant to this approach the reason of blood shortage is non-commercialization of blood-related operations. "A thriving blood market will remove the scarcity of blood. At present blood is scarce because either blood trade is illegal or its alleged unethical nature precludes people from practicing it. Blood donation alone is bound to result in shortages because blood has no price right now. It is exchanged for *free*. And this is the reason why most people are not interested in blood donation [...] Shortages can only be removed if we allow blood trade."¹⁷ Therefore, this attitude considers the development of blood free market that can be equally beneficial for all parties involved: donors (earning money), blood collecting organizations (making profit) and blood recipients / patients (saving lives and curing illnesses).

¹⁷ Madhusudan Raj, "Blood Donation or/and Blood Trade," 5, <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1922931> (accessed 30 May 2019).

Conclusion

The discussion above has illustrated that the legal forms of blood establishments are not determined either by international acts (WHO recommendations or guidelines, EU acts or multilateral agreements) or by local legislation. However, World Health Organization intends to encourage the development of unpaid donation programs. In this regard, the distribution of blood collected on an unpaid basis for profit making contradicts with the goal set by WHO. Unpaid donation is considered as a safe source of blood supply and consequently the blood establishments shall be treated in the same way. Blood establishments shall operate in noncommercial legal forms in order to address the global challenges of blood safety and shortage.

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Issues of Improvement of Norm Creating Activity of International Organizations and International Legal Initiatives of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. International law will continue to grow with the cooperation of states and intensification of integration processes. Consequently, it is reflected in the creation of new legal norms for the full regulation of the relationships between the international legal entities and the appropriate alterations or additions to the existing international practice. International lawmaking is not limited to the conclusion of international treaties between states and recognizing internationally legal norms by states. The modern norm creating process is characterized by the increasing the role of international organizations. This implies to study the function of international organizations as a part of the international lawmaking. In addition, international legal initiatives play a decisive role in the effective implementation of rapidly developing international relations and also in the field of international lawmaking, especially in the normative activities of international organizations. The article is devoted to the actual problem of participation of international organizations in international law-making. It also examines the peculiarities and development tendencies of norm creating activities of these organizations. Particular attention is paid to international legal initiatives of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Furthermore, article considers the role of international organizations in the current process of globalization and democratization, as well as national and international legal aspects of relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and international organizations. On this basis, proposals are presented on improving the effectiveness of the activities of international organizations and also on further development of cooperation. In the conclusion, the author cites several proposals on the improvement of norm creating activity of international organizations.

Keywords: international law-making, norm creating activity of international organizations, resolution, international legal initiatives, veto power.

The issue of the International law-making is one of the fundamental themes of the international law theory. The direct participation of international organizations as an independent entity in this process and the growing role of international organizations on the world arena, the increase in the number of agreements with intervention through the normative function, the adoption by effective bodies of international organizations in resolving the global problems of mankind as well as the development of universally recognized standards, implies to study this function of international organizations as a part of the international lawmaking.

In the doctrine of international law, international lawmaking is defined as the process of States association on the content of norms and their implementation¹. International normative practices differ from national norm-creating by complexity and specificity. First of all this difference is occurred not only by the absence of a single legislative body in the international arena, but also the deficiency of a single constitution, contracts or other documents regulating this process. However, this situation provides with an opportunity to international law of freely expressing their perspectives to develop methods and techniques that can be easily adapted to the rapidly changing international standard of living. With the expansion of international law, and its increased specialization, it is no longer the case that it is 'made' by a finite number of entities (states) through a handful of intergovernmental processes. Instead, international law is made in a large number of fora, including a variety of multilateral processes, tribunals and the organs of international organizations².

The process of norm creating activity of international organizations comprises their actions aimed at the development, improvement, modification or abolition of legal norms. It should be endorsed that no international organization, as well as universal organizations, have

¹ И. Барковский, "Правотворческая деятельность международных организаций: теоретические аспекты и современные тенденции," *Белорусский журнал международного права и международных отношений*, № 2 (2003): 12.

² Alan Boyle, Christine Chinkin, "The Making of International Law," *European Journal of International Law*, vol. 19, no. 3 (2008): 601.

“legislative” powers. Explicitly, any norm created while developing recommendations, rules and treaties adopted by international organizations initially should be recognized by states as an international legal norm, and secondly, this norm is ought to be mandatory for these states.

Today, the activities of international organizations cover all aspects of interstate cooperation, in which a great number of countries participate. Until recently, international organizations were seen as a means of diplomacy³. Nevertheless, the activities of international organizations are broader than diplomacy and include all new opportunities, obtaining more operative functions beyond the competence of the information coordinating body.

It is important to note that regardless of how large this land is, its scale is so narrow that today in the international community there is no any state that has not collaborated. As a consequence of relations between states, some common problems complicate international relations and require the improvement of international legal norms. As mentioned above, international relations are effectively regulated by the use of mechanisms of the norm-creation of international organizations. However, the commence of this mechanism depends on states and they are the initiator of the creation of a new norm as well. Proceeding from this, Uzbekistan, which gained its independence just over a quarter of a century ago, is also the founder of various international agreements.

In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan is a sovereign democratic republic and a full-fledged subject of international relations. In reference to Article 17⁴ of our Constitution, our country’s foreign policy is based on the principles of sovereign equality, non-use or threat of force, inviolability of borders, peaceful settlement of disputes, non-interference into other states' internal affairs along with other universally recognized principles and norms of international law.

³ A. Cassese, J. Weiler, *Change and Stability in International Law-Making* (Berlin: De Gruyter, 2010), 41.

⁴ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PPCH “UZBEKISTAN”, 2017, 8.

Hence, in the norms of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of September 10, 2012 “On the Adoption of the Concept of Foreign Policy Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan” it is noted that the foreign policy of our country is realized taking into account active, initiative and rapidly changing international political realities of the 21st century. Consequently, the implementation of foreign policy on the basis of these normative standards, international initiatives and proposals of Uzbekistan have been widely acknowledged by the international community, the international reputation of our country and the role of participation in solving regional and international issues have increased. In particular, it is essential to note the initiatives of the first President I. Karimov on the Aral Sea and Afghanistan concerns, the declaration of Central Asia as a zone free of nuclear weapons, creating multilateral normative documents, arranging international formats of mutually beneficial cooperation and counteracting transnational threats and ensuring regional security. Sequentially, these initiatives were highly appreciated by the international community as well as the results of their implementation have a positive impact on humanity.

In particular, the UN adopted a special resolution of 6 December 2006 which, on behalf of the countries of the region, was transmitted by Uzbekistan, entitled “Establishment of a nuclear-weapon-free zone in Central Asia” No. 61/88⁵. The General Assembly recognized the Treaty on the Establishment of a Nuclear-Weapon-Free Zone in Central Asia as an important step towards strengthening regional and international peace and security.

In Addition, the final meeting of the 6+2 group on Afghanistan – China, Iran, Pakistan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Russia as an observer – the United Nations / United Front and the Taliban in Tashkent – is an important international historical event on which was approved the Tashkent

⁵ Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 6 December 2006 61/88. Establishment of a nuclear-weapon-free zone in Central Asia, <https://undocs.org/en/A/RES/61/88> (accessed 28 May 2019).

Declaration on the basic principles of the peaceful settlement of the conflict in Afghanistan.

Moreover, Uzbekistan participated in a number of international and regional conferences, including the Moscow meeting (April), the Kabul Process (June), the Conference on Regional Economic Cooperation for the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan (Ashgabat, November) “Asia Heart – Istanbul process” (Baku, November-December) and the International Dialogue Meeting (Oslo, December). The head of our state represented the position of Uzbekistan on stabilizing the situation in Afghanistan and made concrete proposals on this issue.

At an international conference entitled “Central Asia: One Past and a Common Future, Cooperation for Sustainable Development and Mutual Prosperity”, held⁶ in November 2017 in Samarkand, proposals were launched to join Afghanistan in regional economic processes.

Furthermore, on March 27, 2018, the Tashkent sophisticated conference «Peace process, security cooperation and regional connectivity» was held⁷. This forum, initiated by our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev, differed from previous international conferences on the format and with the fact that it was directed to find a substantial solution to the Afghan problem. Therefore, the initiative of holding it was widely supported by the international community. The opinion of authoritative international organizations, politicians and experts was expressed that this forum plays a practical role by providing concrete proposals for solving the problems of the Afghan people, especially in promoting peace and security in Afghanistan, thereby enhancing security in Central Asia and in neighboring regions.

It should be noted that the conference put forward proposal and applications to establish peace in Afghanistan, restore the socio-economic

⁶ Official website of the president of Uzbekistan, <http://president.uz/ru/lists/view/1227> (accessed 28 May 2019).

⁷ Official website of the president of Uzbekistan, <http://president.uz/en/lists/view/1601> (accessed 28 May 2019).

infrastructure and support Afghanistan in its full integration into regional economic processes. The result was the signing of the Tashkent Declaration.

It should be declared that today Uzbekistan actively contributes in the work of the UN committees, which are engaged in standard-setting activities to develop normative documents consequential to the whole world and improving existing norms of international treaties. Particularly, Uzbekistan is considered to be a co-author of such documents as the “Treaty on a Nuclear-Weapon-Free Zone in Central Asia”⁸, the resolution about “Developments in the field of information and telecommunications in the context of international security”⁹ adopted by the 71st session of the General Assembly, the resolution “on Improving the coordination of efforts against trafficking in persons” implemented by the General Assembly on the 72nd session, also resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 17 November 2017 about “Role of the United Nations Regional Centre for Preventive Diplomacy for Central Asia”¹⁰.

What is more, on April 9, 2018, the Plan of work on improving the international legal and contractual activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2021 was approved, which defined specific tasks for the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and other competent bodies for the development and strengthening worldwide legal relations between Uzbekistan and other countries and international organizations, as well as enhancing the role of our state in transnational lawmaking.

On September 19, 2017, at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, intended to make a proposal on the accomplishment of a special decree of the General Assembly in support of the efforts of the states of Central Asia

⁸ Treaty on a Nuclear-Weapon-Free Zone in Central Asia, <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N16/422/11/PDF/N1642211.pdf?OpenElement> (accessed 28 May 2019).

⁹ Developments in the field of information and telecommunications in the context of international security, <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N16/399/50/PDF/N1639950.pdf?OpenElement> (accessed 28 May 2019).

¹⁰ Role of the United Nations Regional Centre for Preventive Diplomacy for Central Asia, Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 17 November 2017, <https://unrcca.unmissions.org/sites/default/files/n1738914.pdf> (accessed 28 May 2019).

in terms of ensuring security and enhancing regional cooperation, resolution on “Education and Religious Tolerance” and “International Convention on the Rights of Youth” which will be unified global legal instrument aimed at the formation and accomplishment of youth policy in the conditions of globalization and rapid development of information and communication technologies¹¹.

As it is acknowledged that there is no centralization of the international normative process, including the normative activities of international organizations, the international community, under the auspices of the United Nations, should enhance a special international commission for the coordination of normative activities or delegate this authority to the United Nations International Law Commission.

That is to say, considering the current trends in the normative activities of international organizations, it is necessary to amend the decision-making mechanisms. Additionally, the use of “veto” power in the pronouncement of the permanent members of the Security Council often leads to the non-acceptance of important resolutions, so it is desirable to implement a dimension on veto power.

In conclusion, many international conventions, agreements and other documents that are significant for the whole world that are the result of the normative activities of international organizations, in particular, the normative activity of the United Nations, are in many cases advanced and adopted on the basis of state initiatives. However, in sequence these international legal norms are performed in the national legislative system and serve the affluence and prosperity of a country.

¹¹ Address by H. E. Mr Shavkat Mirziyoyev, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the General Debate of the 72nd Session of the United Nations General Assembly, New York, September 19, 2017, https://gadebate.un.org/sites/default/files/gastatements/72/uz_en.pdf (accessed 28 May 2019).

Issues of National and International Legal Aspects and Perspectives of the Activities of International Organizations in Uzbekistan

Foreign policy is the direction and domain of state activities to ensure the country's national interests in international relations as well as to arrange concrete, practical steps of the state to realize its goal and objectives. Consequently, efficient foreign policy and foreign economic affairs are the most important factor for the successful implementation of large-scale and democratic reforms in the country and strengthening the country's image in the international arena and improving the welfare of the inhabitants as well.

Within a short period of time, Uzbekistan has created a political and legal basis for its foreign policy, defined its priorities and principles in interstate relations. Currently has been clearly implementing appropriate measures So as to retain development of the reforms concerned. In particular, more than 40 "road maps" have been approved¹² in recent years to develop practical cooperation with foreign countries and international organizations. Moreover, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.5400 of April 5, 2011, "On Measures for the Basic Improvement of the System of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Enhancing Its Responsibility for Implementing Priorities for Foreign policy and Foreign Economic Activity"¹³. Accordingly, has provided significant objectives for establishing the systematic refinement of the system of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, hence has accomplished practical significance for the enhancement of the Strategy of Action in the Five Principles of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021¹⁴ as well as The Concept of Administrative Reforms of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹⁵.

¹² Official website of the President of Uzbekistan, <http://president.uz/uz/lists/view/1423> (accessed 28 May 2019).

¹³ National database of legislative data, 06/18/5400/1023, 06.04.2018.

¹⁴ Collection of laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 6-num. 70-article, 20-nub, 354-article, 2017.

¹⁵ National database of legislative data, 06/18/5496/1603, 01.08.2018.

For instance, as one of the goals of this normative legal act is affirmed the creation of conducive foreign policy conditions for the efficient execution of democratic reforms in the country and also the rapid process of modernization of society and economy, mutual and multilateral strategic cooperation with the world's leading countries and international organizations along with the promotion of international initiatives of Uzbekistan in substantial sphere of regional and world politics.

Indeed, in the era of globalization and democratization and intensive amplification of countries with activation of interrelations of states there is often created international institutions to facilitate solving common problems and also achieving attainable prosperity. Therefore, these organizations embody special role in resolving transnational issues on the basis of peaceful, humanitarian approaches while encouraging cooperation in terms of providing information and reducing expense¹⁶.

Currently, the The Yearbook of International Organizations encompass detailed information on over 37,500 active and approximately 38,000 dormant international organizations from 300 countries and territories – enclosing intergovernmental (IGOs) and international non-governmental organizations (INGOs). Approximately 1,200 new organizations are inserted each year¹⁷. In addition, such international institutions are divided into two types: first, organizations having free autonomy and organizational structure for making decisions in formal multilateral relations between states¹⁸; second, voluntary non-governmental organizations established for the implementation of common goals and public welfare¹⁹.

¹⁶ R. Jackson, G. Sorensen, *Introduction to International Relations: Theories and Approaches* (3rd ed, New York: Oxford University Press, 2007), 102.

¹⁷ Union of International Associations, *The Yearbook of International Organizations*, <https://uia.org/yearbook> (accessed 28 May 2019).

¹⁸ P. Diehl, B. Frederking, *The Politics of Global Governance: International Organizations in an Independent World* (4th ed, Colorado: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2010), 15.

¹⁹ M. Karns, K. Mingst, *International Organizations: The Politics and Processes of Global Governance* (2nd ed, Colorado: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2010), 221.

Regardless of the international legal framework, the foremost purpose of the international community is to form the necessary circumstances for the development of states and the use of globalization for the benefit of citizens²⁰. This is reflected in the creation of forums for the advance of interstate cooperation in social, economic, political, cultural and other fields, the peaceful settlement of international conflicts, the unification of various international instruments, regulations and the multilateral amendment of common problems as well.

It should be noted that presently the Republic of Uzbekistan has constituted diplomatic relations with more than 130 countries around the world. There are 45 embassies of foreign countries, 8 honorary consuls, 19 missions of international organizations, 18 representations of international intergovernmental and governmental organizations of foreign states and also 1 trade mission with diplomatic status are operating in Tashkent. Moreover, 47 diplomatic and consular missions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are accredited in foreign countries and international organizations. Furthermore, Uzbekistan is a member of more than 100 international organizations and evolves interaction with varied structures of multilateral cooperation²¹.

Additionally, since joining the United Nations, Uzbekistan has been the initiator of many proposals concerning the importance of all mankind. In particular, the establishment in Central Asia of a zone, free of nuclear weapons (1993); The arms embargo on Afghanistan (1995); Determination of the “6+2” group for Afghanistan (1997); the Tashkent Declaration on the Basic Principles for the Peaceful Settlement of the Conflicts in Afghanistan (1999) adoption special resolutions of the General Assembly in support of the efforts of the states of Central Asia in terms of ensuring security and enhancing regional cooperation, resolution named “Education and Religious

²⁰ А. А. Адаменко, “Роль международных организаций в современном мире,” Секция «Проблемы и перспективы международной интеграции в современном бизнесе», Том 3 (2017): 893.

²¹ Official website of Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan, <https://mfa.uz/en/cooperation/> (accessed 28 May 2019).

Tolerance” and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Youth (2017), the appeal to the youth of the heads of the SCO member states as well as the espousal of the Action Plan and the establishment of the SCO Youth Council in the realization of this Program (2018).

Concurrently our country is a member of such international organizations as the CIS, the SCO, the OIC, the OSCE, the IMF. Moreover, Uzbekistan performs exemplary participation in the activities of these organizations with numerous initiatives and concrete strategies to solve common problems.

Regarding the fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan has created encouraging conditions for the effective completion of the activities of international organizations, in pursuing noble ambition in our territory, international institutions have developed cooperation with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and other competent bodies. Here are a few examples.

Particularly the UN which has been presented in Uzbekistan since 1993 has been supporting Uzbekistan not only in addressing a diverse range of needs of economic reforms and improving on governance system but also in accomplishing a variety of international obligations. Over the last 22 years, the UN has delivered technical assistance to Uzbekistan for more than USD 434 million²² to reinforce economic, governance, healthcare and education enhancement along with the protection of environment. In 2015, the UN system in Uzbekistan and the Government signed a new UNDAF for next five years, i.e. 2016-2020, that has marked a new significant milestone that should further strengthen the close cooperation between the United Nations and the Republic of Uzbekistan.

What’s more, the Cooperation with the United Nations International Tourism Organization (UNWTO) is crucial for the advance of international tourism in our country hence, the UNWTO Regional Center for the

²² Official website of United Nations in Uzbekistan, <http://www.un.uz/rus/pages/display/what-we-do> (accessed 28 May 2019).

Development of Tourism in the Great Silk Road has been functioning in Samarkand since 2004²³.

Uzbekistan has been one of the state parties of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) since 26 February 1992. Collaboration of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the OSCE and its institutions is conducted at different levels and it covers a wide range of questions and issues. In 1995, on initiative of Uzbekistan the Liaison Bureau in Central Asia was initiated, which carried out activities on adjusting contacts at different stages and solidarity in areas presenting mutual interests. In June 2006, on initiative of Uzbekistan the Permanent Council has decided to institute the office of the OSCE Project Coordinator in Uzbekistan. In July 2006 the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the OSCE signed the Memorandum of Understanding that pledging to establish the post of the OSCE Project Coordinator in Uzbekistan. In its turn, the Coordinator carries out projects that include assistance in strengthening legislation; conducting training courses; organizing seminars, conferences and study visits; and giving advice on improving the performance of state authorities, government agencies and civil society organizations²⁴.

Since 2001, with the efforts of our country, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization has been reformed the organization's activities, creating and strengthening mutually beneficial cooperation with participating States and other global and regional institutions. In particular, during the presidency of Uzbekistan in the SCO, important documents were adopted regarding the institutional education of the organization, like Regulation on observer status in the SCO and the Order of the SCO interaction with observers, the Convention on the Privileges and Immunities of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and the Tashkent Declarations. In addition, in January 2004, the Regional Anti-Terrorism Structure of the

²³ Uzbekistan, UNWTO Boost Cooperation, <http://www.uzbekembassy.in/uzbekistan-unwto-boost-cooperation/> (accessed 28 May 2019).

²⁴ OSCE Project Coordinator in Uzbekistan, <https://www.osce.org/project-coordinator-in-uzbekistan> (accessed 28 May 2019).

Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO RATS) was opened in Tashkent²⁵. Meanwhile, this permanent body serves as an effective instrument of consolidation and practical cooperation of the law enforcement and intelligence services of the SCO member states in the fight against radical, aggressive extremism, separatism and organized crime.

Since October 2, 1996, our state is a full member of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, which calls for solidarity of Islamic countries in the context of the emerging global geopolitical situation. At the third extraordinary OSCE summit in Mecca in 2005, Uzbekistan initiated the creation of a unified position of the OIC member states within the framework of an international organization. This proposal was covered by most of the Muslim states of the world, and then included in the relevant section of the organization's ten-year program. October 18-19 in 2016 in Tashkent under the slogan «Education and enlightenment – the path to peace and creation» was held the 43rd session of the OIC Council of Foreign Ministers. At this session, Uzbekistan officially assumed the functions of the chairman of the Foreign Ministers Council. During the presidency of Uzbekistan, 23 OIC events were held, which significantly enriched both the agenda and the activities of the Organization. It should be noted that, at the next summits the chairmanship of Uzbekistan was highly appreciated and its contribution to the refinement of Islamic cooperation was widely recognized by member of states.

However, above mentioned statements reveals the successful relations between Uzbekistan and international organizations, based on the analysis of our research, taking into account the theoretically and practically uncontrolled aspects of the current activities of international organizations, we can offer the following:

Firstly, like foreign countries, international organizations, their representative offices and other organizational units as well as officials, in accordance with international agreements concluded, enjoy immunities,

²⁵ The Shanghai cooperation organization, http://rus.sectsc.org/about_sco/ (accessed 28 May 2019).

including civil jurisdiction of the participating States. The property and assets of international organizations are not subject to confiscation, requisition, expropriation and some other form of interference²⁶. Immunity as a general principle is proclaimed in the charters of the relevant organizations and is specified in the supplementary agreements of the organization with the host State and in national legislation as well. The issues concerning the immunity of international organizations should be reconsidered, in terms of international and national legislation, with the intention of progressing mutually beneficial relations and also avoiding violating the norms of international law.

Secondly, the immunity of an international organization also applies to representatives of the organization on the basis of relevant norms. For example, the International Convention constitutes that the United Nations and its officials have the privileges and immunities necessary for the independent implement of their functions²⁷. Another rule of international law reads: "The head of the representative office and the staff of the diplomatic association have immunity from the criminal jurisdiction of the country of origin and are not required to give evidence in the case. However, this immunity does not exempt the jurisdiction of the sending State"²⁸ in practice, there are cases when direct and legal effect measures are taken against representatives of international organizations. Therefore, given the effective intensification of relations with international organizations is desirable to clarify the list of government agencies that can communicate directly with international organizations and those that can establish relations through the Ministry of foreign Affairs as well as to develop a special mechanism on this issue.

Thirdly, today's state of foreign and domestic policy of our state obligates the rapid development of international relations of state

²⁶ В. А. Канашевский, *Внешнеэкономические сделки: материально-правовое и коллизионное регулирование* (Wolters Kluwer Russia, 2010), 553.

²⁷ Convention on the Privileges and Immunities of the United Nations of 13 February 1946, <http://www.un.org/en/ethics/pdf/convention.pdf> (accessed 28 May 2019).

²⁸ *Ibid.*

institutions. Sequentially many state organizations have a special department that commences affairs with foreign countries, international organizations and other international institutions on behalf of this organization. In order to effectively fulfill the tasks stipulated in the foreign policy of international relations and further enhance the prestige of the state power, it is indispensable to appoint officials of international departments of state organizations together with the competent department of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is desirable to introduce a mechanism for upgrading the qualifications of these employees in order to familiarize them with information on the current state of relations among Uzbekistan, foreign states and international organizations and also ensure their accountability in the Foreign Ministry.

As our president Shavkat Mirziyev emphasized, “Active interaction and cooperation with the United Nations, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, the Commonwealth of Independent States, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation and other international organizations serve the national interests of Uzbekistan”²⁹.

In conclusion, it is trendy to say that the global problems of the modern world are diverse and their solution requires the concerted efforts of humanity, the strengthening of cooperation, the formation of permanent forums and formats for broader negotiations in international arenas and the effectual functioning of such international institutions on the territory of the member states. Accordingly, determining a just solution to common issues on account of national interests of states endow with the stability and well-being of all mankind.

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L'Économie Créative et l'Innovation comme Vision Moderne pour Améliorer le Bien-être des Nations

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Abstract. The creative economy is one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy at the beginning of the 21st century. But it is also a sector that makes the difference in terms of income generation, job creation and exports. Between 2002 and 2017, exports of creative goods increased each year by 38% on average by 1.1% in developing countries. By creating jobs, the creative economy contributes to people's overall well-being, self-esteem and quality of life, contributing to sustainable and inclusive development.

Keywords: creative economy, jobs, industrie, productivity, innovation, well-being, competitiveness, national economy.

La créativité humaine fait aujourd'hui la différence dans le processus de production et augmente généralement le bien-être des états du monde. Cette tendance indéniable reflète et porte des bouleversements majeurs, durables et irréversibles dans les économies nationales.

Au 21^{ème} siècle, ni l'économie ni la créativité ne sont nouvelles, mais la nature et l'ampleur de la relation qui les unit et la manière dont elles se combinent pour créer de la valeur et de la richesse sont surprenantes et essentielles. En 2001, John Howkins, doyen du département des industries créatives du Shanghai School of Creativity, publie le livre "L'économie créative: comment les gens gagnent de l'argent par les idées", dans lequel il plaide pour le rôle de la créativité dans l'augmentation de la richesse du pays.

La créativité a une extraordinaire expansion mondiale. À l'heure actuelle, tout le monde veut être créatif, chaque pays veut être créatif, chaque ville veut être connue sous le nom de "ville créative" ou "ville intelligente".

L'économie créative est une économie ou une société dans laquelle les gens sont préoccupés par leur capacité à avoir une idée. Par conséquent, les principaux intrants et extrants sont les idées. Dans l'économie créative, l'augmentation du bien-être national est déterminée par trois facteurs principaux:¹

- Niveau de développement technologique,
- Capacité à générer des connaissances,
- Créativité.

Ces trois éléments sont en synergie absolue et fonctionnent en permanence, dans le but d'accroître la productivité du travail, en vue de réduire les coûts et d'accroître la compétitivité des produits finis. D'autre part, la combinaison parfaite de ces éléments dépend de la qualité du facteur humain en jeu, d'autant plus que la créativité est une compétence humaine. Dans ce contexte, le capital humain englobe trois formes distinctes de capital:

- Capital social – capable d'utiliser les technologies existantes.
- Capital intellectuel – responsable de la création de nouvelles connaissances.
- Capital créatif – capable de générer de nouvelles idées créatives.

L'auteur américain Richard Florida, dans son livre "The Rise of the creative class", mentionne que la croissance économique, la compétitivité de l'économie nationale, est le résultat de la participation active d'une nouvelle classe, la classe créative, dirigée par l'entrepreneur créatif.² À travers ce terme, il définit les individus impliqués dans le processus de création et de production de biens et de services.

Ana Nuevo-Chiquero, professeure à l'Université de Sheffield, effectue une analyse comparative de deux travailleurs possédant des études, une expérience, un sexe et même un IQ identique et constate qu'ils sont payés différemment et qu'ils contribuent de manière différente à la

¹ R. Florida, *The Rise of the Creative Class: And How It's Transforming Work, Leisure, Community, and Everyday Life* (New York: Harper Business, 2014).

² Ibid.

croissance de la productivité.³ Dans ce contexte, nous devons identifier quels sont les ingrédients secrets du succès économique. La réponse est simple. Les institutions financières internationales explorent de plus en plus le rôle du facteur humain dans le développement économique mondial. Il existe de nombreuses études et recherches sur son impact sur les activités économiques. Dans le rapport mondial sur les facteurs humains, *The Human Capital Report 2015*, élaboré par le Forum Economique Mondial, il est précisé que le talent, et non le capital, constituera le lien essentiel entre l'innovation, la compétitivité, la productivité et la croissance économique au XXI^e siècle. L'augmentation de la performance des facteurs humains sera fonction des connaissances, du talent, de la créativité, de la motivation par la satisfaction, de la volonté de s'engager et de l'information. La même idée est également exposée dans le rapport de l'Indice mondial de l'innovation: *Le facteur humain dans l'innovation 2014*, selon lequel la performance de l'épargne dépend directement de la qualité de la main-d'œuvre. Le rapport comprend plusieurs chapitres où l'importance des compétences de l'individu en tant que clé essentielle de la promotion de l'innovation, de l'accroissement de la productivité, de la croissance et du bien-être est abordée.

Les recherches de l'OCDE indiquent qu'outre les études, l'expérience, les connaissances, les talents et les compétences, la productivité peut être générée s'il existe une forte motivation pour l'individu. En adoptant ces caractéristiques, nous constatons que nous assistons à la redéfinition d'un nouveau modèle de facteur humain impliqué dans l'activité économique. Au 21^{ème} siècle, études et raisonnement sans motivation, créativité et talent ne cèdent plus au processus économique. La créativité et le talent, combinés aux connaissances, à la compétence et à la loyauté, génèrent le bien-être de chaque société et des performances élevées.

³ A. Nuevo-Chiquero, "How your personality relates to your productivity and salary," World Economic Forum, Sydney, 2015, https://agenda.weforum.org/2015/04/how-your-personality-relates-to-your-productivity-and-salary/?utm_content=buffer6d4c4&utm_medium=social&utm_source=facebook.com&utm_campaign=buffer (accessed 03.04.2019).

Et pourtant, quelle est l'économie créative? Selon la CNUCED, l'économie créative n'a pas de définition unique. Ce concept en évolution s'appuie sur l'interaction entre la créativité et les idées humaines et la propriété intellectuelle, le savoir et la technologie. Il s'agit essentiellement de l'activité économique fondée sur la connaissance sur laquelle reposent les "industries créatives".

L'industrie créative comprend la publicité, l'architecture, l'artisanat d'art, le design, la mode, le film, la vidéo, la photographie, la musique, les arts de la scène, l'édition, la recherche et le développement, les logiciels, les jeux informatiques, l'édition électronique économie créative. Ils sont également considérés comme une source importante de valeur commerciale et culturelle.

L'économie créative est la somme de tous les secteurs des industries créatives, y compris le commerce, le travail et la production.

Fig.1.1 Valeurs et parts des exportations de biens créatifs, annuel, 2002-2015, mil.\$

Source: élaboré par l'auteur, les données de la CNUCED, <https://unctadstat.unctad.org/wds/TableViewer/tableView.aspx> (accessed 10.03.2019).

Aujourd'hui, les industries de la création comptent parmi les secteurs les plus dynamiques de l'économie mondiale, offrant aux pays en développement de nouvelles possibilités de sauter dans les secteurs émergents à forte croissance de l'économie mondiale.⁴

Après les rapports de l'Organisation des Nations Unies pour l'Éducation, la Science et la Culture (UNESCO), on constate que dans le monde il y a plusieurs exemples illustrant la diversité et le caractère innovant de l'économie créative, ainsi que sa capacité à améliorer la vie au niveau local et les moyens d'existence dans les pays en développement. Ainsi, en Argentine, les industries culturelles et créatives emploient près de 300 000 personnes et représentent 6,5% du PNB. Au Maroc, l'édition et l'imprimerie emploient 7,8% de la main d'œuvre et représentent un chiffre d'affaires de plus de 570 millions de dollars. En 2009, l'industrie musicale représentait plus de 54 millions de dollars et elle a encore progressé 7 fois depuis cette date. A Bangkok, en Thaïlande, la seule industrie de la mode représente 90 000 entreprises et dans toute la région, des jeunes gagnent leur vie en tant que designers au niveau local. Dans la ville de Pikine, au Sénégal, l'association Africulturban a fondé une Hip Hop Akademy qui dispense aux jeunes des environs une formation au graphisme et au design numérique, à la production de musique et de vidéo, à la gestion promotionnelle et au marketing, ainsi qu'à la fonction de DJ et à l'apprentissage de l'anglais. Ce programme novateur aide les jeunes professionnels des industries créatives à devenir plus performants sur des marchés locaux et internationaux en perpétuelle évolution artistique et technologique. A Chiang Mai, au nord de la Thaïlande, l'initiative CMCC (Chiang Mai Creative City), un cercle de réflexion doublé d'une plate-forme

⁴ UNCTAD, Creative Economy, <https://unctad.org/en/Pages/DITC/CreativeEconomy/Creative-Economy-Programme.aspx> (accessed 10.03.2019).

d'activité et de réseautage, a été lancée comme une entreprise coopérative par des militants venus du monde de l'éducation, du secteur privé et des instances gouvernementales, associés à des groupes communautaires locaux. S'appuyant sur les ressources culturelles disponibles sur place, la CMCC a pour objet d'accroître l'attractivité de la ville en tant qu'endroit où vivre, travailler et investir et d'en faire la promotion comme une destination de choix auprès des investisseurs, entreprises et industries culturelles.

L'innovation découle du concept de nouveauté et de créativité. C'est un processus continu résultant du développement et de l'application de nouvelles idées et technologies. C'est le principal moteur de la croissance économique. Ces dernières années, l'innovation a marqué de manière significative son impact sur le bien-être, ce qui l'oblige à l'augmenter. Un nombre croissant d'économistes évaluent l'impact de la technologie et de l'innovation sur l'augmentation de la productivité du travail, d'où la croissance économique et le bien-être des employés (Scarpetta et Tressel, 2002, Griffith 2004, Cameron 2005). Dans ces contextes, la capacité d'innovation d'une économie dépend du niveau de ses stocks de recherche et développement, de son capital humain, de sa participation au commerce international, de la réglementation des marchés et du transfert de technologie.⁵

Actuellement, l'innovation est soutenue par la créativité, l'accès à Internet, les investissements dans le développement de la recherche, le capital intellectuel et le processus de mondialisation. C'est une préoccupation au niveau des gouvernements, des entreprises, des universités et de la société civile. (OCDE 2016)

Les innovations ont plusieurs dimensions. Ils combinent des aspects non seulement économiques, mais aussi sociaux et culturels, dont certains sont abstraits et ne font pas l'objet d'une évaluation économique. Les

⁵ D. Soumitra, L. Bruno, W. Sacha, *The Global Innovation Index 2016: Winning with Global Innovation* (Geneva: Cornell University, INSEAD, and the World Intellectual Property Organization, 2016), 25, http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2016.pdf (accessed 12.02.2018).

indicateurs couramment utilisés dans l'analyse empirique de l'innovation sont:

- **Tendance à la R & D** – Pour innover, les entreprises doivent investir dans la recherche et le développement afin de créer ou d'adopter de nouveaux produits ou procédés sur le marché. Le pourcentage ou la part des dépenses de R & D peut servir à évaluer la contribution au processus d'innovation dans l'entreprise. Cependant, ce n'est pas un indicateur parfait, car tous les efforts de recherche et développement ne mèneront pas à des résultats.

- **Adoption de technologies** – L'adoption de nouvelles technologies contribue de manière significative à accroître la productivité. Parallèlement, de nouveaux produits et procédés font leur apparition sur le marché, augmentant le quota de production qui leur est attribué. Un facteur essentiel est l'investissement réel dans les machines, le matériel et l'équipement.

- **Brevets par travailleur** – Dans le Rapport 2002 sur la compétitivité mondiale, il est souligné que les économies innovantes comptent au moins 15 brevets par million d'habitants. La concurrence entre les principales économies est étroitement liée à la capacité de ces pays à innover et à conquérir de nouveaux marchés mondiaux pour les produits à la pointe de la technologie. Tous les autres pays sont considérés comme disposant d'une épargne fondée sur la technologie.

- **Intensité des compétences en facteurs humains** – Le lien étroit entre innovation et main-d'œuvre qualifiée est bien établi et documenté. Afin d'évaluer la contribution de la main-d'œuvre qualifiée à l'innovation, les analyses empiriques utilisent la part de l'emploi dans tous les emplois réalisée par des scientifiques, des ingénieurs et d'autres professionnels. La part de l'emploi des travailleurs titulaires d'au moins un diplôme universitaire par rapport à l'effectif total est également utilisée.

Une autre approche de l'innovation est proposée par le Groupe des pays les plus développés du monde, le G20, en coopération avec l'Organisation de coopération et de développement économiques. De leur

point de vue, les pays au potentiel très innovant et créatif soutiennent la croissance de la prospérité nationale par le biais des stratégies et objectifs suivants:

- Suivre les performances et le progrès des TIC;
- Financement à long terme pour la recherche et la science;
- Stimuler l'innovation pour surmonter les défis mondiaux;
- Stimuler le potentiel réel pour passer à la quatrième révolution industrielle;
- Relever les défis communs par le biais de la coopération internationale en science et innovation;
- Accroître la qualité de la science en milieu universitaire;
- Cultiver le talent et les capacités du facteur humain;
- Investissements croissants dans les scientifiques et la classe créative;
- Promotion de la mobilité des étudiants nationaux et internationaux;
- Faciliter la mobilité des chercheurs;
- Promouvoir la collaboration dans le domaine de l'innovation entre entreprises;
- Soutenir l'innovation des entreprises et promouvoir l'esprit d'entreprise.⁶

Si nous prenons des exemples concrets, l'économie la plus innovante et créative reste celle des États-Unis. L'histoire de l'économie américaine est l'une des progrès considérables associés à une innovation remarquable. Le mot "scientifique" n'avait pas encore été inventé, mais des chercheurs comme Isaac Newton ont commencé à découvrir les fondements scientifiques sur lesquels reposaient deux siècles d'inventions pratiques. Plus tard, les Américains ont profité de la révolution industrielle, qui a été

⁶ G20 innovation report 2016: Report prepared for the G20 Science, Technology and Innovation Ministers Meeting, China: OECD's Science, Technology and Industry Scoreboard, 2016, <https://www.oecd.org/innovation/G20-innovation-report-2016.pdf> (accessed 22.01.2019).

une explosion d'innovation, propulsant des sommets économiques sans précédent et constituant un exemple puissant pour les autres pays. Aux États-Unis, l'innovation est considérée comme le créateur du bien-être et du "caractère américain".⁷

Les États-Unis disposent d'un système d'innovation très décentralisé et très diversifié, faisant intervenir de nombreux acteurs, l'environnement institutionnel-gouvernemental, le monde universitaire, le secteur privé et diverses organisations à but non lucratif. Le système combine un niveau élevé de recherche et développement, des investissements massifs dans le facteur humain et le développement de modèles commerciaux sophistiqués.

Selon le Global Innovation Index, établi chaque année par l'Organisation mondiale de la propriété intellectuelle, les États-Unis se classent dans le top 10 des pays ayant le plus haut indice d'innovation. En comparant cet indice entre 2010 et 2016, nous constatons une augmentation de l'indicateur de sophistication du marché, passé de 70,9 points en 2010 à 86,6 en 2016, et de la catégorie des biens créatifs, qui est le produit de l'innovation, de 43 points à 51,6 points en 2016. [Fig. 1.2]

⁷ A Strategy For American Innovation (2011): Securing Our Economic Growth and Prosperity, National Economic Council, Council of Economic Advisers, and Office of Science and Technology Policy, Washington, 2011, 25, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/sites/default/files/uploads/InnovationStrategy.pdf> (accessed 24.04.2019).

Fig. 1.2 Analyse comparative de l'indice mondial de l'innovation 2010/2016 aux États-Unis

Source: Elaboré par l'auteur basé sur les données du Rapport global de l'innovation 2010-2011 et 2016-2017

http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/economics/gii/gii_2011.pdf,
http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2016.pdf (accessed 10.03.2019).

En vue d'améliorer l'indice de l'innovation du pays, l'administration de la Maison Blanche a élaboré plusieurs stratégies pour promouvoir l'innovation dans l'économie nationale depuis 2009: A Strategy For American Innovation: Driving Towards Sustainable Growth And Quality Jobs (2009), A Strategy For American Innovation: Securing Our Economic Growth and Prosperity (2011), A Strategy For American Innovation (2015).⁸

⁸ A Strategy For American Innovation (2011): Securing Our Economic Growth and Prosperity, National Economic Council, Council of Economic Advisers, and Office of Science

Fig. 1.3 La Pyramide de l'Innovation aux États-Unis

Source: A Strategy For American Innovation: Securing Our Economic Growth and Prosperity (2011). National Economic Council, Council of Economic Advisers, and Office of Science and Technology Policy. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/sites/default/files/uploads/InnovationStrategy.pdf> (accessed 24.04.2019).

Le modèle de promotion de l'innovation destiné à stimuler la croissance économique est complexe et échelonné. Il est structuré en une

and Technology Policy, Washington, 2011, 25, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/sites/default/files/uploads/InnovationStrategy.pdf> (accessed 24.04.2019); A Strategy For American Innovation: Driving Towards Sustainable Growth And Quality Jobs, *Executive Office of the President*, Washington, DC, 2009, https://www.whitehouse.gov/assets/documents/SEPT_20_Innovation_Whitepaper_FINAL.pdf (accessed 27.03.2019); A Strategy For American Innovation (2015), National Economic Council and Office of Science and Technology Policy, Washington, 2015, https://www.whitehouse.gov/sites/default/files/strategy_for_american_innovation_october_2015.pdf (accessed 24.04.2019).

pyramide qui envisage à l'origine le développement de quatre blocs clés: l'innovation dans l'éducation, l'innovation en recherche, la main-d'œuvre intelligente et la création d'un écosystème TIC innovant. La prochaine étape est le développement et la sophistication du marché grâce aux entreprises innovantes et aux entrepreneurs créatifs. La dernière étape de l'innovation du pays est l'accent mis sur le développement des biotechnologies, des nanotechnologies et des applications spatiales innovantes. Ces questions parlent du haut degré de développement de l'économie américaine. [Fig.1.3]

Le Japon est un autre pays très innovant et créatif. Le pays s'est appuyé sur son expansion économique et le bien-être de la population sur la science, la technologie, l'innovation, la recherche, la robotisation et l'éducation aux facteurs humains. Son profil de science et d'innovation démontre la performance technologique qu'il possède. Selon les données de l'OCDE, les dépenses en recherche et développement ont dépassé 3,56% en 2015 et se classent au troisième rang mondial. Le nombre de chercheurs japonais est impressionnant, avec plus de 987 456 personnes en 2015. Selon les données de l'OCDE, il est classé deuxième dans le monde, dépassant la seule Chine. Dans le même temps, le Japon se classe au premier rang mondial pour le nombre de brevets, soit plus de 17500 en 2015. La même année, le pays a publié plus de 130000 articles scientifiques, ce qui représente 5,8% des élèves scientifiques du monde. (OCDE 2015)

Selon le tableau de bord mondial de l'innovation, le Japon se classe parmi les 20 pays ayant le plus haut indice d'innovation. En comparant cet indice entre 2010 et 2016, nous constatons une amélioration significative de l'indicateur Capital humain et recherche, qui est passé de 53 points en 2010 à 57,5 en 2016, et de 32 points à 39 points en 2016. [Fig.1.4]

Fig. 1.4 Analyse comparative de l'indice mondial de l'innovation 2010/2016 au Japon

Source: http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/economics/gii/gii_2011.pdf, http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2016.pdf (accessed 10.03.2019).

L'innovation est un domaine important et stratégique de l'économie japonaise. Elle est approchée au plus haut niveau par l'État, avec la création du Conseil National pour la Science, la Technologie et l'Innovation. En 2016, la Stratégie d'Innovation du 5ème Plan de base (exercices 2016 à 2020) a été approuvée et est axée sur les mesures de recherche et d'innovation du pays à l'horizon 2020:

- Créer une nouvelle "société super intelligente" ou "Société 5.0" basée sur les technologies avancées, la bio / nanotechnologie et l'intelligence artificielle;
- Établir un cycle vertueux systémique de ressources humaines, de connaissances, de capital et d'innovation, qui stimule la mobilité des employés entre ces trois environnements; [Fig. 1.5]

Fig.1.5 Le cycle de la vertu systémique au Japon

Source: Fifth Science and Technology Basic Plan of Japan, http://www8.cao.go.jp/cstp/english/basic/5thbasicplan_outline.pdf (accessed 10.03.2019).

- Investissements substantiels dans l'intelligence et le talent du facteur humain en augmentant les dépenses de R & D de plus de 4%;
- Augmenter le nombre de femmes scientifiques jusqu'à 30% du nombre total de chercheurs. À l'heure actuelle, selon les données de l'OCDE, les femmes scientifiques représentent 14,5% du total;
- Maximiser le potentiel scientifique et éducatif du pays en favorisant la mobilité des étudiants et des enseignants, une participation plus active des femmes à la recherche universitaire et en renforçant la collaboration privée et universitaire;
- Développer le potentiel d'innovation pour revitaliser le pays.⁹

L'Australie est un autre État qui allie parfaitement créativité et innovation pour atteindre des performances économiques. C'est

⁹ Research Institute of Economy, Trade and Industry of Japan, http://www.rieti.go.jp/en/projects/program_2016/pg-04/ (accessed 10.03.2019).

probablement l'exemple le plus éloquent d'un État à haut niveau de bien-être. "Les changements technologiques exceptionnels transforment notre façon de vivre, de travailler, de communiquer et de générer de bonnes idées. Nous devons adopter de nouvelles idées sur l'innovation et la science et exploiter de nouvelles sources de croissance pour générer une part significative de la prospérité économique en Australie".¹⁰

L'Australie attache une grande importance à l'innovation et à la science, reconnaissant que ces deux éléments sont à la base de la prospérité économique, de la compétitivité et du bien-être. L'Australie offre une infrastructure dans les TIC modernes, des niveaux d'investissement élevés, des dépenses supérieures à 2,5% pour la recherche et le développement, des incitations commerciales et une solide protection de la propriété intellectuelle. Dans le même temps, l'Australie accorde une importance particulière à l'éducation. Elle est classée parmi les meilleures universités du monde et possède d'excellentes institutions académiques et de recherche.

¹⁰ Innovation and Science, Industry Monitor, 2016, www.industry.gov.au/oce (accessed 05.04.2019).

Fig. 1.6 Analyse comparative de l'indice mondial de l'innovation 2010/2016
Australie

Source: http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/economics/gii/gii_2011.pdf, http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2016.pdf (accessed 10.03.2019).

L'Australie se classe parmi les 20 pays ayant le plus haut indice d'innovation. En comparant cet indice entre 2010 et 2016, nous constatons une amélioration significative de l'indicateur Infrastructure, de 52 points en 2010 à 65,5 points en 2016, et de la sophistication du marché, qui représente les flux d'échanges et d'investissement, de 58 points à 66 points en 2016. La mise en œuvre correcte des mesures institutionnelles découle des produits de biens créatifs, avec une augmentation de 8 points en 2016 par rapport à 2010.

Pour stimuler la créativité et l'esprit d'entreprise, le gouvernement australien a lancé le Programme National pour l'Innovation et la Science, une série d'initiatives visant à encourager les australiens à développer leurs compétences innovantes, à promouvoir une collaboration intensive entre l'industrie et les chercheurs, à développer et à attirer les talents. Il repose sur quatre piliers principaux:¹¹ [Fig. 1.6]

- *Culture et capital.* En Australie, la priorité est donnée à la création et à la promotion de jeunes entreprises sur la base de modèles économiques mondiaux combinés à une ingéniosité locale traditionnelle. Pour améliorer ces problèmes, 200 millions de dollars du Fonds d'innovation seront alloués à l'investissement dans de nouvelles entreprises dérivées et en phase de démarrage;

- *Collaboration.* Cette notion fait référence au partenariat entre les esprits brillants de la recherche et l'environnement des entreprises. À l'heure actuelle, seuls 43% des chercheurs australiens sont engagés dans des activités commerciales, par rapport à l'Allemagne (56%), à South Correa (79%) ou à Israël (84%). (OCDE 2015) L'objectif est d'accroître le degré d'innovation, de créativité et d'accroître l'activité d'exportation de l'entreprise grâce à la productivité du travail.

- *Talent et capacités.* Ces deux capacités sont le moteur pour augmenter la productivité du travail. En Australie, 13 millions de dollars sont investis dans la participation des femmes à la recherche, aux sciences et aux entreprises, et 45 millions de dollars supplémentaires pour motiver les étudiants et les jeunes à participer à des concours internationaux en sciences réelles ou socio-humaines;

- *Gouvernement exemplaire.* Un gouvernement efficace, organisé et innovateur est celui qui crée l'ensemble du système économique basé sur la croissance économique par l'innovation, la recherche.

¹¹ National Innovation and Science Agenda, Commonwealth of Australia 2015 Report, 2015, 5, <http://innovation.gov.au/system/files/casestudy/National%20Innovation%20and%20Science%20Agenda%20-%20Report.pdf> (accessed 05.04.2019).

L'Australie est un pays qui met l'accent sur l'importance du capital humain. L'innovation, la créativité, les compétences et les connaissances acquises par les travailleurs grâce à l'éducation et à l'expérience dépendent directement de la croissance du bien-être.

En conclusion, on estime que le progrès économique d'un pays dépend du degré de mobilisation et d'utilisation intensive de ses propres ressources et de sa capacité à participer activement au processus d'internationalisation économique. La participation active aux processus économiques mondiaux renforce les efforts de chaque pays pour accélérer le progrès économique. En conséquence, le bien-être de l'humanité est le résultat du progrès économique de chaque pays et de l'échange de valeurs matérielles et spirituelles entre eux. L'utilisation de l'innovation et le modèle de l'économie créative prouvent de loin qu'ils ajoutent de la valeur à l'entreprise, à l'institution et, si l'entreprise crée à son tour un environnement favorable au développement personnel, la croissance du bien-être est un facteur garanti et réalisé.

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Mega-Sciences and Public Administration

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Abstract. The paper considers the current issue of correlation between universal concepts, theories, innovations, management, complex systems analysis and public administration. On the basis of that we construct the substantial synergetic potential of Public Administration of the future.

Keywords: public administration, mega-science, synergetic potential.

“politics will be substituted only by scientific management and scientific governance of public economy”

N. I. Bukharin, *Selected Works*, Moscow, 1990

Presentation of the problem

We will start from the generally accepted statement that there is much variety in the practice of Public Administration (PA) around the world. The second point is that Public Administration is not only about the administration itself, but also about public values (Ringeling, 2013). The third point that for more than two decades we have been observing waves of public administration reforms. Sometimes these waves turn out to be “tsunamis” with very diverse outcomes (Drehler et al., 2010). And some authors assume that technology does matter in the current PA reforms and will do even more in the future (Vintar, 2010). In spite that the field of PA is predominantly driven from the classical administrative or New Public Management doctrines, we pointed out the role of ICT in PA in some

creative manner (Hancharonak, 2012) by mentioning the German sociologist and political economist Max Weber who developed the concept of rational bureaucracy, what we now call traditional hierarchical organizational management structure that among all other levels stretches to governmental dimension. On the other hand, however, considering that even school-kids know what Internet can do, we can as well say they are actually aware of web-technologies implying evolvement of “web” non-hierarchical management approaches. Thus, we noticed evident linguistic coincidence and at the same time considerable difference in content of the processes themselves.

However, not only ICT but other future technologies, such as bio-and nano-technologies have a substantial transforming potential in PA which Mirko Vintar (2010) proposed roughly classify into three stages:

- Technology as a tool;
- Technology is an enabling infrastructure;
- Technology as a “trend setter”.

Such a growing and many-vectorial role technology for PA on the future forced us to overview some mega-sciences which provide the methodological basis for the technological development.

Methods

Cybernetics. In fact, the rise of this mega-science dates back to 1948, the year the book “Cybernetics” by Norbert Wiener was first published. Focused on the processes of management and regulation as well as on the phenomenon of information, cybernetics has already drawn much attention to the sphere of its studies. Besides, cybernetic models and regularities have become widely applied to social systems claiming to be treated as universal discipline-dominated theoretical “constructions”. Their relevance and effectiveness in social processes, however, has proved to be not that crucial as expected before and wide approval of the cybernetic approach has been considerably graded.

System Approach. Two basic ideas, in A. Krushanov's view (2001), constitute this branch of knowledge: the idea of systematic approach is viewed as "the whole is more than the sum of its parts" or " $2+2=5$ " (see Figure 1) and the idea of prevalence of system regularities. Though, for the time-being, according to the author, system researches have been fruitful in many ways and having implemented all their starting heuristic potential they gave place to one more claimant for megascience – synergetics.

Figure 1 When "simplicity is worth than steeling" (Russian saying)

Synergetics. In the period from 1977 to 1978 there was a rise of a new interdisciplinary domain – synergy called so by its founder Hermann Haken, a physicist, professor of Stuttgart University. Hence, the domain just faces its 40-years history that is unlikely to be sufficient for regarding it as well-established and approved branch of knowledge. Even more so, the

development of macroscopic systems studied by synergy may take much more time. Consequently, there are sure to be possible ill-defined problems and even mistakes particularly when synergetic principles are applied to social systems and if there are attempts of revealing the absolute algorithm in solving all the current issues or applying “synergetic” way of their interpretation. H. Haken (1983) defined synergetics as an interdisciplinary branch of knowledge which investigates “study of systems consisting of a number of subsystems of any nature like electrons ... and even people”.

H. Haken’s “even” once again underlines the necessity of careful implementation of synergetic principals applied to social systems and society with the human as their leading element. Influence increase of religious, ethic, psychological, cultural, ecological, social and political factors of human activities have led to considerable changes in social sphere as well. There has been a break-through in engineering and technology. Strong competition, resource shortage, unevenness of states development, (i.e. it is stated in the report of the Roman Club “the industrial revolution which began in England two hundred years ago has not come to its end yet in some parts of the world”). Social life, in general, has become more mobile and diverse due to political instability and restriction of activities of economic entities by the government caused by escalation of ecological and social problems. Multiple-choice alternative, coincidence (or rather probability), irreversibility are of great importance for social environment and they determine its constantly growing complication as managerial aims are achieved.

Synergy has its principle contribution in forming the conception of self-organization of the developing world which in its turn has a number of versions of its development. Synergy enabled to expose a constructive function of dynamic chaos invariantly with regard to organic and inorganic life as the science itself analyses the universe on the basis of general principles controlling the rise of self-organized structures and / or functions. It is relevant when the beginnings of a new microscopic structure are caused by emergence of “collective modes” under the influence of frequency, their

competition and selection of the most adapted mode or a combination of modes.

Undoubtedly, this approach contributes to scientific search and making such a system of administration which meets basic tendencies of the society. At the same time, it should be underlined that we consider the analysis of interaction of two fundamental and interrelated processes – public (premeditated, centralized, institutional) administration (regulation) and social self-organization (this process is inherently decentralized and poorly institutional) as well as a search of the most appropriate correlation between external centralized administration and self-government in the process of social system regulation. It would be unfair to give much importance to “creative abilities of chaos” in the matter of society organization and to think of public administration as a possible (due to this small-scale and even sporadic) means of social self-organization.

The Soviet history events like self-destruction of the USSR in the period of stagnation and super-centralized power, the throw of the country into the deep of real (not invented) chaos, the experience of “color revolutions”, nowadays terroristic attacks teach us to take a new approach to public administration. Today it is still important to realize the significance of state power and public administration at least for self-preservation of a concrete society or a state preserving them from degradation and finally from total disappearance.

It must be admitted, however, recent excessive reference to synergy didn't lead to any well approved and achieved findings in social sciences and humanities notwithstanding some high expectations made before. Though, it is quite relevant to bring as an example some fundamental restrictions on complex systems predictability set in recent decades.

Thus, it is possible to agree with the viewpoint of the researchers (Knyazeva and Kurdumov, 2007) that it is necessary to realize not only possibility of synergy application to social sciences and humanities but also obvious restrictions to application of synergy models to these fields. On the other hand, the view of V. S. Stepin, a member of the Academy of Sciences

of the Russian Federation, may be viable that it is synergetics which is to take the leading place in the center of the world scientific map in the 21st century.

Innovations viewed as a result based on the system approach. We regard system approaches in education and science reforms as appropriate concerning the refinement of the state recognised List of Research Specialties. Institutionalization of “PA” as a new scientific specialty can be, in fact, an effective innovation itself (on the territory of the Former Soviet space, except for Ukraine where such a research discipline has been introduced on the national level). Its implementation, however, is related to some factors restricting innovations in the field of public administration. From another side, special attention should be focused on training administrative personnel and young leaders. This is exactly the main point for efficient innovations in the sphere of administration and, thus, a tendency to make regulation of innovations and public regulation of innovation activities large-scale and directed. A competency-based approach should be mentioned which indicates that to have a skilled specialist is not enough but just necessary for solving a complex problem. Relevance of a competent specialist and the competency known as williness to accept innovations have become a key requirement. It is just the competency which can be essential for a nonlinear model in innovation activities by analogy with nonlinear optics (it should be noted, the Nobel Prize in physics was given for this achievement). So, the result of innovation activities (P) can be formalized in the following way:

$$P = P_l + P_{nl}, \quad (1)$$

hereby P_{nl} is proportional to χ , which we called as susceptibility to innovations; P_l - denotes the result in the framework of a linear model.

Hence, it is of primary importance for young PA leaders to acquire the competency known as williness to accept innovations. We hold the view that this is one of the prevailing ideas how to improve the present-day system of PA education.

Modern Management. At present, many researchers instinctively predict that the 21st century will bring serious changes in today's understanding of management, i.e. a switch to another administration paradigm is expected. It is mainly determined by strengthening the so-called society synergetic parameters: openness – globalization, nonlinearity – integration, instability – dynamism. A distinctively new administrative paradigm is based on the next evident transformations:

- from functional to process administration;
- from work in groups to teamwork;
- from decision-making to topical tasks formulation;
- from governing people to people's power;
- from knowledge for administration to knowledge management;
- from training to learning.

Public and “nonlinear” administration

Now we shall concentrate on synergy principals of PA analysis. First, it is significant, that synergy potential of public administration is predetermined by state and society intercourse. Being hierarchical, viability of the present-day social system is impossible without social restrictions. The law of hierarchical compensations has been discovered. Under the law, an upgrowth in diversity at the top level in a complex hierarchical system is made possible only if there is the lack of it at the previous ones. The same law, however, works in the reverse way when an upgrowth in diversity reaches the bottom it levels down the top level of an organization. As a result, the system can be destroyed. Therefore, the presence of fundamental social restrictions cannot be interpreted one-sidedly – as unable for further development. While a social system is in due functioning and development its evolution is referred to the growth of new forms of organization as a result of “the growth of stability from instability because of instability” just as due to “a number of fundamental ideas and images, ... shaping common tendencies for process development in it”.

Through PA the state is an organizing centre of social life being not just restrictive and suppressive but having, above all, constructive power. Under Hegel's definition of the state, it is the most perfect organization of social life based on legal norms representing the reign of real life. From another side, historically the role and entity of the state was not constituent enough and much distorted. It was determined by imperfection of the state and low awareness of the society as well as by inconsiderate progress in the science.

H. Kelsen views the role of the state to be in charge of maintenance of order and legal regulation equal for all citizens in the society. It took the whole epoch to find the proper treatment of the problem pertaining to society and state development and was first put into effect in legal democratic societies. But from the very beginning the state power guaranteed the formation of social integrity with the help of law, established norms of human relations. "A state is a specially organized universality and integrity that constitutes legal regulation".

Conclusions

Therefore, it has to be acknowledged, the rise of the state became the most significant form of society self-organization, its major political mechanism, necessary as well as a regulating parameter (a synergy order parameter) of social self-organization. In this stage of state's development, there haven't become apparent any well-known inconsistencies between state activity and processes of self-regulation in the society.

A new stage of self-regulation in the society comprises two rather distinct forms of entity and methods of society organization, that is, civil society and national legal society. At the present stage there is a task to ensure close interaction between the two forms as well as reveal the drawbacks of the previous stage of social development. On its way to democracy the state was highly criticized: its constituent nature was found weak virtues existing in the society were admitted incapable of ruling the roost in the world and was allocated only to restrain vices. Some most

radical thinkers insisted on a strong position the society and the state: “one can encourage rapprochement, the other can bring disagreement”, “the first is a defender, the second is a punisher”; therefore “anyway, society is blessing, the government even the best one is a necessary curse, the worth of it is a curse extremely implacable”.

At the same time, as it has been demonstrated in the due course of history, state power and public administration will never be withdrawn as Marxism and Leninism founders and followers had predicted and will not be substituted by communist self-organization (social self-organization). At this point, “oscillation process” typical of synergetic systems is more likely to take place. In this respect we support the view of A. Kulichenko (2004), that methods and mechanisms of public administration should undergo changes. But the conclusion that main functions of public administration will stay the same even in time of the most efficient self-organization of social system – we cannot approve of. Thus, the system of society regulation should be a reasonable combination of hierarchical organization, legal regulation and control with new structures and functions aimed at perception of minor and occasional signals and changes, stimulation of positive tendencies. And legal regulations and public administrators are to have resonant adjustment to these new structures and functions to generate a synergetic effect. Maintenance of change and stability, traditions and innovations are the ground points which are to specify creative, spontaneous processes in the society and public administration, viewed as basic elements of (modes) social self-organization. As it has been stated above, synergy potential of public administration is generally determined by dualism of the state and the society. Society potential is chiefly implemented by means of administration. Its development, including the form of a new institutionalized specialty for researchers as “PA” comprising cybernetic studies, system and synergetic approaches as well as other approaches referred to megascience-related methods highlighted by A. Krushanov. Another way of society potential increasing is intellectually saturated technologies and corresponding institutional changes (Hancharonak, 2018,

2019) implementation in life-long system of education for public administrators.

Thus, turning back to the epigraph of the given paper we would agree with the author's predictions made in the 19th century having substituted the last word "public economy" by the word "state".

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Re-Assessing the Depth of State and International Law in Soviet Ideology

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Abstract. This article seeks to examine how the concepts of state and international law have been ascertained and assimilated into practice in the Soviet Union despite having a fervent ideological opposition to the said concepts. Furthermore the objective of this article lies in examining the contribution made by major Soviet jurists to the realm of international law and in order to comprehend the scope of state and place of international law in the Soviet Union, this article has made a historical observation. Results emerging from this article could be utilized in appreciating the scholarly contribution of the USSR to international law and at the same time this article has unveiled anomalies that existed between Marxian doctrine and Soviet practice on law and state.

Keywords: Soviet, State, International Law, Ideology.

The events took place in October 1917 Russia disrupted the myth of impossibility of creating a proletarian state and in the words of John Reed's "The ten days that shook the world" it broke the existing myth about formation of socialist society and the creation of the USSR in 1921 saw the emergence of different ideological, political bastion in the world, which lasted for seven decades of modern history. Nevertheless the state apparatus adopted by Soviets on treating state, international law have had peculiarities from how they were perceived by Western democratic states in Europe and the USA. Ascertaining the scope of state and international law under Soviet doctrine have generated an academic knack during the heyday of the USSR as an interesting topic and the greater ambiguity loomed before understanding of Soviet doctrine to state and international law was essentially attributed to the unavailability of materials in English and the

articles written on the subject were more or less filled with misshapen facts on Soviet doctrine. Even though it's been two decades after the dissolution of the USSR the legacy left by Soviets on treating state and international law from their doctrinal perspective still remain quite attractive to examine. In this article we make an attempt to recognize the exact nature of state described in Soviet doctrine after the revolution and how the Soviet state organized itself would be examined in this article, also we further examine the anomaly between the international law practice in the USSR and the Marxist-Leninist ideology towards the law generally.

In tracing the conception of state from Soviet perspective, it should be understood that cardinal understanding of state is imbued with the Marxian dogma of state and the very roots of Soviet understanding of state have been bulwarked by the depiction of state as an oppressive tool. Pioneer of Bolshevik revolution Lenin himself took the task of comprehending the notion of state in accordance with his understanding of Engel's book "The Origin of family, private property and State" and having gained much profound inspiration from Engels' discourse on state, Lenin went on to propound his own concept of state which eventually paved its path to become an inherent part of Soviet ideology on state. In his classic work "State and Revolution" Lenin states "State is the product of irreconcilability of class antagonism. The state arises then and there, when and where class antagonism cannot be objectively reconciled. Or to reverse the object: the existence of state proves that class antagonism is irreconcilable".¹ Lenin seemed to be adamant on his staunch belief that state would play a less role in mediating in the class struggle and his view on state as villain was decorated from his deep historical analysis over how state has hindered the class struggle through enabling the continuation of class structure. While quoting Engels, Lenin states "not only the state in antiquity and Middle Age had been organs of exploitation of slaves and serfs, but even the contemporary representative state is an instrument of exploitation

¹ V. I. Lenin, *State and Revolution*, First Edition (New York: International Publishers, 1943), 24.

of hired labor by capital". Having seen the decedent nature of state in its historic role as brutal organizer of class division, Lenin believed in the classic Marxian prediction of the extinction of state from its very existence. After following the hypothesis established in Engels' work, Lenin affirmed in his thoughts that state is naturally destined to be ceased from its existence in a society where class does not exist anymore. He states: "With the extinction of classes the real state itself will inevitably pass out of existence. The society which will organize production on a new basis of free and equal association will relegate the state where it shall belong: to the museum of antiquities along with the spinning wheel and the bronze axe".²

However, the incongruity of Marxian idea of withering away of state began to appear in the dawn of the USSR as world first socialist state as its approach to conception of state was paradoxical at outset from what Engels propounded, because in Engels' belief "state will not be eliminated, but will wither away". But the emergence of the USSR as a union under proletarian dominance did not accomplish the Marxian desire of seeing the withering away of state, instead of it transformed into a more rigid state mechanism. According to Lenin the proletarian state will succeed the bourgeois state and then it will reach the ultimate state of withering away. When withering away stage seemed to be an anomaly after formation of the Soviet Union, it was Stalin who gave the maiden Soviet interpretation of state at his address to the 18th congress of Communist party. Stalin's position on state and reason for its existence without withering away emphasized that as it would be an impossible task to reach the withering away stage of state as long as one socialist state has been surrounded by capitalist countries which was the exact situation envisaged by the USSR after October revolution.³ For example, the proletarian need to crush the remaining of capitalistic society was reflected in the Article 9 of the constitution adopted by Soviets in 1918. It states: "The fundamental aim of the Constitution of the Russian Socialist

² Ibid.

³ Mintatuts Chakste, "Soviet Concepts of State, International Law and Sovereignty," *American Journal of International Law*, vol. 43, No. 1 (1956): 35.

Federal Soviet Republic, designed for the present transition period, is to establish a dictatorship of the urban and rural proletariat and the poorest peasantry in the form of a powerful All-Russian Soviet government with a view to crushing completely the bourgeoisie, abolishing the exploitation of man by man, and establishing socialism, under which there will be no divisions into classes and no state power”.

The continuity of state after revolution and the conceptual approach to state in Soviet doctrine saw many challenges as it began negate itself from original idea of Marxism. As described above the USSR was surrounded by a number of capitalist states and but maintaining international relations with those states was inevitable as the political and social unrest were blooming before the severe economic dislocation. Large parts of the country were affected by famine resulting from civil war policies of forced requisition of grain from the peasantry. However, in 1921 Great Britain happened to be the first country to accept Lenin’s offer of trade which led to sign Anglo-Soviet Trade Agreement in 1921 and Britain took one step further by accepting de facto existence of Soviet state. However, the continuation of international relations between the USSR and bourgeois, capitalist states shocked the proletarian movement in the USSR as the later was the incarnation of evil which is the fundamental caused prolonging the emergence of communist society. From Marxist-Leninist ideology the Soviet state needed to fight for the liberation of world working class against the bourgeois states and the tools to be used in this battle were not ballot boxes and voting paper which known to be Communists as debilitating tools, but the instruments supposed to be used in this crucial struggle was summed up in the term “World Revolution”. But the question arose was that how would it be legitimate to continue a state mechanism and relations with other states which was known in Soviet terminology as “Capitalist Encirclement”. This dilemma was confronted by Soviet jurists and mainly it was their theoretical task to trace legal aspect of state and the relation between the USSR and the states of “capitalist encirclement”. In examining the Soviet attitude to state it is important to observe the two ideological differences

displayed by two grand jurists of early Soviet era Korovin and Pashukanis. Korovin's position was essentially painted from the antipathy on seeing state as an oppressive tool and he went on to say: "These illustrations permit to draw the conclusion that the theory of class structure of the contemporary state is not only a very instrumental hypothesis for understanding the mutual relations between Soviet Russia and the world of imperialistic colossuses and pygmies, but also the official doctrine of the USSR which is consistently released by the government in building up the structure of the republic as well as in its international relations".⁴

However, Korovin's position was criticized by another prominent Soviet jurist Eugene Pashukanis vehemently albeit his initial admittance of state as an instrument of class oppression and he too denied the state centric solution for clashing class struggles, yet his opposition to Korovin's position emerged from his reaction to seeing foreign relations with others states as a unity. Nevertheless, it was highly vague to understand whether Pashukanis regarded Non Soviet state as a personified unity and none of his writings give a clue about his exact understanding of statehood under international law, especially his masterwork *General Theory of Law and Marxism* was mainly referring to elucidating the deep inter connection between the legal form and the commodity form in Marxism. When Pashukanis was finally vanished by Stalin's purge, Korovin became the only authentic Soviet state jurist for interpreting Soviet concept of "State". All in all the Soviet attitude to state was moulded under the guise that the legitimacy of state intervention in some circumstances. Regarding the intervention upon state, it should be really important to observe that Soviet theory does not solely reject the idea of intervention. Korovin has looked at the interventions of allied powers in Russia in 1918-1919 as the realization of the principle of class struggle on an international scale and says: "As such their legal aspects are acceptable to the legal scene of the transitional epoch, as class struggle is the established method of mutual relations

⁴ Eugene Korovin, "The Second World War and International Law," *American Journal of International Law*, vol. 40 (1946): 742.

between opposite worlds on the international arena. The strictly negative attitude of the Russian working people to the various interventions by the allied powers does not indicate the rejection of intervention as a method of class struggle. It was rejection and condemnation of those given interventions”.⁵

With this anomaly Soviet attitude to understanding the concept of state should be understood in light of the transitions period faced by the USSR after revolution and Korovin’s justification upon other state sovereignty was as alien factor throughout his writings. He pointed out “The mightiest instruments of progress, a surgical measures to ease the birth pangs of a new world”. This embellished phase seemed to have stood as Soviet justification of state intervention since 1939. In doing a deeper examination about the Soviet understanding on the relations between proletarian state and non-communist “capitalist encirclement”, the original Marxist-Leninist doctrine of class struggle always stood as an indispensable factor. It was always prevalent in the writings of Korovin and before him Stalin had aptly pointed out the ultimate objective of Soviet state in upholding its principles relating to statehood and sovereignty. Stalin said: “The victory of the revolution of one country at the same time is the beginning of the perquisite of the world revolution”. His explanation of Soviet state practice affirmed Lenin’s original position of duty of one proletarian state to help other proletarian movements around the world to achieve their revolutionary efforts. According to Stalin: “The victorious proletariat of one country should rise against the remaining capitalist world attracting the oppressed classes of other countries, starting revolts against the capitalists in these countries, and in case of necessity, even sending its military forces against the exploiting classes and their states”.⁶

It is evident that Soviet concept of state was an evolving one in accordance with the circumstances and it is important to remember that at

⁵ Id., “Mezdunarodnoye pravo na sovremennom etape,” *Bolshevik*, No. 16, 21 October 1946, 26.

⁶ Mintatuts Chakste, *Op. cit.*

least from its outlook Soviet perception was in compliance with original Marxist-Leninist doctrine, but its real structure was frequently subjected to the needs of Communist party and the events that the USSR faced in its struggle to survive.

The uptake of international law by Soviet jurists was another interesting phenomenon which caused uproar in Western academic circles, because mainly the Marxian antagonism on law and state had created a sheer curiosity among Western scholars to find out how Soviet treated international law. Nevertheless, tracing Soviet approach to international law should distinguish from what pre-revolutionary Russia understood by international law. It is a fact beyond dispute that Russia approach to international law emerged as an off shoot of its involvement in the West as a civilizational dialogue during the period of Peter the Great where Russia was persuading to reach the stage of European modernity. In his article entitled "The History of International Legal Theory in Russia: a Civilizational Dialogue with Europe" Lauri Malksoo believed early efforts of international legal scholarship in Tsarist Russia was mainly attributed to Peter's the Great forced Europeanization which resulted in making Russia a late bloomer in *ius publicum europenium*. Malksoo states: "Obviously before Peter's reforms, there could have been no Russian international law scholarship".⁷ Peter Pavlovich Shafrov was the pioneer of international law scholarship in Peter's the Great court and he wrote the first printed argument in Russian in the international law of "Civilized Nations" in 1716 and he was much enthusiastic in appealing for Western European public opinion in order prove Russia is a civilized Western country. He was anxious in realizing this was not seen self-evident in the West. He states: "For several decades the Russian people and state have been discussed and written about in other European states are the Indians and the Persians and other peoples which have no communication with Europe except some trade. Russia was not

⁷ Lauri Malksoo, "The History of International legal Theory in Russia: a Civilizational Dialogue with Europe," *European Journal of International Law*, vol. 9 (2008): 211.

seen as participant in European matters of peace and war and was even rarely counted among the European nations”.⁸

However, the attitude towards international law by Soviets was fundamentally different from imperial Russian prejudices on international law and Soviet understanding was entirely determined by Marxist and Leninist theory. Korovin states: “It is the right moment to comprehend the elementary truth that such notions as Marxism, proletarian dictatorship and the rest of the ideological foundations of the state and social order of contemporary Russia are categories binding in many ways: one cannot at the same time propagate them, defend the class nature of social relations, accept the economic materialism as the basis of sociology, and simultaneously endeavor to enact policy law on the basis of unprincipled eclecticism. In controversies of doctrines and theories, in heated disputes of jurists, historians and diplomats, the jurists of the USSR has once place – he must remember, know and defend it”.⁹

Korovin’s attempt to read international law under Soviet narrative was admirable in a state where international law had been derogated by its doctrine itself as a bourgeois tool reached its zenith by capitalist patronage. Especially it was a real matter of impossibility for Soviet state which stood for the interests of proletarian dictatorship to accept and adjust itself for international legal norms made by bourgeois character. Korovin states: “The deeply rooted fundamental difference of the legal and social order of capitalist society on one hand and socialist order on the other entails a manifold and substantial alteration of legal norms governing mutual relations between the bourgeois countries and the socialist ones. The sum total of these norms will form one of the regional international legal systems which could be designated as “the international law of the transitional epoch”. The historic limit for the international law of the transitional epoch

⁸ P. S. Shafirov, *A Discourse Concerning the Just Cause of War between Sweden and Russia: 1700-1721* (Dobbs Ferry, N.Y.: Oceana Publications, 1973), 45 [with an introduction by W. E Butler].

⁹ Eugene Korovin, *Loc. cit.*

would not be the day when the state machinery is handed over to the “museum of antiquity”, but the day of victory of the proletarian revolution in the countries of the capitalist West”.¹⁰

In overall understanding the Soviet jurists were not in a position of appreciating any kind of intellectual comity with the Western international legal academia, because as they firmly believed that intercourse between Soviet state and other states was just a pretext that was expected to be ended by world revolution abolishing the capitalist order in the world. In such a context that intellectual discourse between Soviet state and the intellectuals from bourgeois state always seemed to be impossibility, because the very existence of Soviet state was described as “A most convincing negation of the whole of the bourgeois order as such and constant threat to its security”. Korovin’s notion of international law was known as “International law in the time of transition” which was the title he provided for his text in 1933 which provided a comprehensive account in Soviet understanding of international law. As we see Korovin appeared as a strict opponent of maintaining a closer intellectual discourse between Soviet state and other states which stated as “an intercourse on the basis of intellectual unity (ideological solidarity) between countries of bourgeois and socialist cultures cannot exist as a rule and hence rules of international law covering this intercourse become pointless” yet, Korovin did not forget the fact that certain sets of rules can exist in terms of upholding fundamental needs in world order such as prevention of the epidemics, preservation of monuments of antiquity, works of art, etc.

In understanding the Soviet attitude towards the treaty law that it becomes a salient factor, that the “most favored nation” clause was widely used in dealing the trade agreements with Soviet republics. Such a clause appears either in its absolute form, or under the form of conditional (compensational) favoredness, occasionally giving way to preferential regulations more or less extensive in scope. But apart from using it among the Soviet republic the USSR seemed to have opted for “Most Favored

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 45.

Clause” in making trade agreements with capitalist Western states. For example, Korovin has elaborated on an article entitled “Soviet Treaties and International Law” the scope of “Most Favored Nation” clause used in the trade treaties between the Soviet Union and Great Britain, which was pointed out by Korovin as a mere commercial application of the treaty. Regarding the trade agreement existed between Germany and Russia, Korovin states: “Article 16 of the provisional Russo-German agreement of May 6, 1921, proclaims “the spirit of mutual benevolence which should strengthen economic ties.” Articles 8 and 9 guarantee Russian citizens “the prescriptions of international law and of the German common law.” Comparing this convention with Article 4 of the Treaty of Rapallo (April 16, 1922), “making provisions for the application of the principle of the most favored nation to the laws affecting foreigners and to the commercial relations of the two states, we find, in Article 4, that the clause becomes operative only from the day of the ratification of this diplomatic instrument, which is sufficient evidence that this principle had, prior thereto, been absent”.¹¹

Along with Prof. Korovin, Evgeni Pasukanis was another noted Soviet scholar who made a hall mark legacy in Soviet legal scholarship. Being a rigorous critic of Marxism, Pashukanis believed in the withering away of state and law in his active days as the most prominent Soviet legal scholar before his rival Korovin took his place. In fact his initial engagement in international law was much lesser than the contribution he made upon developing the Marxian understanding of jurisprudence and his masterwork “General Theory of Law and Marxism”, but he provided a sharp analysis on international law in his later work “Encyclopedia of State and Law”, a mammoth work published by Communist Academy between 1925 and 1927. Pasukanis shared the same view as Prof. Korovin on international law as a hegemonic tool for class struggle and world domination of the capitalist states and according to him the inherent nature of class division maintained

¹¹ Eugene Korovin, “Printsip suvereneta v sovetskom i mezhdunarodnom prave,” Pravda, XXI, 26 March 1947, 8.

by law has been covered through the technical language used by bourgeois jurists. The common phrases which have been frequently used in international law like “international community”, sovereign equality were subjected to wider criticism of Pashukanis as rhetorical quibble used by bourgeois scholars to conceal the class nature. He states: “Neither do they see or want to see, that the “international community” they depict in their writings reflects the common interests of the ruling classes of different states with identical state structures”.¹²

The doctrinal notion of civilized and semi-civilized states in international law was another feature Pashukanis found as the reflection of the class nature in international law. In its inherent unjust beginning, international law has derived its legitimacy from the fact that how bourgeoisie states organized in separate state political trusts that dominates the proletarian and colonial states, however in Pashukanis’ view international law comes to a different direction with the influx of the Soviet Union, in the presence of later system international law becomes an inter class law wherein bourgeois order cannot maintain the entire world domination anymore due to the rise of proletarian system. According to Pashukanis: “The only real guarantee that the relationships between the bourgeois states (and in the transitional period with states of another class type) will remain on the basis of equivalent exchange, on a legal basis (on the basis of mutual recognition of the subjects) is the real balance of forces. Within the limits set by a given balance of forces separate questions may be decided by compromise and exchange on the basis of law”.¹³

The approaches used by Pashukanis and Korovin towards international law have clearly been based on the Marxist-Leninist ideology and it is important to understand that jurists who have emerged from Marxist tradition they had not forgotten their doctrinal view of seeing law as a part of economic exploitation and the it was their belief that international

¹² Evgeny Pashukanis, *Law and Marxism: A General Theory*, Revised Edition (London: Pluto Press, 1987), 90.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 123.

law propounded after the creation of Soviet state would work for the greater expectations of the masses. Cardinal notion of Soviet doctrine is, of course, that of state sovereignty. Exercise of sovereignty has in fact been the most important sociological context in which the Soviet conception of international law developed. For many years Soviet jurisprudence interpreted state sovereignty in an absolute sense. It is only recently that has come to recognize that sovereignty under law more desirable than sovereignty above law, a feat which is worthy of praise. What is however less certain is whether Soviet juristic ideology identified itself with the original Marxian view that valued sovereignty as a dynamic factor, capable of shattering the *status quo* for the benefit of revolutionary change or whether it shifted toward a conservative position which cherished sovereignty because it centralized power and served the interest of stability. All in all the legacy made by Soviet jurists in international law was not faded into oblivion with the dissolution of the USSR as it's insights continued to inspire third world legal scholars in constructing their narratives on colonialism and law. For example, the TWAIL (Third World Approach to International Law) scholarship emerged from newly independent developing countries based their doctrinal view on international law as a colonial creation after getting a deep influence of Soviet readings.

In this brief article we have attempted to retrospect the approach used by Soviet jurists in understanding the conception of international law as a class tool and Soviet interpretation of state. The glimpse of today's history shows us the success of Soviet approach to international law and their decay as well, especially when it comes to recognizing people's right to self-determination the contribution provided by the USSR remains majestic in the annals of history. Regarding the new direction of international law tradition emerging in post-Soviet Russia, it may be still inconclusive assume whether Russia would develop and consolidate itself much towards the Western mainstream notion of international law or create their own unique approach while keeping the rich tradition they inherited from Marxist-Leninist ideology.

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The Coup Attempt from Turkey and the Models of Decision-Making

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Abstract. The purpose of this article is to study the coup attempt in Turkey from 2016 and the models of decision making according to this event. The objectives of the article are: to detail the coup attempt, to present the context of the negotiations between Turkey and the European Union, to analyze three models of decision about this event, to evaluate obstacles in the negotiation process between Turkey and the European Union. Regarding methodology, I will start with the theoretical part (from special sources). There are official documents of studying the international elements.

Keywords: Turkey, coup attempt, models of decision making, negotiations.

Introduction

Before the coup attempt the Turkish state was in a process of Europeanization, amid the European crisis. It will be shown the context of negotiations between the European Union and Turkey. Currently, Turkey has made efforts to get closer to Europe, but does not meet yet all the conditions for the membership of the European Union, so that all the negotiation chapters to be closed. To solve this problem, the EU works towards revealing the mandatory requirements related to the accession process, while the candidate country is striving to meet its membership conditions by creating the necessary institutions during the process. At the moment, Turkey is no longer so interested in joining the European Union, searching for possible alternatives through cooperation with countries such as Russia or China.

I had chosen this subject, because it seems an interesting subject in the light of the last events. Also, the events from the neighborhood of the European Union left their mark.

There will be studied the changes made by the coup attempt through the models of decision making (the rational actor model, the cybernetic model and the cognitive approach). That part explains the reasons behind the development of Turkey (through the three models of decision making). Also, in this analysis the personal contribution will be seen.

One of the priorities of the European Union was the enlargement in the East and South. Unfortunately, in the last period the EU faces major crises in its structure and the enlargement in that part of Europe was postponed. The important points for the European structure were: the economic crises, the situation with Russia, the migration problem, Brexit negotiations, which represented different threats for the stability of the EU.

Details of the coup attempt

On July 15, 2016, there was a failed state coup in Turkey organized by the Peace Council,¹ a group of Turkish armed forces. The coup attempt was confirmed by the Prime Minister, Binali Yildirim,² and by the president, Recep Tayyip Erdogan, who called the people in the street. The chief of staff, Hulusi Akar, was taken hostage,³ later released. More than 290 people were killed in Ankara and Istanbul during confrontations.⁴

¹ Niculae Popa, "Lovitură de stat în Turcia. Armata a anunțat într-un comunicat citit la televiziunea națională că Turcia este condusă în prezent de Consiliul Păcii," *Adevărul*, 16 July 2016, <http://adevarul.ro/international/in-lume/lovitura-stat-turcia-armata-anuntat-intr-un-comunicat-citit-televiziuneanationala-turcia-condusa-prezent-consiliul-pacii-1> (accessed 15.12.2017).

² Sam Levin, Kevin Rawlinson, "Turkey military coup: tanks open fire near parliament building – live updates," *The Guardian*, 15 July 2016, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/live/2016/jul/15/turkey-coup-attempt-military-gunfire-ankara> (accessed 15.12.2017).

³ Henry Bodkin, David Millward, Josie Ensor, James Rothwell, "Turkey coup: military attempt to seize power from Erdogan as low flying jets and gunfire heard in Ankara and bridges across Bosphorus in Istanbul closed," *The Telegraph*, 17 July 2016, <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2016/07/17/turkey-coup-plot-president-erdogan-rounds-up-thousands-of-soldie/> (accessed 15.12.2017).

⁴ Ion Gaidău, "Tentativă de lovitură de stat în Turcia: 60 de morți la Ankara. SUA și Germania susțin guvernul ales, Rusia se declară îngrijorată," *Adevărul*, 15 July 2016, http://adevarul.ro/international/in-lume/alerta-turcia-tentativa-lovitura-stat-1_578947335-ab6550cb8e42860/index.html (accessed 15.12.2017).

General Akin Ozturk was the head of the coup. A helicopter launched a bomb above the Turkish Parliament in Ankara.⁵ The Presidential Palace was attacked with bombs and the martial law was declared throughout Turkish territory. National TV, TRT 1, was occupied by Turkish militants who announced that Turkey is ruled by the Peace Council, which will ensure the safety of the population. The border with Bulgaria has been closed and the Greek army has been alerted to the border with Turkey. Another consequence was that a group of over 50 soldiers blocked the Bosphorus Bridge and Fatih Sultan Mehmet Bridge. There has been heard gunfire near the most important airports in Ankara and Istanbul.

President Erdogan accused Fethullah Gulen (self-exiled in Pennsylvania) for organizing this coup, although his group condemned the coup.⁶ After the coup attempt Turkey has called for the US to extradite Gulen. The coup was condemned by the main parties in Turkey and by the international community.⁷

For a general point of view, in the next chapter it can be seen the context of negotiations and the development from the same period (2016) from the most relevant areas.

The context of the negotiations and the models of decision making

The status of Turkey is the one of a candidate state (in 1987 it applied to join the European Economic Community and in 1997 it was declared eligible to join the EU). Involvement for European integration dates

⁵ "Ankara parliament building 'bombed from air' – state agency," *RT*, 15 July 2016, <https://www.rt.com/news/351425-ankara-parliament-bomb-dropped/> (accessed 15.12.2017).

⁶ Mirela Egeea, "Cel puțin 90 de morți și 1154 de răniți în tentativa militară de lovitură de stat din Turcia," *Secunda*, 16 July 2016, <http://www.secundatv.ro/externe/cel-putin-90-de-morti-si-1-154-de-raniti-in-tentativa-militara-de-lovitura-de-stat-din-turcia-37552.html/> (accessed 15.12.2017).

⁷ Orhan Coskun, Dasha Afanasieva, David Dolan, "All flights from Istanbul's Ataturk airport canceled: Reuters witness," *Reuters*, 15 July 2016, <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-turkey-security-airport-flights/all-flights-from-istanbuls-ataturk-airport-canceled-reuters-witness-idUSKCN0ZV2K1?mod=related&channelName=worldNews> (accessed 15.12.2017).

back to 1959 and includes the Association Agreement in Ankara (1963) for the gradual establishment of a customs union (finally finished in 1995).

The accession negotiations began in 2005, but only after Turkey will agree to apply the additional protocol of the Association Agreement Ankara-Cyprus, eight negotiation chapters will be opened and there will be unblocked those chapters which were provisionally closed.⁸

The analysis of the coup attempt will explain the reasons behind the development from the areas (through the three models of decision making).

The rational actor model

This model explains the international events, in this case, the coup attempt in Turkey. First of all, the purpose is clearly established. As a result of the failed coup, in this case, Erdogan has increased his powers. That fact was made through the referenda from April 2017 when most of the Turks had chosen “yes”. An interesting fact is that the diaspora in Europe voted differently than in Turkey. They voted for Erdogan. Westerners were surprised (the referendum was won with the help from Occident). In the big cities like Ankara, Istanbul, Izmir he lost. In the countries from the Central and Eastern Europe the Turks voted against Erdogan. It also identifies the issues: what Turkey loses through the strict measures:

A. The interruption of closer collaboration with the US:

As the United States and Turkey enter the third decade following the end of the Cold War, they are enjoying a new cooperative era in their relationship and their partnership has been enhanced by overlapping perspectives on the unprecedented transformation sweeping the Middle East as well as in a number of other regional and functional areas.

The unfolding of a number of specific issues helped shape the future of the alliance. In the Middle East, the trajectory of the Arab Spring, driven by forces unleashed in the form of popular uprisings, is likely to exert pressure on both Washington and Ankara to coordinate their policies,

⁸ European Commission, “Turkey,” 2016, https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/countries/detailed-country-information/turkey_en (accessed 15.12.2017).

especially as they have similar perspectives on the root causes of the upheaval and the need to assist the regional transformation toward democracy and human rights. How the two countries deal with the Iranian nuclear program, regional tensions created by Iran's stance in the Syrian crisis, and Tehran's difficult relationship with its Arab neighbors will continue to be major components in the U.S.-Turkish relationship. The role Russia chooses to play in the various parts of the world in which Washington and Ankara have interests will also be a decision factor.⁹

The tensions surrounding the extradition of Gulen have damaged the important link with the US. Efforts made in years approaching US values through NATO and not only have come to a halt as a result of this event. Unfortunately, Turkey has returned more to the values of a religion-dominated state, instead of continuing Ataturk's ecumenical efforts. As a reaction, the USA cannot extradite Gulen.

B. The democratic Regression:

Erdogan supported the need to change the constitution of Turkey, an essential act in order to turn the country into a real regional power and not only under its leadership. The challenges for Ankara will be numerous in the future, both externally and internally, in a context where supporters of the president believe that by changing the constitution the state will be more stable, but its challengers talk about building an authoritarian system. According to parliamentary debates, it can be seen the idea to move from a parliamentary political system to a presidential one with full powers to the president elected by popular vote.

The president will be able to hold up to two mandates and will be able to appoint directly not only his deputies, but also the members of the government, members whom he can dismiss at any time without the

⁹ Aliriza Bulent, Aras Bulent, *U.S.-Turkish Relations. A review at the beginning of the third decade of the post-cold war era* (Ankara: Center for Strategic Research, 2012), http://sam.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/Aliriza_Aras_USTurkishRelations_Web.pdf (accessed 27.03.2018).

consent of the parliament. He will have the right to be a political partisan and may directly intervene in court by promulgating decrees, in particular.

The opinion of the Turks was demanded in April 2017, when they were called to the polls, this being the final step. The difference between this referendum and others in recent times in other countries is that Erdogan would not hold a referendum to lose, especially when his name is the synonym of power.¹⁰

The example of Turkey under Recep Tayyip Erdogan presents a potentially theory-busting specimen of a highly developed democracy going authoritarian. Despite recent market uncertainty, Turkey is significantly more affluent than Argentina was 40 years ago and its political trajectory carries global implications. The more Erdogan and his Justice and Development Party (AKP) pulled their economically vibrant country toward autocracy, the bleaker the outlook for democracy in similar or less favorable circumstances.¹¹

C. The loss of credibility:

Turkey loses its credibility on the scene of international relations. New state is being built in emergency, but supportive leaders believe that this does not affect democratic values by offering the example of France, a state that, like Turkey, was in alert to terrorist attacks, but has held presidential elections in April 2017. The difference is that tens of thousands of people have not been arrested in France and the mass media was not censured amid a state of emergency.¹² Another goal could be greater cohesion within the Turkish state.

Establishing alternatives:

- avoiding a new state attempt,

¹⁰ Răzvan Munteanu, "Noua Turcie: O construcție sub stare de urgență," *Adevărul*, 20 January 2017, http://adevarul.ro/international/in-lume/noua-turcie-construcție-starea-urgenta-1_588217815ab6550cb89ef4ea/index.html (accessed 15.02.2017).

¹¹ Jason Brownlee, "Why Turkey's authoritarian descent shakes up democratic theory," *The Washington Post*, 23 March 2016, https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/monkey-cage/wp/2016/03/23/why-turkeys-authoritarian-descent-shakes-up-democratic-theory/?utm_term=.84a818daa732 (accessed 27.03.2018).

¹² Răzvan Munteanu, *Op.cit.*

- consideration of cooperation with Russia and China,
- the continuation of the accession negotiations, but without elation.

Investigating alternatives:

- Erdogan has increased his powers and used successive arrests to avoid a similar event,

- showing dissatisfaction with slowing negotiations with the EU, Turkey is trying to get closer to similar structures, such as the Eurasian Economic Union,

- methodologically, neither the accession negotiations with the European Union will be abandoned.

Implementing the decision: Erdogan, as a result of replies from the EU for failing to implement some principles, has increasingly shown its interest in joining other structures, such as the Eurasian Economic Union. Russia has shown its approval for such a feasible move by the Turkish state. However, the idea of accession negotiations has not been abandoned. Actually, Erdogan enjoys more power within the state by modifying the legislative provisions.

Authoritarian leaders do not simply come and go and when they do go, they rarely go quietly. The test of an autocrat like the Turkish president, Recep Tayyip Erdogan, is not how he came to power, but how he treats critics, journalists, minorities, and whether his rule can go unchecked by constitutional limits.

In response to this, the European Union, which Turkey has been negotiating to become a full member of since 2005, is now reflecting on whether to cut and re-orient pre-accession funding: money that nations receive in order to help meet the legal requirements of joining the bloc.¹³

¹³ Steven Blockmans, "The EU is damaging its credibility over Turkey," *CNN*, 24 October 2017, <https://edition.cnn.com/2017/10/24/opinions/the-eu-and-turke-blockmans-opinion/index.html> (accessed 28.03.2018).

The cyber model:

In addition to the cost-benefit analysis that was presented in the previous model, it is demonstrated how people make decisions and learn in a rational way. Rationality is bounded by procedures to eliminate uncertainty. The procedures consist of the European acquis and the decision-making modalities. The referral was a procedure and subsequent actions will be carried out as such (more political power for the Turkish president). Decisions become simple as a result of reasoning. The information is filtered without calculating probabilities. The EU will have to reinvent itself as a result of Brexit in reasoning.

People and institution have a risk aversion (a new coup attempt). Decisions are taken at turning points (the choice between the EU and the Eurasian Economic Union) when time is short.

This is the theory of decision-making and it is well established in the EU, with bureaucracy playing an important role in decision-making, but also in Turkey through new political decisions. Decisions may be subjective, depending on the leader (in this case according to his political guidelines). These influences in reasoning can intervene involuntarily, without even the decision makers realizing. A leader oriented towards more political power will try to put into the agenda the creation of mechanisms to maintain it.

As shown above, the AKP constructed a sprawling surveillance-control-censorship regime during 2013-2016 mainly in response to the political fallout from Gezi protests and the corruption scandal as well as security-related incidents such as terrorist attacks. In the aftermath of the failed coup, the AKP's internet policy was similarly shaped by political anxieties which ultimately expanded and fortified the existing online control regime and in the immediate aftermath of the failed coup, the AKP government under the leadership of the president Erdogan declared a state of emergency and embarked on a massive purge of security officers, civil servants, educational and media workers it accused of being affiliated with the religious movement of Fethullah Gulen – the alleged mastermind of the coup. Given the severity of the potential threats the coup would have

caused had it succeeded, a national consensus emerged, uniting the AKP, opposition parties and different political actors and engendering the belief that the state of emergency would be used only to root out the coup planners. It soon became clear that Erdogan and his government would repress other perceived enemies, especially the Kurds, to consolidate their hegemony and stifle any remaining opposition, both online and offline.¹⁴

The cognitive approach:

Recep Tayyip Erdogan is the most controversial public figure in recent Turkish political history. His preponderance in political domain is remarkable even by Turkish standards. The power of Erdogan has effectively weakened most internal checks on his power, any attempt to explain Turkey's recent foreign policy outcomes will be seriously lacking without considering his leadership impact.¹⁵

Erdogan's increasingly erratic and miscalculated, but not irrational behavior. It is difficult to provide future projections for analysts and observers of Turkey, who use a conventional wisdom approach. The idea is that he has no specific strategy, but simply follows his inner instincts. He has become increasingly authoritarian in his leadership.¹⁶

The cognitive approach gives a new perspective. Psychological characteristics and elements are important in understanding politics. Regarding the coup attempt, Erdogan could have used mental shortcuts through historical analogies. He found the solution for avoiding the coup, the calling for people in the streets. Also, in this model there are used confirmatory distortions by finding only the information that are suitable for

¹⁴ Bilge Yesil, Efe Kerem Sözeri, Emad Khazraee, "Turkey's Internet Policy After the Coup Attempt: The Emergence of a Distributed Network of Online Suppression and Surveillance," *ScholarlyCommons* (2017): 12-13.

¹⁵ Aylin Ş. Gorenen, Meltem Ş. Ucal, "The personality and leadership style of Recep Tayyip Erdogan: implications for Turkish foreign policy," *Turkish Studies*, no. 3 (2011): 357.

¹⁶ Abdullah Bozkurt, "A psychological profile of Erdogan," *Haberler*, 25 March 2014, <https://en.haberler.com/a-psychological-profile-of-erdogan-404055/> (accessed 18.02.2018).

the main idea, excluding other opinions. Confirmatory deficiencies could make him easily see every challenge as a sign of intentionally.

Erdogan reacted furiously to the crackdown and claimed that those behind the investigations were trying to form a state within a state, in an apparent reference to the Hizmet movement.¹⁷

The coup attempt from Turkey had internal and external consequences. It influenced the next steps in accession negotiations. Through the models of decision making it was analyzed the event from 2016, seeing different perspectives.

Evaluation

Turkey has had a good start in the accession negotiations with the European Union. It was a rapprochement to Europe or a more interdependent trade between the Turks and the West, etc. Unfortunately, the current crises put Turkey in a difficult situation. Negotiating chapters are considered advanced or medium in terms of status, but could not be closed yet. Before the recent challenges that the European Union is facing, widening this geopolitical structure to the east and south was a priority, but for the moment this goal is postponed. The fact that the accession negotiations for the Turkish state are not a priority for the European Union is because of other problems that affected Europe in a way or another.

There is a strong connection between the elements from the negotiation chapters on the judiciary and fundamental rights and on justice, freedom and security and the analysis of the coup attempt from 2016. The actions after the coup attempt affected democracy and human rights.

Turkey also took in consideration a possible cooperation with Russia and China through the Eurasian Economic Union. However, it is still not possible to specify exactly which route to choose...

¹⁷ "Turkey's failed coup attempt: All you need to know," *Aljezeera*, 15 July 2017, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2016/12/turkey-failed-coup-attempt-161217032345594.html> (accessed 28.03.2018).

It remains to follow international reactions that can influence the situation in one way or another.

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The Law Applicable to Attribution of Conduct and Veil Piercing. From a Single Parent Company to Global Corporations

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Abstract. This article describes the conflict of law rules applicable to attribution of conduct and in particular to veil piercing in corporate groups of companies. The study is of a significant importance as it is related to complex activities of corporate groups, conducting business globally through the subsidiaries established in different jurisdictions worldwide. As there is no unified law which would apply only to groups, it is not feasible what are the laws applicable in case of attribution of the subsidiary's conduct to a parent company within a group. Therefore, choice of law rules for groups need to be separately studied and this article reflects on what is the direction provided by European Private International Law in this regard.

Keywords: attribution of conduct, veil piercing, corporation, groups, conflict of laws, choice of law, contracts, torts.

Introduction

To meet “expectations” of the modern commercial world, a company’s operation and activity cannot escape of being more complex, and at the same time it has to remain competitive globally. “To succeed globally today, it is no longer sufficient to have a national corporation and, say, a number of local subsidiaries internationally. The company itself needs to become truly global, seeing itself more as a network of activities”.¹ In the “network of activities” one of the essential usual integral elements of any company is physical participation of its organs and officers, servants (i.e. employees), affiliates, conduct of which is assimilated with a company. Within a complex and global “network of activities” one small misconduct of

¹ Peter Lorange, *Shipping Company Strategies: Global Management under Turbulent Conditions* (Oxford, Elsevier, 2005), 9.

one participant (for example, in a subsidiary) in one of the sections of cross-border business may lead to the negative consequences for the subsidiary, parent company and in some cases for the entire corporation.

Relations within the network of activities are governed by different disciplines and at the same time are or may be subject to different national, regional or international laws. Moreover, provided by legislation freedom of the internal structure of companies, freedom of establishment, flexibility motivated by tax consideration and other aspects are important for a company's activity. For mere convenience of a parent company or for particular economic advantages (tax, liability issues) network of activities may take globally complicated form today and in result "network of activities" became a subject to diversified "legal environment".

Specific working conditions, complicated regime of delegation of powers, particular regime of liability, also specific regulatory framework for some "section" of industries are some, but not all, characteristic of global corporations. Taking into account above mentioned, the actions of human beings within the network of activities are of a particular attention. The liability of a parent company in a group is also at stake. Liability of a company is a result of the ordinary "mistakes" of natural persons within that network. Whether the employees or company's organs are responsible and under what circumstances their fault is attributed to a (parent) company should be governed by a particular law(s).

If we assume that a natural person (not working for or on behalf of a company) is accused of a tort which was committed with cross-border element (parties and facts relate to different states), the question will be: is a person liable for the tort? Having this question in mind, the answer will lay in the substantive law of the country to which the rules of European Private International Law will lead.

In the case of a company or a group the situation is different. In general, if adult individuals, working for the company, may control the actions and be responsible for them, why does the company, an artificial structure, shall be liable instead of (or for) them? And what if we are talking

about the group of companies: if a subsidiary has its own legal personality under the law, why a parent company may be held liable for the actions of its subsidiaries established in other states? The more complex the global organizational structure is the more complex relationship in the company are and the more difficult it is to find out whose acts may be attributed to the company.

However, our main goal is not to investigate in details the national laws governing the attribution rules and veil piercing. We plan to find out what are the choice of law rules leading to national laws governing the rules of attribution and veil piercing.

We will start from the fundamental concept of a legal personality. Then attribution rules and corporate piercing will be analyzed. The analysis will be made not only with emphasize to different approaches in legal systems, but the place of these rules in relevant fields of law will be illustrated. The discussion of the existing theories on choice of law rules of Private International Law will bring us closer to the main point of this article. The next step in the article is a reference to existing provisions of European Private International Law. Taking into account the analysis made in connection with attribution rules and veil piercing, their place within the scope of the European choice of law rules will be shown. We will conclude with final concluding remarks. This article will include illustrations for both contractual and non-contractual relationships. The examples will be taken from both legal systems – civil and common law, where a particular attention will be paid to Dutch, English Law, and to the Law of the USA.

I. From a separate Legal Personality to attribution rules

Theoretical overview

We will refer to a “company” herein, meaning all legal entities with a legal personality, as “the principle of separate legal personality concerns usually not only an entity with limited liability, but also any natural person

or entity (usually incorporated) whether or not such a person or entity enjoys limited liability”.²

The initial historical origins of the concept of separate legal personality are not clear. The question on how to accept the existence of a legal entity as a distinct person, if it (a legal entity), as a matter of fact, can't act without natural persons, has been analyzed for a long time. Among other opinions, two distinct approaches are based on two theories: Fiction Theory and Realistic Theory. According to the Fiction Theory, only individuals (i.e. human beings) are capable of mind and will. The corporation is “persona ficta”, and because of the absence of “mens rea”, it cannot be liable for the tort committed by individuals. Probably the roots of ultra vires also come from this Theory: a company cannot be liable for the acts which are outside of its objects. The Realistic Theory, in contrast, accepts that a company is a part of a society as is an individual is. The Realistic Theory suggests that a company is responsible for the wrongful consequences of the intention, which is “formed” by a developing and incorporating will of the individuals. Thus, the Realistic Theory recognizes a real existence of a company as a structure consisting of a will of individuals, and via these individuals a company is capable to form its own intention. The latter view is closer to our today's reality. Evolution of social relations naturally leads us to suitable forms and environment for business relations, and with the progress of these relations more developed structure of relationship arises. The concept of a company as a legal person attracted interests of a number of scholars and there are various thoughts in this regard. One of the scholars, Frederick Hallis supported the idea that this is the main struggle: whether a company is an independent person or merely a collectivity of its members. And through realization of this struggle the understanding of the concept of legal personality may be achieved.³

² Karen Vandekerckhove, *Piercing the Corporate Veil* (UK, Kluwer Law International, 2007), 1.

³ Cheong-Ann Png, *Corporate liability: a study in principles of attribution* (UK, Kluwer Law International, 2001), 6. One of the first scholars who gave first interpretations on the Fiction

After a long historical struggle, the principle of “the veil of incorporation” was upheld in one of the significant court cases *Salomon v A. Salomon and Co. Ltd*⁴: a company was not an agent (or alter ego) of its founder, but a separate person distinct from its members; and the business belonged to the company and not to Mr Salomon, who was the founder. The Lords accepted that “if the form of the company was within the letter of the law they would not look behind it to the substance”.⁵ There are other fundamental court decisions in common law, demonstrating distinctive character of a legal person. For example, in the case *Macaura v Nothern Assurance Co. Ltd*⁶, a shareholder insured the assets of the company in his own name and then couldn’t claim according to the insurance policy because the assets doesn’t belong to him, but to the company. And the shareholder had no insurable interests in the property of the company. If we take as an example a group of companies, in the case *The Eurymedon, New Zealand Shipping Co Ltd v AM Satterthwaite*⁷ it was shown by the House of Lord that a holding company cannot take advantage of a contract between a subsidiary and a third party for the holding company’s benefit. All these and other numerous cases demonstrate an independent existence of a legal person. Before “legal personality” was legally granted in history, owners were not considered as separate from its business; they were bound by all consequences and liable for all risks resulting from business. As we see, the official practical effort to distinguish a legal person was made through court interpretation by House of Lords. Thus a doctrine of legal personality was formulated, which till present time is a basis for company law governing companies, including multinational companies.

Theory were Sinibald Fieschi (later Pope Innocent IV in 1243) and Frederich Carl von Savigny and Raymond Saleilles. The Realistic Theory was expounded by Otto von Gierke.

⁴ *Salomon v A. Salomon and Co. Ltd* [1897] AC 22, House of Lords.

⁵ Alan Dignam, *Hicks and Goo’s Cases and Materials on Company law* (UK, Oxford University Press, 2008), 96.

⁶ *Macaura v Nothern Assurance Co. Ltd* [1925] AC 619, House of Lords.

⁷ *The Eurymedon, New Zealand Shipping Co Ltd v AM Satterthwaite* [1975] AC 154.

Capacity

One of the consequences of the concept of the “veil of incorporation” is that a legal entity was almost identified, with some exceptions in rules, with a human being. So “social actors” – natural and legal persons – are both independent “addressees” of the law. An entity’s legal personality is separate and distinct from all corporate actors gravitating around it: shareholders, creditors, managers, workers, State. An artificial form of business organization lacks legal personality until its incorporation (“registration”, “publication of the Articles of Association” or other legal requirements, which may differ per jurisdiction). Once a company is established in accordance with a national law, it gets its capacity of a legal personality. Legal personality includes two types of capacity: legal capacity consists of capability to have own rights and duties, and capacity to act – of the ability to exercise own rights and duties.

Legal capacity: Having rights and obligation, a company owns corporate assets, it holds and active and passive relations: 1) active, for example, means to transact, to have contractual relations; 2) passive means possibility to be held liable. A company is an entity to which the legal effect of corporate actions is attributed (e.g. torts) etc. All these presume the existence of specific patrimonial structure of a legal person, autonomy of which entails: “a series of consequences concerning the particular legal status of the various corporate actors that gravitate around it. Such consequences give, in their whole, a substantial part of the current regulatory framework of a corporation, as still in force in the overwhelming majority of national systems”.⁸ Autonomy of the patrimonial structure makes a company liable for its obligations.

Capacity to act: As a company cannot personally exercise rights and duties, for capacity to act organizational structure is needed. This internal organization structure acts externally for and on behalf of the legal person in

⁸ José Engrácia Antunes, *Liability of corporate groups: autonomy and control in parent-subsidiary relationships in US, German and EU law: an international and comparative perspective* (NL, Kluwer Law and Taxation Publishers, 1994), 58-59.

its relations with third parties (external organs) and responsible internally for the formation of an inner will and strategy as a guide for its own activity (internal organs).⁹ “The capacity of action of the legal person is entrusted to its own organs”.¹⁰

One of the important aspects of the organizational structure is the definition and allocation of the powers of corporate organs. Another aspect important for the structure is principles that govern the functions of each organ, for example, fiduciary duties of managers.

Other actors: It is impossible to exercise its capacity, to reach its commercial goals without workers. That is why precondition of the normative attributions of legal personality (legal capacity and capacity to act) is the company’s organizational structure. Workers are practically significant in running every-day activity and are an important part of the organizational structure as well. Their role may become even more important especially in a complex corporate group when a decision-making process and control by management is diffused.

Their relations are formed through employment relations with an employer (and nomination by directors) rather than via incorporation of a company by the law and article of association by nomination of the founders; though the article of association is also an agreement of a special kind, nevertheless, “organs” and officers, authorized by law and article of association, are “primary” actors and their relations are of a different nature.

So if we start from the very beginning:

1) on the top of a classic model would be the general meeting of the shareholders: the sovereign corporate organ holding decision-making power on fundamental issues of corporate life, such as election and removal of directors, adoption or amendment of corporation articles,

⁹ *Ibid.*, 60.

¹⁰ Werner Flume, *Allgemeiner Teil des Bürgerlichen Recht (‘die juristische Person’)* (Berlin, Springer, 1983), 377.

and major corporate matter such as merger, sale assets, or dissolution;

2) the Board of directors (primary actors), the organ holding power to Manage the business and affairs of the corporation;

3) the board of auditors (sometimes supervisory board);

4) the workers, represented through various internal bodies.¹¹

All these actors have different “status” and “duties” in a company and depending on the “status” and “duties” acts of those included to that structure are counted as the acts of the company. Again these are the rules of attribution which determine this.

Lex societatis (nationality) of the company

It is important to note that “national law determined which organs have power to commit the company vis-à-vis third parties and defines the scope of their powers, whether directly by legislating or – as in the UK – indirectly by leaving it to be prescribed in the company’s status.¹² In principle, these and other matters below are supposed to be scrutinized first of all when dealing with any company. The matters are not harmonized and each state may have its particular conflict of law rules, which determine what is a subject of a national law in respect of formation and operation of a company.

For example, the Conflicts of Laws (corporations) Act of the Netherlands¹³ provides that the law governing a corporation (*lex societatis*) shall extend, in addition to its establishment, in particular, among other, to the following subject matter:

- the possession of legal personality or a power to be a subject of rights and obligations, to perform legal acts, to act at law;
- the representative authority of constituent bodies and officers of the corporation;

¹¹ Antunes, *Op. cit.*, 62

¹² Vanessa Edwards, *EC Company Law* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1999), 34.

¹³ Conflict of laws (Corporations) Act (Netherlands), Article 3.

- the liability of directors, supervisory board members and other officers in that capacity as regards the corporation, the question who, jointly with corporation, is liable for any acts by which the corporation is bound pursuant to authority such as that of incorporator, partner, shareholder, member, director etc.

Lex societatis of a company is determined in accordance with chosen by the state theory: the incorporation or the real seat (place of central management and control). So each national law in the EU provides information on the theory chosen by the state.¹⁴ Traditionally, “theory of incorporation is especially popular in countries with long-standing commercial maritime tradition where an open attitude to trade is expected to be met with reciprocity, as opposed to the more mercantilist attitude adopted in other countries” (France, for example).¹⁵

In the Netherlands, where the theory of incorporation is applied, the national company law of the Netherlands will regulate the matters of formation and operation of the company (see above). Once the seized court determines the national law of the company, the next step is to find out how in accordance with that law the company must be represented and which transactions made by its organs or officers (as defined in Articles of Association) are binding for the company (it should be mentioned that the national legislation of the MS must be in line with Directive 68/151, First Council Directive). Due to provisions of the First Directive on Company Law, Article 9¹⁶, a transaction which is beyond the intended objects and powers is valid vis-à-vis third parties. If there are any limitations of the powers in the statute or in the decision of competent organs such limitations are ineffective as against third parties. Though the transaction may not be invalid due to the lack of capacity, but it may be invalid for the reasons of

¹⁴ Stefan Grundmann, *European Company Law* (Intersentia, Antwerpen-Oxford, 2007), 119.

¹⁵ Edwards, *Op. cit.*, 334.

¹⁶ First Directive 68/151/EEC of 9 March 1968 on co-ordination of safeguards which, for the protection of the interests of members and others, are required by member States of companies within the meaning of the second paragraph of Article 58 of the Treaty, with a view to making such safeguards equivalent throughout the Community.

directors' conflicts of interest¹⁷, for example, or if third parties acted in bad faith or had constructive knowledge on misrepresentation.

Groups in the commercial world

Nowadays, new forms of business organization or “liberalization”¹⁸ of old forms develop, and it is explained by various factors, including social, economic, technological, legal etc. Moreover, as we mentioned above, a single independent corporation is not sufficient today for the commercial dealing. Some groups will likely have subsidiaries all over the world. A group of companies is more a rule than an exception today. When a company creates secondary establishment it usually chooses two main types of secondary establishment: branches or subsidiaries. A branch is a structural part of a company, and direct instructions and unitary management are under the law of the home country (lex societatis). A subsidiary is subject to the law of the host state, and the instructions can be difficult under this law, as is the pursuit of a common interest (rather than the interest of the subsidiary)”. A parent company normally is not liable for the debts of a subsidiary, because a subsidiary is an independent legal person, “and this can be advantage (or a disadvantage) in current business operations but also in structural changes, including with respect to tax law”.¹⁹

By way of secondary establishment companies choose to run business worldwide. Today multinational corporate groups operate through a number of subsidiaries which are formed (established) under the laws of many states and are subject to their company law (in particular matters of management, representation, liability etc.). In principles, as it is described in respect of subsidiaries, a parent company is no more liable for the unlawful behavior of its subsidiary. So the same concepts of a legal personality and its

¹⁷ Coöperatieve Rabobank “Vecht en Plassengebied” BA v Erik Aarnoud Minderhoud, C-104/96 [1997] ECR I-7211.

¹⁸ A. McCahery, Levinus Timmerman, Erik P. M. Vermeulen, *Private company law reform: International and European perspectives* (The Hague: T.M.C. Asser Press, 2010), 18-19.

¹⁹ Grundmann, *Op. cit.*, 520

principles are thought to be applied to relation between a parent company and subsidiary, where subsidiary remains to be applicable to convenient or beneficial for it jurisdiction. A parent company is assumed to be protected from liability. For this reason many authors, as was already mentioned above in the section “From a separate Legal Personality to Attribution rules”, are of the opinion that a usual approach of a regulatory framework provided for by traditional corporate law, concerning issues of formation, organization, financing, management, liability, dissolution are not suitable for multinational companies today.²⁰

The fact that in a group subsidiaries are treated as separate is not surprising.

If we approach a structure as a business unit than as legal person recognized by law, the relations within the expanding structure is of a particular attention nowadays. In the part about capacity we demonstrated a classic model of a single-company structure. That single-company structure may expand externally (mergers etc.). In that case the structure experiences no significant modification. All commercial activities are interests and goals of one particular business unit and the patrimonial structure is governed by these interests and goals. But when a company expands externally to break limitation which may be on its way (organizational, financial, legal) for the growth, significant modification in the patrimonial and organizational structure take place. In spite of the fact that each unit (subsidiary) in a group is independent, the business carried out by each unit is relevant for the whole group, because “the profitability of any constituent corporation (subsidiary) is largely irrelevant, except as it contributes to the overall effort”.²¹ At the same time to achieve best business with joint efforts results, allocation of resources is made among different divisions worldwide: financial, technological, labor, managerial division. Each of this division, being an independent entity, is managed in

²⁰ Antunes, *Op. cit.*, 57.

²¹ Jonathan Landers, *A Unified approach to Parent, Subsidiary, and Affiliate Questions in Bankruptcy* (42 University of Chicago Law Review, 1975), 591.

accordance with the interest of the whole group. For this reason unified management is another distinctive character of a group.²²

What if a “legal personality” is disregarded? Exceptions to “veil” and individual liability of corporate actors

Possession of a legal personality doesn't mean that there are only advantages for the founders, organs, officers, workers of a company, which may always “shelter” behind the “veil”. There are also exceptions when “the veil” is lifted and founders or other individual are liable not a company, or a parent company may be responsible for the activities of their nominee directors in their subsidiaries.

In general, a court cannot disregard an independent legal personality of a company, but the “veil” can be lifted when it is provided by law or judicial interpretation, or there can be requirements of public policy. For example, in cases of judicial interpretation, “courts have lifted the veil of incorporation to recognize the substance of practical realities of a situation rather than a form”.²³ For example, it is notable in cases with groups, where a shareholder – a parent company is held liable personally for the acts of its subsidiary, and the latter is deemed to be alter ego of the former. In Salomon case it was decided that a company is not an agent of a founder. But in the fundamental court case *Smith, Stone & Knight v Birmingham*²⁴, it was decided that six requirements must be established before the Salomon principle could be disregarded to support the finding that a subsidiary carried on a business as an agent for its parent company, and the parent company, therefore, may be held liable:

- The profit of the subsidiary must be treated as the profits of the parent company,
- The persons conducting the business must be appointed by the parent company,

²² Antunes, *Op. cit.*, 70.

²³ Dignam, *Op. cit.*, 102.

²⁴ *Smith Stone & Knight Ltd v Birmingham Corporation 1939*4 All ER 116.

- The parent company must govern the venture and decide what should be done and what capital should be embarked on it,
- The profits of the business must be made by the parent company's skill and direction,
- The parent company must be in effective and constant control.²⁵

We will consider rules with “piercing” in groups separately in the next sections.

Also, individual liability of corporate actors may be prescribed by law, for example: according to the specific legal provisions the directors may be held personally liable vis-a-vis a company or third parties. Liability, for instance, may arise when a company goes bankrupt and director's mismanagement was an important cause of the bankruptcy.²⁶

Turning to the employees not necessary being “organs” or officers authorized by an article of association, usually, for example, a company may be vicariously liable (one of the attribution rules) for the negligence of an employee.

A statutory example could be legal provisions of the Companies Act 1985 (the UK), where in Section 349 (4)²⁷ individual liability of officers is addressed. The directors and other employees may be personally liable to a holder of any bill of exchange, promissory note that they have signed on behalf of the corporation when its name was not properly mentioned on the instrument, what was upheld in *John Wilkes (Footwear) Ltd v Lee International (Footwear) Ltd*.²⁸

²⁵ Francis Rose, *Company Law* (Sweet&Maxwell, Thomson Reuters, 2015), 42.

²⁶ Julian Maitland-Walker, *Guide to European Company Laws* (London Sweet&Maxwell, 2008), 673.

²⁷ http://www.opsi.gov.uk/RevisedStatutes/Acts/ukpga/1985/cukpga_19850006_en_16#ID_AXTLCE (accessed 6 May 2019).

²⁸ *John Wilkes (Footwear) Ltd v Lee International (Footwear) Ltd*.²⁸ [1985] B.C.L.C. 444.

II. General principles of corporate liability

Development of Attribution rules

While the corporation is legally separate and distinct from its members, it is ultimately an artificial creation and it acts through its servants or agents.²⁹ All actors in the corporation participate in the business of the company. Each of the actors has its specific status in the system of relations within the company. So the status of corporate actors differs and also different types of relations are created within the company to carry on the business. The result of this is a complicated organizational structure and due to various factors within this structure, there are different approaches to corporate liability: when a corporation may be said to incur liability for the acts of its directors or other employees. If we take both civil and common law systems, there are in general three approaches to the liability: vicarious liability, agency and the directing mind theory. We will address these approaches in order to investigate in the next parts the basic structure of relations with and between corporate actors, and, in the end of this section of the article, to determine the place of attribution rules and veil piercing in the system of substantive laws.

As an example we will take development of common law traditions where the following principles were distinguished historically step by step:³⁰

A) Traditional directing mind theory:

a) The theory first was traced to the judgment of Viscount Haldane L.C. in *Lennard's Carrying Co. Ltd. v Asiatic Petroleum Co. Ltd*³¹:

"A corporation is an abstraction. It has no mind of its own any more than it has a body of its own; its active and directing mind must consequently be sought in the person of somebody who for some purposes may be called an agent, but who is really the directing mind and will of the

²⁹ *Ferguson v Wilson* [1866] L.R. 2 Ch. 77, 89.

³⁰ Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 14.

³¹ *Lennard's Carrying Co Ltd v Asiatic Petroleum Co Ltd* [1915] AC 705.

corporation, the very ego and center of the personality of the corporation.”³²

In that case, Mr Lennard, who was responsible for the management of the vessel on the shipowner’s behalf, was found to be the directing mind and will of the shipowner-appellant. The shipowner’s vessel was unseaworthy. Under section 502 of the English Merchant Shipping Act 1894, a ship-owner was not liable to make goods loss or damage to the cargo that occurred without actual fault or privity. It was held that the true construction of the legislation must mean that the actual fault or privity is that of an individual who is not merely a servant or agent of the appellant. It should be someone for whom the appellant is liable on the ground that his action is regarded as its very own – its directing mind and will.

Presumption on applicable law is that the *law of the subject matter* is the law governing attribution rules of this kind.

b) The directing mind theory was then approved by the House of Lords in *Tesco Supermarkets Ltd. V Nattrass*.³³ It was stated that this is a matter of law to be found whether the individual is alter ego of the company as opposed to the servant and agents. We presume that for servant and agents not the construction of the substantive law, but first of all existence of relations between corporation and servants or agents is of importance.

The decision of *Tesco* was essential in respect of the jurisprudence on personal liability of corporations. In that case, it was also distinguished between the theory of directing mind (under *Lennard* case) from liability of a company under employer-employee (or servant) and principal-agent relationships. The directing mind theory does not extend beyond those of whom that are empowered under its constitution to exercise its powers.

In that case, again according to directing mind theory liability is found in an appropriate national Act under which the main obligation – non

³² Viscount Haldane L.C. in *Lennard’s Carrying Co. Ltd. v Asiatic Petroleum Co. Ltd* [1915] AC 705.

³³ *Tesco Supermarkets Ltd. v Nattrass* [1972] AC 153.

contractual – are in breach.³⁴ So first of all we refer to the substantive law of the subject-matter, then according to the context of legislation we find the class of individuals who are under the obligation to exercise due diligence and whether this class is the mind and will of the company. If it is not, the company does not incur personal liability, if the class is that which is mind and will of the company – personal liability of a company is involved.

However, the Tesco case didn't provide a sufficient ground for analyzing corporate personal liability.

B) Development of principles of attribution.

In common law system the directing mind theory was applied for a long time. However, the decision of *El Ajou v. Dollar Land Holdings Plc. & Another*³⁵ and *Supply of Ready Mixed Concrete, Re*³⁶ led to expansions from traditional directing mind theory:

- it was recognized that a corporation is a legal abstraction and there is a need to attribute to them the conduct or state of knowledge of their servants and agents as well, but not in all cases of course
- it was also accepted that though it is useful to look to the constitutional structure of a corporation to identify the individuals who are in positions of management and control (*Lennard's* and *Tesco*), it is not always decisive. It is essential to look to the specific individuals who exercises management and control in relation to the alleged act or omission
- the identification of the individuals who represent the corporation's directing mind is a question of law. It depends on the construction of the substantive law in issue.
- in determining the alter ego of the company it is important to take into account the relative position of the individuals in the

³⁴ Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 17.

³⁵ *El Ajou v. Dollar Land Holdings Plc. & Another* [1994]2 All ER 685.

³⁶ *Supply of Ready Mixed Concrete, Re* [1995]1All ER 135.

organizational structure, other relevant facts and the circumstances of the case.³⁷

C) Further development of attribution rules.

In the case mentioned in the latter example *Supply of Ready Mixed Concrete, Re*, Lord Hoffmann would stress:

So the company's primary rules of attribution which are generally found in its constitution, the articles of association, are not enough to enable a company to go out into the world and do the business. Not every act on behalf of the company could be expected to be the subject of a resolution of the board or unanimous decisions of the shareholders. The company therefore builds upon the primary rules of attribution by using general rules of attribution which are equally available to natural persons, namely, the principles of agency. "It will appoint servants and agents whose acts, by a combination of the general agency principles and the company's primary rules of attribution, count as the acts of the company. And having done so, it will also make itself subject to the general rules by which liability for the acts of others can be attributed to natural persons, such as estoppel or ostensible authority in contract and vicarious liability in tort".³⁸

The next, one of the important cases in respect of formation of the attribution rules in common law history is the *Meridian* case.³⁹ The attribution rules were extended even more this time: Where the person is a corporation, knowledge of the servant or agent who has the authority to make the transaction on its behalf shall count as its knowledge.⁴⁰ In the end the following attribution rules were formulated as an approach to the corporate liability⁴¹:

- *Primary rules* – these rules actually relates to the class of individuals whose actions according to the traditional directing mind theory would be attributed to the company: so those are principles

³⁷ Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 21-22.

³⁸ Alan Dignam, *Op. cit.*, 134.

³⁹ *Meridian Global Funds management Asia Ltd v Securities Commission* [1995] 3 All ER91 8.

⁴⁰ Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 23.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, 24.

under the companies legislation and its jurisprudence that provide for the corporation to act through its board of directors and shareholders in general meetings (“organs”) (Lennard’s and Tesco). The articles of association and the memorandum will define the construction of the division of power between the organs. Corporation would be personal liable under these rules.

- *Primary rules* as it was stated in the case Supply of Ready Mixed Concrete, Re, Lord Hoffmann should be supplemented by the *general rules*, because it is unrealistic that the corporation’s general meeting of shareholders and board of directors will confirm every act of the corporation. General rules include application of the agency principles to the activities of individuals that are authorized by the corporation. According to agency law Principal would be personally liable. This is different in case of tortious liability. The general rules also take into account the doctrine of vicarious liability: the corporation is responsible for torts committed by their servants within the course of their employment, and the liability in this case is not personal, but vicarious.

- *Secondary rules* concern the cases where corporation’s personal liability is defined not in accordance with actual authority (primary rules) and agency (general rules), but is found when depending on the construction of legislation or a matter under the common law conduct or knowledge of the individual is attributed to the company.

The methods in which personal corporate liability may be determined according to the secondary rules vary in the court cases:

- contextual approach: to identify an individual who is directing mind is not necessary in case when attribution rules involves construction of legislation. It is based on scrutinizing the rationale of legislation, taking into account the policy and objectives of the legislation.

- functional approach: directing mind theory is still relevant in common law, where the criterion for attribution of conduct and

knowledge of the servant and agents depends more on the operational role of the servant or agent in relation to the alleged infringement or wrongdoing and the circumstances in issue (functional approach).

D) All three rules (primary, general and secondary) are interdependent and each of the rules is applied in the appropriate legal relations: contractual or non-contractual:

1) Contractual obligations mainly via:

- primary rules,
- general rules (agency),

2) Non-contractual obligations mainly via:

- general rules (vicarious),
- secondary rules.

In the next two parts we will scrutinize the principles which constitute the basis for attribution rules described above, and the basic structure of relations with and between corporate actors taking into account primary rules, general and secondary rules.

Principles of attribution rules in contractual obligations of the corporation

A) Notion on Agency. The agency relationship does not present between the corporation and its members or between its members inter se.⁴² But, as we will see, between the corporation and servants and agents, there exists a relationship that is akin to agency.⁴³ Despite this, it is fairly stated by some authors that the Agency Law lacks its independent scientific approach nowadays. As a separate discipline in law schools the Agency Law doesn't exist, but goes through the main areas of law: company law, contract law, tort law. However it was fair to stress the following: Clearly, agency is central to business dealings. No owner of a business can do

⁴² Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 39.

⁴³ Paul Davies, *Gower's and Davies's Principles of Modern Company law* (Sweet&Maxwell, 2003), 179, 199-200.

everything himself; he must delegate some things to agents, and this is true not only of large corporations but of sole proprietorships that have employees who work for the owner. In partnerships, the partners act as each other's agents. And in corporations, the shareholders are completely unable to act on their own behalf; they delegate authority to a board of directors, who in turn delegate authority to the officers of the corporation. Indeed, agency is one of the main themes of corporate law... In torts, it enters via vicarious liability; in contracts, via the validity of contracts made by agents.⁴⁴

So who is an agent? The simplest traditional approach: The agent is a person who acts on behalf of the principal. Modern writers accept the approach which provides a definition to the "agent" from the point of view of a power-liability relation: Powell, for example, said that an agent was a person who (inter alia) "has power to affect the legal relations of his principal with a third party".⁴⁵ In traditional approach the agent is instructed by principal. The instructions are called the agent's authority. Even in the absence of authority, there are conditions under which the agent may have power to bind the principal. And according to some authors it is not correct to identify these two concepts, authority and power.⁴⁶ The distinction has been stated by Professor Corbin.⁴⁷ Authority differs from Power: Authority is a fact; Power is a legal relation. Authority is conduct of the principal, including either oral or written communication to the agent; Power is neither conduct nor a document. Authority may create Power, but not always; Power may be created by Authority, but may also be created by other operative facts.

There are strong arguments that "agents" are relevant in the law of contract. On the other hand, a category of "servants" is more relevant in torts. "Agency is really a relationship that has meaning and importance in

⁴⁴ Eric Rasmusen, *Agency Law and Contract formation* (2001), 1.

⁴⁵ G. H. L. Fridman, *Law of Agency* (7th edition, Butterworths, 1996), 20.

⁴⁶ Raphael Powell, *The Law of Agency* (London: SIR ISAAC Pitman & Sons Ltd, 1961), 6.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, 36.

the fields of contract”.⁴⁸ But agents can make principals liable for torts committed incidentally in the course of its functions related to making of contracts. “Servants” bind principals committed incidentally to the performance of other tasks. So “agents” are to perform a specific function presumably instructed by principals, where “servants” perform in normal course of their employment.

In other words, the term “agent” should be restricted to one who has the Power of affecting the legal position of his principal by the making of contracts or the disposition of property: but who may incidentally, affect the legal position of his principal in other ways. Only agents may affect the principal in this way, creating legal relations between their principal and third parties. “Servants” and also “independent contractors” by virtue of their employment in such capacities cannot affect the principal like this.⁴⁹

In most cases, the agent’s power may arise from actual, apparent authority. An agent who has been expressly authorized to act can bind the company with respect to matters within his express, implied or usual authority. The authority is express when, for example, a board of directors passes a resolution which authorizes two of their number to sign cheques.⁵⁰ It may be implied from the nature of the business which the agent is employed to transact. As it was demonstrated in the Freeman⁵¹ case the board of directors appointed one of their number to be managing director, where the board supposed to have actual expressed (by the virtue of law and articles of association) authority, and the managing director – implied in this case; so implied authority depends for its very existence on the existence of an express authority, it is an extension of express authority, and, therefore, depends of the wishes manifested by a principal (company acting through the board) to his agent.

⁴⁸ Fridman, *Op. cit.*, 36

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, 303.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*, 63.

⁵¹ *Freeman and Lockyer v Buckhurst Park Properties (Mangal) Ltd* [1964] 2 QB 480 at 488, [1964] 1 All ER 630 at 635.

An “agent” with no authority at all will not bind the company unless the company later ratifies his acts, which it will do if the company wants to enforce the contract.⁵² When an agent has no authority (he exceeds his authority or has not been given at all) and whose acts were not ratified may bind the company if he acts within his apparent or ostensible authority. Even though there is no authority in fact to act, ostensible or apparent authority may create the relationship between the corporation and the third party (not principal-agent relationship). It is normally applied to the situation when the agent in fact has no authority, but appears to the third party to have authority as a result of a representation by the principal to that third party. So, apparent authority is created by representation from the principal (corporation) to the third party that the relevant individual is authorized to enter into an arrangement of this order on its behalf. The third party relied on the representation and this representation is an estoppel preventing a corporation from denying its obligation under the agreement.⁵³

Another type of agency is agency by operation of law. There is no consent of the principal in this case. The law itself “presumes” what the principal would have agreed to the agent’s doing, if the principal had been free to give instructions to the agent. By operation of law may act a corporate official exercising corporate functions specified in company law of the place of incorporation. Another example, as mentioned above by the operation of law the agency of necessity for the master of the ship is established, because it must be impossible for the master to be able to communicate with the owners of the ship or the cargo and ask for instructions⁵⁴ (though this seems to limit the operation of this form of agency in the light of modern communications, although it may be relevant where there are numerous cargo owners). Also a further essential feature is that the master must act bona fide and for the benefit of the interested parties.

⁵² Rose, *Op. cit.*, 20.

⁵³ Freeman and Lockyer v Buckhurst Park Properties (Mangal) Ltd [1964], 644.

⁵⁴ The Australia [1859] 13 Moo PCC 132.

Whatever type of agency we would consider, each model of relations within principal-agent-third party always has external and internal side. Obviously internal side concerns principal-agent relations, and external principal-third party and agent-third party. There is no need in references to conclude that authority of agents, if there is one, is found normally in internal relations. A power to bind the principal may be found in internal and external relations. Thus based upon the most important principles of Agency Law underlined above, we will see below how this principles work in attribution rule, namely primary and general. Also we will make some preliminary, but not final presumptions on the applicable law to the given relations.

B) Contractual Obligations. Primary rules. As it was mentioned above, traditional approach presumes consensual agency. So from the very beginning consent was the basic rule of Agency relations, and this is not surprising, because to act on behalf of principal the consent of the latter is something natural. As we could understand from the previous part “A” there can be exceptions. In the light of complex relations within the corporation, the agency principles even become more complicated between corporate actors, and the principal and corporate actors. One of the concepts, which still have a range of open questions, is “corporate agency”, and who are corporate agents who transact on behalf of the company and bind it.

In the Netherlands the division is made between *legal and consensual representation*. Legal representation doesn't depend on the consent of the principal. In the Netherlands representation of companies by its bodies and officers (also called corporate agency) is a legal representation, because authority is attached by operation of law. In the UK, it is the memorandum and the article of association which determines the power of organ: “national law determines which organs have power to commit the company vis-à-vis third parties and defines the scope of their powers, whether directly by legislating or – as in the UK – indirectly by

leaving it to be prescribed in the company's status."⁵⁵ This approach is closer to consensual agency. However, both approaches will fall into the category of corporate agency for the purposes of our research. It is also stressed by some authors that these two concepts may overlap. While in continental system, we are talking about legal representation (by operation of law), it is also may be referred to as corporate agency. Corporate agency is like an intermediate between legal representation and consensual agency.⁵⁶

Thus a contract may be made by a company itself,⁵⁷ i.e. by its organs (or as it is called in common law instead of "organs" – by shareholders in the general meeting and the board of directors). The division of powers is defined in the articles of association or by national company law. Primary attribution rules concern corporate agents, but only those who are acting "by virtue of an authority conferred by law or by the constitutive documents" of the corporation⁵⁸:

- managing directors of joint stock companies ("public" companies): ...directeur, bestuurder or lid van der raad van bestuur (Netherlands NV); ... (managing) director (U.K. plc);
- managing directors of limited companies ("private" companies): ... directeur, bestuurder or lid van der raad van bestuur (Netherlands BV); ... (managing) director (U.K. Ltd).

But the law may also specify that an individual managing director or he or she in cooperation with others should represent a company as management if it is provided by the article of association.⁵⁹ In this case, the latter is also related to corporate agency (not to rules of consensual agency).

A contract made by the company itself (through one of its organs) will obviously bind it.⁶⁰ But the power to bind is determined according to the

⁵⁵ Edwards, *Op. cit.*, 34.

⁵⁶ H. L. E. Verhagen, *Agency in Private International Law: The Hague Convention on the Law applicable to Agency* (Martinus Nuhoff Publishers, 1995), 8.

⁵⁷ Rose, *Op. cit.*, 50.

⁵⁸ Verhagen, *Op. cit.*, 172.

⁵⁹ Art. 2:240 Netherlands CC.

⁶⁰ Rose, *Op. cit.*, 50.

provisions of company law, not agency law (consensual). Regarding applicable law to the power to bind the company, the reference is made to the articles of association of the company and to the national company law as described earlier. As it was mentioned above, an example can be the Conflicts of Laws (corporations) Act of the Netherlands⁶¹, which provides the scope of issues the law governing a corporation (*lex societatis*) shall extend to.

The principles of primary attribution rules apply to impute the decisions of the board and members in general meetings to the corporation. As these decisions are made by the company itself, thus by its organs acting under authority, which is deemed to be “actual”⁶² or “real”.

Again whereas a board of directors as an “organ” has actual authority, their authority refers to relationship between the corporate principal and “organs”, and these are considered as the internal relations. At the same time the extent of authority may be ascertained by construing the nature of the arrangement entered into, the course of dealings between the corporation and the third party as well as the customs of the specific trade.⁶³ But the power of the agent to bind may be ascertained only according to the legal provisions and constitutive documents which constitute basis for principal–agent relations (company-organs).

The board of directors, as whole, is generally delegated all powers of management and it may sub-delegate any these powers to individual directors or other servants or agents. If sub-delegation does not conform to the requirements of company law (for example, as specified in Article 2:240 Netherlands CC), we will likely to deal with ordinary rules of consensual agency and apparent authority of corporate actors, not corporate agency. Now we will consider cases in which principles of consensual agency rather than corporate agency applies to corporate actors.

⁶¹ Conflict of laws (Corporations) Act (Netherlands), Article 3.

⁶² Edward Elgar Cheltenham, *EU Private International Law* (Peter Stone, UK, 2006), 299.

⁶³ Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 42.

C) Contractual Obligations. General agency rules. No doubts that “organs” are primary actors, actual authority of which is based on the provisions of company law and its articles of association. What about apparent authority and actual authority which doesn’t fall into category of corporate agency (legal representation)?

- First of all, before considering other officials, it is necessary to scrutinize the case when “organs” exceed their authority. Only when an official (“organ” or authorized individual managing director) acts “by virtue of an authority conferred by law or by the constitutive documents”, this actual authority falls within the scope of corporate agency. If a corporate official acts outside his authority conferred by law or by the constitutive documents of the company the authority is already “apparent”, not “actual” anymore, because an official merely purports or appears to act pursuant to authority conferred by law or by the corporation’s constitution.⁶⁴ Transacting on behalf of the company, an agent here with apparent authority doesn’t have legal instructions from its principal (company), but nevertheless creates legal contractual relations between a company and third party. Creating this external relations, an agent’s apparent authority and powers to bind a company will normally found not in company law or articles of association, but presumably in the law which governs this external relation created by an unauthorized agent (company-third party).

- We already mentioned in the previous part here above that authority of corporate officials may be connected with their corporate functions by operation of law (even though they are not “organs” of the company).⁶⁵ Art. 2:240 CC of the Netherlands specifies conditions under which corporate officials may represent the company apart from “organs”. If this is not specified by law, corporate officials are deemed to have apparent authority contracting on behalf of the company. Our aim here to demonstrate the way the apparent authority is established in the absence of corporate authority vested by the operation of law to corporate officials, but

⁶⁴ Verhagen, *Op. cit.*, 174.

⁶⁵ Art. 2:240 Netherlands CC.

vested only by articles of association. For example, the law doesn't provide that the representation authority can be vested on one of the board members. But nevertheless, the article association grants such authority to one of them. The contract concluded by one of the members is binding for the company. The power to bind will be determined according to the law governing corporate structure, even though the authority is only apparent.⁶⁶

- It is possible that agents are authorized by the constitutive documents, but are not included to the primary actors with actual authority described above. "With reference to Netherlands law Van der Grinten observes that these authorizations in practice always concern functionaries employed by legal entities. These functionaries are authorized where the constitutive documents recognize corporate positions, such as ... "deputy-directors" and "procuration-holders"... (in the case of public and private companies)".⁶⁷ According to different approaches these officers are linked to "consensual" agency or to a totally distinct category (neither corporate nor consensual). It is presumed that the extent of their authority is not the subject of company law, so it is suggested that the "functionaries" scope of authorities is regulated by the rules of ordinary powers of attorney, thus by consensual agency.⁶⁸ And whether a company is bound by their acts is primarily a question of agency law, depending not upon actual authority, but upon apparent authority, or external powers of representation (principal-third party).

- In addition to corporate authority, corporate officials may be granted with special powers of attorney to execute particular acts. The officer, who does not act "by virtue of an authority conferred by law or by the constitutive documents", acts as an ordinary agent who has been authorized by the principal. This authority will fall into the category of consensual agency. Here again external relations, i.e. principal-third party, play a primary role in order to define the extent of the powers granted to

⁶⁶ Verhagen, *Op. cit.*, 178.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*, 173.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

the official by the power of attorney. This is deemed to be appropriate, because a third party should not be bound by the law agreed between corporation and an agent, thus within their internal relations. However, the question of whether those who granted the power of attorney has the authority to do so, should be found in the internal relation, thus is an issue of corporate agency.⁶⁹

- The law governing the corporate structure, thus company law, also applies to power of attorney granted by shareholders. In the Netherlands it has discussed by Vlas: “it would certainly be very impracticable when the decision-making in the general meeting of shareholders could be affected by a system of law not known to the company and applicable only in the relationship between the shareholder and his representative”.⁷⁰

This was confirmed in the case Natco⁷¹: this question is so closely connected with the “validity of the decision-making in the general meeting of shareholders” that should be governed by the law of the company’s structure (i.e. the law of the place of incorporation). And the latter is irrespective where the power of attorney is exercised.

Principles of attribution rules in non-contractual obligation of the corporation

A) General rules (vicarious liability). When there are no instructions to agents and servants, the liability, nevertheless, may be attributed to the company. Whereas the “organic” theory (primary rules) is based on the notion that the actions and will of the company’s agents constitute those of the company and a company is personally liable, in case of vicarious liability fault has not to be attributed to the company; the legislation may just

⁶⁹ Ibid., 174.

⁷⁰ Ibid., 180.

⁷¹ Natco, HR 20 April 1990 NJ 1991, 560.

provide that the company may be liable for the actions of its agents or employees (servants). Seniority of an employee is irrelevant in this case.⁷²

- In general, a servant may commit a tort without an authority assigned. But the company will be vicariously liable for a servant's tort if he has acted within the scope of his employment and the act is incidental to his course of employment.⁷³ So there is no need in considering of authority and power of the servant. Whether a servant was acting within the scope of the employment agreement will be subject of relations between employer and employee, but the corporate liability is determined by the law applicable to non-contractual, i.e. tortuous obligations.

- Actions of agents, on the other hand, are confined to what the agent does within the scope of his authority. The liability of a principal for the torts of his agent is exactly the same as his liability in respect of the contracts made by his agent.⁷⁴ The authority again may be express or implied, it may be apparent or acquired by ratification if the act was not authorized in advance by the principal. If an agent commits a tort without due authority, this presumably falls under the category of "negoriorum gestio", what will be discussed in the last Chapter.

B) Non-contractual obligations. Secondary rules. A company may be liable in tort personally if the acts of a natural person (servant or agent) constitute an act of the company itself even though there are no particular instructions, but there is functional responsibilities and legislative context.

Whereas in agency the knowledge of agent in principle is imputed to his principal where he has been authorized to enter into agreement on its behalf and the relevant knowledge refers to anything in relation to the performance of the agreement or its terms. There is no such authorization in fact in accordance with secondary rules: the object of secondary rules is to provide the means through which the conduct or state of knowledge of the relevant servants or agents of a corporation may be attributed to it for

⁷² Julie Cassidy, *Concise Corporations Law* (The Federation Press, Sydney, 2006), 43.

⁷³ Rose, *Op. cit.*, 56.

⁷⁴ Fridman, *Op. cit.*, 305.

the purpose of establishing personal liability and obligations. These secondary rules are relevant in relation to allegation of corporate infringement or wrongdoing where it is necessary to demonstrate actual fault or reprehensible knowledge.⁷⁵ As we already mentioned before, there are two approaches: functional and contextual:

- The individuals delegated with appropriate responsibilities for different aspects of operation of the company are regarded as its directing mind and will (or alter ego). The applicable law, which will determine whether the servant or agents have these specific responsibilities, presumably will be the law governing corporate structure or any other law relevant to internal relations between principal and agent or servant. As apart from traditional directing mind theory these are not necessarily exercising management or control, so class of individuals identified with the corporation is wider in functional approach due to Meridian⁷⁶ case described above. However, the power to bind the company in this case we suppose is found in the relevant legislation which is the law of the subject matter of the main obligation. Because requirements of the fault or reprehensible knowledge in relation to a particular infringement of wrongdoing are found in particular substantive law where the provisions of corporate liability are defined.
- Regardless of whether the servants and agents are alter ego of the company as according to functional approach, the corporation is attributed with the conduct or knowledge of the individuals who are identified pursuant to the construction of the relevant legislation. This last approach is contextual. Here again the relevant legislation is the law of the subject-matter.

⁷⁵ Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 42.

⁷⁶ Meridian Global Funds management asia Ltd. V Securities Commission [1995], 506-507.

III. Corporate Liability in Groups

As far we considered general attribution rules. In this part we will discuss corporate liability in corporate groups. As we have already mentioned the fact of separate legal personality in case of corporate liability is directly connected with the concept of attribution of conduct of corporate actors to the company itself. Only according to those rules, a company as a separate “person” may be held liable. As we could see, these rules are based on primary rules, general and secondary and accordingly may be found in Company Law (primary), Tort Law (general, vicarious), Contract Law (general, agency), secondary (legislation and organizational structure of a company, depends on subject matter, circumstances in status or common law). All these rules show how a company is separated from its members-founders and under some circumstances from other actors of corporation: agents, servants, if the corporate liability is incurred. But a company may be held liable also when it is a shareholder of another company, its subsidiary.

“Today, multinational corporate groups operate by way of sometimes hundreds of subsidiaries organized under the laws of many different states, collectively conducting a single enterprise under the control of the parent corporation. The corporate group is the dominant form of enterprise organization in the largest worldwide markets”.⁷⁷

“One of the great unsolved problems of company law” related to such groups as it is referred in the literature⁷⁸ is a problem of parent-subsidiary relationships, when a parent is held liable for conduct of its subsidiaries. Apart from attribution rules here a legal personality of subsidiaries works in a different direction: a shareholder being a parent company is liable for subsidiaries’ conduct in spite of the fact that subsidiaries have its own legal personality.

So the scheme for a *single independent company* is that a company, not its shareholders, is liable according to attribution rules for the conduct of agents and servants of the company. While in case of a *group of*

⁷⁷ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 5.

⁷⁸ C. Schmitthoff, *Banco Ambrosiano and modern company law* (1987, 151 ZGR), 458.

companies, shareholders-parent companies may be liable for the conduct of its subsidiaries or the actors of the subsidiaries. Here we will consider according to which principles corporate liability of a parent company in the role of shareholders may be invoked. In this case, the rules will be called not attribution rules in the sense of corporate liability for its members and other corporate actors, but corporate piercing rules in the sense of liability of a parent company in a corporate group. However, we have already considered some approaches regarding piercing issues earlier. As we could see these “veil piercing” issues may be applied in two forms:

- 1) Personal liability of individuals in the single company,
- 2) “Personal” liability of a corporation in a group of companies.

As we have to decide regarding the applicable law to the attribution of conduct to the group of companies, the second form is our focus in this paper.

It should also be noted that there is no separate company law for a group of companies. Corporation law (company law) is based on the idea of a single, independent corporation. So no specific rules on a group of companies exist usually, but mainly in accounting and tax law some subjects related to corporate group are regulated independently. Though there are also systems which opted for a specific regulation of corporate groups, for example, Germany, but the entity law doctrine (single company law) is prevailed.⁷⁹

Also another important fact, before we turn to the piercing rules themselves, is that rules differ per substantive law of each legal system. We will consider some examples of Dutch and English piercing of the corporate veil in order to give at least some initial presumptions on the issues of applicable law.

“Piercing” in a group of companies in The Netherlands

According to the Article 2:5 of Dutch Civil Code, commercial companies with limited liability have a legal personality different from the

⁷⁹ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 5.

personality of their shareholders. As a rule, corporate shareholders (parent companies) of a Dutch company with limited liability are not liable for the debts of the company (subsidiary) beyond its capital contribution.

A) Tort. First time shareholder liability for debts of the corporation was upheld in the Osby judgment of the Dutch Supreme Court (Hoge Raad) on the basis of the rules of tort.⁸⁰ In that case, the main question was whether a parent corporation (Osby Sweden) could be liable vis-à-vis a creditor of its wholly-owned Dutch subsidiary (Osby Netherlands). A parent corporation at the same time had provided credit to the subsidiary and had received all the assets of the latter, actual and future, as collateral. So in reality Osby Netherlands didn't have any assets for satisfaction of its debts.

Before Osby case the similar situation was in Erba case, though in Osby it was extended to parent-subsidiary relations. After Osby decision there were a number of cases where the following idea was supported: a parent corporation may have a legal duty to take into account the interests of their subsidiaries' creditors. In this case important factors are:

- 1) a violation of the duty of due care towards third-party creditors will often turn on the question whether or not the parent corporation knew or should have known that its act or omission would harm the creditors of its subsidiary;
- 2) when the parent intensively influences the subsidiary's daily management, it may be considered as a quasi-director. Being a quasi-director, it may be held bound by the same duties as formal directors and it may incur the same liabilities in the event of breach of duty.⁸¹

So according to the factors above the legal ground for the solving of cases of veil piercing were the *rules of tort*. Also the basis for the piercing for a group of companies may laid down *in the company law* as described below.

⁸⁰ Dutch Supreme Court (Hoge Raad) 25 September 1981 (Osby-Pannan A/B v. Ias Verkoopmaatschappij BV), NJ 1982, no 443.

⁸¹ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 35.

B) Directors' liability (Company Law). The Article 2:138 (NV)/248 (BV) of the Dutch Civil Code provides for liability of directors of a company for the debts of a subsidiary in the case of gross mismanagement that is an important cause of the bankruptcy of their company. This provision also covers the situation when directors are not formally appointed, but only de facto, so a parent corporation may be considered as a de facto manager when it has had a direct influence over the subsidiary's management and when in reality the subsidiary's formal management has been set aside.⁸² Again, according to company law, as in the latter case, a parent company may incur the common director's liability in case of bankruptcy, if it acts as a formal director.

C) Voluntary piercing (Company Law). Voluntary piercing may be specified in the Company Law. For example, in the Article 2:403 Dutch Civil Code a declaration by a parent corporation may be made that it will be jointly liable for the debts of its subsidiary in order to allow the latter to obtain an exemption from the duty to publish annual accounts. This only concerns debts of the subsidiary that result from legal transactions (e.g. contracts), it does not include tax liabilities or liabilities for torts committed by the subsidiary.

D) Identification. When application of legal norm of the subject matter or contractual rule of the main obligation doesn't explicitly refer to legal persons, it is deemed that two legal persons concerned have different identity. Identification results in the consideration of two affiliated persons having one identity, when acts and liabilities of one corporation may be attributed to another corporation.⁸³

In the end, the court should decide on the priority between: the content, purpose of the contractual or legal norm and the legal personality of affiliated corporations.

⁸² M.L. (Loes) Lennarts, *Concernaansprakelijkheid* (Groningen, 1999), 180.

⁸³ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 36.

The example of Dutch case law would be Heuga decision of the Dutch Supreme Court of 1995.⁸⁴ It is said that the Dutch Supreme Court has traditionally treated the identification theory with reticence: The fact that a corporation (subsidiary), party to a contract, is part of a corporate group, even when almost all of its shares are in the hands of one shareholder, and when this shareholder forms an economic unity with its corporation, does not generally provide sufficient ground to hold the shareholder liable for the contractual liabilities of the corporation. There are suggestions to apply the identification to the cases where rules on tort do not provide a solution.⁸⁵

“Piercing” in a group of companies in The United Kingdom

In our first chapter “From separate Legal Personality to Attribution rules” it was already illustrated the importance of the case Salomon reflecting the principles of fundamental attribute of corporate personality⁸⁶ and a cornerstone of English company law in general, and of entrepreneurial liability. The same principles are applied to corporate groups: shareholders of a limited liability company are not as such liable for the debts of their company. Corporate veil lifting in the UK is allowed in the following cases (we will consider some of them):

a) Fraudulent and Wrongful Trading (legal piercing):

One of the rules where piercing may be applied is found in Insolvency Act 1986 (Section 213-215) on fraudulent and wrongful trading. The fraudulent trading occurs when the business of a company has been carried on with the intent to defraud creditors of the company or for a fraudulent purpose. The requirement related to the intent makes it impossible to apply piercing to shareholders liability. For this reason the Act was extended to “wrongful” trading and now it provides the same type of liability for a director of a company that has gone into insolvent liquidation

⁸⁴ Dutch Supreme Court (Hoge Raad) 26 January 1994, (1994) 545 N.J. (with comments J. M. M. Maeijer).

⁸⁵ Karen Vandekerckove, *Vereenzelviging en het doorbreken van de rechtssubjectiviteit van verbonden vennootschappen* (2000 TRV,) 277.

⁸⁶ Davies, *Op. cit.*, 85.

and that knew or ought to have concluded that there was no reasonable prospect that the company would avoid going into insolvent liquidation. For the corporate groups the importance lies in the liability of a parent company in case of shadow directors.

As we may suppose, for this type of piercing the law of the corporate structure, which got insolvent, should be dominant, thus a subsidiary's company law or insolvency law shall be reference for the director's (parent's) liability requirements in case of fraudulent and wrongful trading.

b) Abuse of company name (legal piercing):

A company may get into insolvent liquidation, and if within five years after the insolvency directors of the former company form the new company, giving to new one the same or identical name and buying the assets of the previous, they are deemed shadow directors of the new company. Insolvency Act provides personal, joint and severe liability of the shadow directors (which are concerned in management) with the company in the mentioned case (Section 216 Insolvency Act 1986).

We may conclude about applicable law to be the same as in the section "a".

c) Other types of directors' liability (legal piercing):

Apart from a parent's liability (when the parent is a director of its subsidiary) in case of insolvency, it may be held liable for breach of the general directors' duty of care and skill and fiduciary duties. The specific type of liability may arise, for instance, when in its capacity of director, the parent caused loss to the company by retaining or misapplying its assets (Section 212 Insolvency Act 1986). According to this provision, a director may be liable for ordinary or gross negligence.⁸⁷ The example is the case of when a director had a direct or indirect interest in a transaction at the company's expense.⁸⁸

d) Common Law Exceptions to Limited Liability (Judicial Piercing):

⁸⁷ M. R. Pasban, *A review of directors' liabilities of an insolvent company in the US and England* (2001, JBL), 36.

⁸⁸ *Knight v. Frost*, [1999] 1 BCLC 364, 365.

Apart from the statutory exceptions, there are a number of examples in common law, when courts made decisions to lift corporate veil. In such cases, it is said by some authors that shareholder liability depends on “a degree of judicial subjectivity” and remains “tangled in a mesh of uncertainty”.⁸⁹

One more example: how the court lifted the veil... We have demonstrated that in each legal system there could be different approaches to piercing of corporate veil. And there is no unique approach in relation to corporate liability of a parent company. When usually a parent corporation dominates or controls its subsidiary, the following terminology may be used in conclusion about the subsidiary: “alter ego”, “agency”, “sham”, “shell” etc. But excessive control and lack of separate existence usually is not enough to pierce the veil. So there are other doctrines, and in result various metaphors exist, which don’t provide clear legal rules. And it is difficult to predict results of the case with the multinational company where different subsidiaries and jurisdictions are involved. We will conclude this part with the example of well known court case to show how the court may decide the case in the United States for example, piercing corporate veil in a very unpredictable way. In the United States the doctrine of “enterprise liability” is applied by the courts, when a corporate group was considered as a whole, so any of the members may be held liable as a parent company as well. This was also about Amoco Cadiz case. In result of the casualty the oil spill from the super tanker Amoco Cadiz extended over about 130 miles of the French coast. The effect was devastating on the northwest coast of France and its departments, cities and people. The tanker Amoco Cadiz had been purchased by Amoco Tankers Company, Liberian wholly-owned subsidiary of Standard Oil Company, an Indian corporation with principal place of business in Chicago. But on the other hand, the ship was purchased at the proposal of another subsidiary of Standard, Amoco International Oil Company, incorporated in Delaware with principal place of business in

⁸⁹ S. Griffin, *Holding companies and subsidiaries – the corporate veil* (1991, 12(1), *Comp. Lawyer*) 17.

Chicago. Amoco International Oil Company was in charge for design of the ship, supervision of its construction, maintenance and repair, and at the same time was actual operator of the ship for the moment of the accident. The registered owner at that time was another subsidiary, Amoco Transport Company. A parent company, Standard was held liable for damages jointly and severally with Amoco Transport and Amoco International Oil Company. Though there was no evidence of fraud on the part of a parent company, and, at the same time, the defects of the design, construction, maintenance, crew training, or operation could be attributed directly to Standard; however, that was a decision of Standard to purchase a vessel, also to decide who would be the owner of the vessel on the basis of advice of its accounting, tax and legal departments. Nevertheless, it is stressed in the literature that none of the facts was decisive in itself.⁹⁰

The Law governing piercing of corporate veil in transnational cases

We could see from the examples above that there are a number of methods of piercing. And each state applies different ways, determining whether the corporate veil should be pierced. We have also provided some our suggestions regarding to which substantive law the legal relations have to be linked to. For example, company law, bankruptcy law, tort law. However, these substantive laws are not identical per state, and we have mentioned that the uniformed law on corporate groups does not exist in all states; however the enterprise entity theory (as opposed to corporate entity theory) is just emerging theory and is not universally accepted.⁹¹

So which law to apply in case of transnational cases which involve parent-subsidiary relations?

First of all, if a corporate group law exists, it may be applied mandatorily (loi de police). Even though there is corporate group law in a particular state, there should be connecting factors which lead to

⁹⁰ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 87.

⁹¹ Andreas F. Lowenfeld, *International Litigation and the questions of reasonableness* (Oxford University Press, 1996), 85.

application of that law in the state. But what if there is no such group law at all?

We started this section and even this article from the notion on “legal personality”. We have already indicated that in the parent-subsidiary relations “legal personality” of a subsidiary plays a significant role. For this reason, legal capacity and capacity to act of the subsidiary is connected with its *lex societatis*. Nevertheless, not all issues, of course, are governed by the *lex societatis*. We have already shown the Conflicts of Laws (corporations) Act of the Netherlands, which includes the list of the matters governed by the *lex societatis*. Also *lex societatis* governs the grounds for dissolution of the company, for example. Traditionally the veil piercing is considered as a problem not only of legal capacity, but also for recognition of legal personality of the company as an establishment of a foreign parent-company. Especially this problem concerns subsidiaries, which are located in the “real seat” countries, but are incorporated in a different state. In this case, piercing is deemed to be an obstacle for recognition of “foreign” secondary establishment (subsidiaries). If in a “real seat” state a subsidiary is not recognized and a parent company is held liable in result of veil piercing, so a parent company-shareholder is subject to unlimited personal liability. But in view of “freedom of establishment” in the EU, this should have a different approach. Even though veil piercing and non-recognition has the same effect, it is submitted that *lex societatis* is not necessarily the law governing veil piercing. And this is even more supported by the fact that in the EU due to freedom of establishment, Member States have to recognize secondary establishments of the foreign companies, providing them with the same rights as a national entity has.

Suggesting that secondary establishment is recognized in the Member State of the EU, again this is not necessarily *lex societatis* governing veil piercing. Is there any single connecting factor for the choice-of law rules in case of veil piercing? Definitely not, because from our examples above on the veil piercing in the Netherlands and the UK, it was clear that different disciplines of the law are involved as it was noted above. Moreover, it is

sometimes not easy to determine to which disciplines of the law the subject-matter of the case is related.

Looking through our examples in the beginning of this chapter, we may start from the cases in the Netherlands and now we will summarize:

a) **Torts.** In the first example we considered a tort vis-à-vis creditors; a false appearance of creditworthiness was created with the knowledge and support of the parent company. The latter is a substance of the tortuous act committed by a parent company in the place of subsidiary's location – *lex loci delicti/damni*. As creditworthiness concerns the assets of the company-subsiary, a false appearance of the subsidiary presumably was created in the same place where the assets are located. Usually assets are located where a subsidiary has its seat/incorporation.

b) **Lex societatis.** Here, especially for “real seat” states, *lex loci delicti/damni* and *lex societatis* will be the same.

c) **Directors' liability** may be governed in different ways depending on the case. If directors-parents violate the rules of company law, we make reference to company law. It is submitted that a director-parent company acting as a director of a subsidiary should respect the *lex societatis* of the subsidiary. It may also be a case, as is described above, that a director is only a *de facto* director. Nevertheless, *de facto* director may be considered as *de jure* director in cases of violation of bankruptcy law, for example.⁹² But in this case a parent company acting as it were a *de jure* director, thus violating statutory rules (bankruptcy law or company law) also may be deemed to commit a tort vis-à-vis third parties, which incur damages in result of that. Do we have to apply *lex concursus*, *lex societatis* or *lex loci delicti/damni* in such cases?

From the point of view of rights of third parties suffered, *lex societatis* of subsidiary will be appropriate. But inappropriate if a subsidiary is incorporated in the different state. And if this is a violation of company law, again *lex societatis* may prevail. If we will take *lex loci delicti/damni*, the place where the harmful event occurred presumably is the place where the

⁹² Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 623

decision giving rise to violation of company law and tort was taken by a de facto director-parent company. On the other hand, "it seems preferable to locate the gravity of the parent's acts at the seat of subsidiary"⁹³, so the *lex loci delicti/damni* is the subsidiary's location, even though decisions are imposed on the subsidiary's management and concern operation of a subsidiary. So if in result of decision-making power of parent the violation of company law by subsidiary occurred, *lex societatis* may govern the issue of piercing.

In case of bankruptcy again, the choice-of-law depends on the violation of substantive bankruptcy law. If provisions of law require acts of directors (file for bankruptcy, for example) to be performed in the place where a subsidiary has its head office, the tort is deemed to be committed in that place. That place is also the location of the head office, thus presumably *lex societatis* of subsidiary. So *lex concursus* may coincide not only with *lex societatis*, but also with *lex loci delicti/damni*. There also can be other provisions of bankruptcy law like liability for gross mismanagement (having contributed to bankruptcy) for example, where rules quite differs from directors' liability based on rules of tort or company law.

The main point is that if the rule giving rise to liability is a rule of a company law, *lex societatis* may be more appropriate. When it is a rule of bankruptcy law, the *lex concursus* applies.

Regarding bankruptcy proceedings it is also important to stress that *lex concursus* is linked to jurisdiction. Under the Insolvency Regulation,⁹⁴ the courts of the state within the territory of which the centre of the debtor's main interests is situated,⁹⁵ if this is located in the EU, has jurisdiction (main insolvency proceedings). Usually the main interests presumably are located at the place of statutory seat. But if there is an establishment in another state, that state also have a right to open secondary bankruptcy

⁹³ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 627.

⁹⁴ Regulation no. 1346/2000 of the council of 29 May 2000 on insolvency proceedings, OJ L 160 of 30 June 2000.

⁹⁵ According to Preamble 13 of the Regulation, this is a place where debtor conducts the administration of his interests on a regular basis.

proceedings, but they can concern assets located on the territory of that state. So in the Member States, *lex concursus* coincides with the *lex fori* and this is supported by the Article 4 of the Regulation: the *lex concursus* governs the bankruptcy of a company declared in the forum state.

As an example of the important fact that *lex concursus* governs issues of veil piercing the liability of directors for gross mismanagement having contributed to bankruptcy is mentioned above. Such liability, by the way, only arises in bankruptcy.

d) **Voluntary piercing** is only applied if it is allowed in the legislation. The legislation supposedly is the one of the *lex societatis* of subsidiary. Because only that legislation may exempt the subsidiary from duties, for which a parent company takes responsibility. We will presume that constitutive documents of the subsidiary shall include such declaration of a parent company.

e) For the **Identification** we would repeat: When application of legal norm of the subject matter or contractual rule of the main obligation doesn't explicitly refer to legal persons, it is deemed that two legal persons concerned have different identity. Identification results in the consideration of two affiliated persons having one identity, when acts and liabilities of one corporation may be attributed to another corporation. So the court may apply Identification in relation to contractual and non-contractual obligations. And the law applicable to the main subject matter will obviously give a guide to whether identification principles may be applied in the forum place, which can be *lex contractus* or *lex loci delicti/damni*, for instance.

Now we can turn for some examples in common law.

a) We assume that principles of applicable law for *Fraudulent and Wrongful Trading* will be the same as for directors' liability in the Netherlands.

b) *Abuse of company name* in our example in the UK is concerned with the provisions of Insolvency Act, so in that case liabilities for shadow directors is specified by the bankruptcy law of the *lex concursus*, which as

we concluded above may be the same with the *lex societatis* (in case of ‘real seat’) and as suggested with *lex loci delicti/damni*.

c) *Other types of directors’ liability* may be for the breach of general duty of care and skill and fiduciary duties. The duty of care and skills, and fiduciary duties may be included to the provisions of the company law or bankruptcy law. In our example, liability was in gross negligence of a director-parent company for retaining or misapplying subsidiary’s assets.

d) *Common Law Exceptions to Limited Liability* constitutes judicial piercing. In the case *Adams v Cape Industries*⁹⁶ the court provided three types of such piercing. One of them is in case of Fraud (see the next subsection “e”).

e) We will complete our overview of the examples given above with one the most typical judicial piercing: *Fraud found in abuse of the legal personality*. In general abusive behavior may concern issues of company law, private law rules in tort, contract law etc. again here we face different disciplines involved.

Because the underlying idea of this type of judicial piercing is that shareholders have misused the institution of limited liability and have not respected the separate legal personality of their corporation, it seems appropriate to connect an abuse of the legal personality in the first place to the place of the *lex societatis*. What a shareholder can and what it cannot do with its corporation must be determined mainly on the basis of the law that governs the functioning of the company.⁹⁷

As we are talking about abuse of legal personality of the subsidiary, this is likely to be the company law governing the subsidiary as *lex societatis*. However, again the difference in approaches in the theories of “incorporation” and “real seat” may influence the consequences. First of all, parent’s corporation can choose the *lex societatis*. However, the state where the subsidiary is located concern about the public interests and interests of creditors first of all. So if a parent has chosen the incorporation

⁹⁶ *Adams v Cape Industries*, Court of Appeal 27 July 1989, [1990] 2WLR, 657-786.

⁹⁷ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 629.

doctrine state (because of high liability standards, for example) for its subsidiary, the creditors of the subsidiary, where it is really located may be in a disadvantaged position. From this point of view, creditors' interests the *lex loci actus* (may coincide with the *lex contractus* or *lex loci delicti/damni*, but not necessary) may be more appropriate; for example, where the subsidiary is engaged in the transaction. The discussions about these two options for the law governing veil piercing are not new. Far in 1965, during the Warsaw Session of the Institute of International Law dedicated to the stock companies in private international law, proposal was made to apply both the *lex societatis* and the *lex loci actus* (where the subsidiary is active). However, this is difficult to achieve if *lex societatis* and *lex loci actus* are in different states and several laws (*depeçage*) have to be applied in this case. In this regard a draft resolution of the International Law Institute didn't find support.⁹⁸ But it was submitted that only some issues might be governed by the *lex loci actus*: for example, the representation of an establishment of the foreign company on the local territory.

The *lex loci actus* may be taken into account (as a matter of fact for ascertaining liability) in cases of abuse of legal personality if it is necessary to measure the fault of the parent company in tort or if it is necessary to appreciate the civil consequences of parent's actions.⁹⁹ Also interference of the *lex loci actus* is found in contract law, in particular in the Article 11 of Rome II. According to the Article, a person who contracts abroad and who did not have the capacity to enter into the contract under the law of another country (its *lex societatis*), cannot invoke such incapacity if the company would have had capacity to enter into the contract under the law of the state of action, unless the contracting party was aware of this

⁹⁸ International Law Institute, Draft Resolution on stock companies and private international law, Warsaw Session, (1965), 21 (I), Ann. Inst. Dr. Int. 321.

⁹⁹ Article 13 of regulation no 864/2007 of the European parliament and of the council of 11 July 2007 on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations (Rome II).

incapacity or was not aware thereof as a result of negligence.¹⁰⁰ The local rules on an abuse of the legal personality to certain extent may be mandatory from the point of view of social and economic order on the territory of the state of the locus loci actus. But they are not mandatory as overriding, priority rules, lex loci actus leading to the application of the foreign law will be applied in the light of the conflict choice-of-law rules. But if lex loci actus leads to the local rules, mandatory local rules will be applied by default in contradiction of lex societatis. So everything will depend on the direction of lex loci actus.

So, the lex loci actus have only an alternative role (as a connecting factor) to the lex societatis when it is fairer to refer to the law of the action place. On the other hand, if the court chooses such connecting factor as lex loci actus to be more appropriate from the point of view of creditors' interests, this may be detrimental for the parent-shareholders, which exercised their right to choose the jurisdiction for their subsidiary beforehand. Thus a Dutch company operating in Germany may be subject to the lex loci actus in Germany, whereas lex societatis is the Netherlands as it is the state of incorporation.

When liability derives from a personal fault on the part of the parent company, either in the context of a contract concluded or tort committed by the parent, limited liability is not at stake. Personal fault may occur when a parent corporation is in a contractual or tort relationship with the subsidiary's creditors, thus the lex contractus and lex loci delicti/damni have priority. We have already described director's liability in cases when their decision leads to insolvency, or as it is called unduly continuing loss-making activities. Such behavior may be considered as a tort, but if there is specific related provisions in company or bankruptcy law, lex loci delicti/damni will give way to lex societatis or lex concursus. In contractual obligations vis-à-vis subsidiary's creditors, a parent will be bound itself when it has contractual

¹⁰⁰ Originally the Article is based on the *Lizardi* case before the French Supreme Court (Cass. Req., 16 January 1861, (1861) 1 DP, 193 (cited by F. Rigaux and M. Fallon, (Droit international privé, Tome 2), 404, no. 1124)).

relations with creditors. For example, the law governing the agreement – guarantee of the performance of the subsidiary’ obligations will be *lex contractus* for veil piercing if a parent supposed to be liable.¹⁰¹

Applicable law found in internal or external relations in the Group

When we were describing attribution rules in the previous chapter “General principles of corporate liability”, the concepts of internal and external relations in agency played a very important role: principal-agent, principal-third party, and agent-third party. First are internal and last two – external relations in the groups, accordingly: parent-subsidary, parent-creditors, and subsidiary-creditors.

While we were giving examples of the choice-of-law rules, which apply to piercing of veil, each choice of applicable law was either derived from internal or from external relations.

There are suggestions in the literature about choice of law rules from the perspective of internal and external relations in a group in contractual and non-contractual relations.¹⁰² For non-contractual claims, piercing of veil should be decided under the law which is applicable for determining the rights of the external tort creditors, rather than under the law of internal affairs – *lex societatis* of the subsidiary. “Otherwise, the controlling shareholders of a corporation that are potentially subject to liability from successful piercing claims would have the incentive to incorporate in a jurisdiction with a relatively restrictive piercing jurisprudence”.¹⁰³

¹⁰¹ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 662.

¹⁰² Gregory Scott Crespi, “Choice of law in veil piercing litigation: why courts should discard the internal affairs rule and embrace general choice of law principles,” *New York University Annual Survey of American Law*, vol. 64 (2008): 12, SSRN-id317384 http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1317384 (accessed 6 May 2019).

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*, 12.

On the other hand, in non-contractual obligations the chosen law may also apply in theory and now is one of the cornerstones in Rome II Regulation.¹⁰⁴

In contrast to tort, in contractual relations parties in fact usually choose the law; it may be the law which will apply to piercing claims. Except the cases where under other circumstances this chosen law is considered as inappropriate court cannot disregard the choice of the parties. However, it is quite rare when the parties agree as to which body of law will govern any piercing attempts which arise from contractual obligations. For this reason, it is suggested that general choice of law principles should apply to choose the law governing piercing, whether those claims are based upon underlying tort or contract obligations, except where the parties have chosen the law appropriate to circumstances of the case.¹⁰⁵ But again if the latter (chosen by the parties law) is inappropriate, general principles will apply, taking into account connecting factors mentioned in the previous part. In one of the latest cases *Vitol sa v Capri Marine Ltd*, choice of law clause in the charter party was disregarded in respect of piercing of veil. Vitol, the claimant, had obtained judgment against Capri, the first defendant, in the sum of US\$6,793,518.28 in respect of liability under a charter party. To help to enforce the judgment, Vitol obtained Rule B attachment over the Panamax bulker Thor in Baltimore, Maryland on 23 December 2009. Thor was owned by a company managed by the same managers as Capri and in the same beneficial ownership as Capri. The complaint named a number of parties; including the defendants; another company in the beneficial ownership of the defendants; and the managers of Thor and argued that they should all be viewed as a single economic unit without corporate distinction where all assets of the defendants answered for the debts of the other. This was Capri's application for two orders: first, an anti-suit injunction in respect of the Maryland proceedings on the basis that the effect of the jurisdiction and

¹⁰⁴ Regulation 864/2007 (Rome II) on the law applicable to non-contractual obligation, Article 14.

¹⁰⁵ Crespi, *Op. cit.*, 17.

choice of law clause in the charter party was that the issue whether any of the defendants in the Maryland proceedings were alter egos of Capri should be decided in England according to English law; next, an order preventing Vitol from using documents disclosed by Capri pursuant to orders made by the English court in proceedings in Maryland, which it argued were against different parties. Tomlinson J dismissed the two applications. The anti-suit injunction was refused: the jurisdiction clause in the charter party did not extend to the determination of Vitol's case in Maryland against the other enforcement defendants.¹⁰⁶

IV. Applicable law to attribution of conduct and veil piercing in European Private International Law

Since the Amsterdam Treaty, providing of measures relating to judicial cooperation to the extent necessary for the proper functioning of the internal market in the European Community became one of the next steps in establishing progressively an area of freedom, security and justice in the Community (Article 61 (c) of the TEC). The number of Regulations were adopted, and among them the Regulation 593/2008 (Rome I) on the law applicable to contractual (applies from 17 December 2009) and Regulation 864/2007 (Rome II) on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations. In its turn, the Regulations play its significant role in the system of choice of law applicable to variety of civil and commercial matters.

There are several cornerstones in Rome I and Rome II (choice of law by the parties, *lex loci damni*), which are based mainly on Savignian system: national law for the international disputes is determined by neutral and territorial connecting factors, but with some exceptions and special rules (for the particular types of contracts like “carriage of goods”), in respect to weaker parties, mandatory provisions. Regulations aim “at striking the balance between legal certainty on the one hand and doing justice in individual cases on the other”. “This set of rules thus creates a flexible

¹⁰⁶ *Vitol sa v capri marine ltd (no. 2) (the Thor)* [2010] ewhc 458 (comm), Queen’s Bench Division, Commercial Court, the Hon Mr Justice Tomlinson, 9 March 2010.

framework of conflict of law rules, and enables the court seized to treat individual cases in an appropriate manner.¹⁰⁷ For the purpose of our research, first of all the exceptions, i.e. the exclusions from the scope, attract our attention. Then importance of connecting factors determining applicable law is stressed especially in the cases with piercing of veil in groups. We will develop possible solutions on the choice-of-law rules, taking into account the principles of attribution and piercing of veil shown in the previous chapters above, for both contractual and non-contractual matters.

Regulation 593/2008 (Rome I) on the law applicable to contractual obligations

a) Attribution rules:

Primary rules (Organs) are directly connected with the law governing internal relations of the corporate structure – *lex societatis*. Article 1(2) (f) of Rome I Regulation provides that the questions governed by the law of companies and other bodies, corporate or unincorporated, such as the creation, by registration or otherwise, legal capacity, internal organization or winding-up of companies and other bodies, corporate or unincorporated, and the personal liability of officers and members as such for the obligations of the company or body are excluded from the scope of Rome I. According to the Guliano-Lagarde Report, the matters are excluded, *inter alia*, on the ground that the harmonization of company law in the EU is in progress.¹⁰⁸ Exclusion of “questions governed by the law of companies and other bodies corporate” however doesn’t lead to a particular answer on the scope of the questions in each Member State. Thus the Rome I Regulation does not determine how such questions are to be characterized. “Questions governed by the law of companies and other bodies corporate” presumably don’t have a uniform meaning. In the literature, the most spread answer in

¹⁰⁷ Xandra E. Kramer, “The Rome II Regulation on the Law Applicable to Non-Contractual Obligations: The European private international law tradition continued,” http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1314749 (accessed 6 May 2019).

¹⁰⁸ Richard Plender, Michael Wilderspin, *The European Contracts Convention, the Rome Convention on the Choice of Law for Contracts* (Sweet&Maxwell, 2001), 74.

this regard is that this is *lex causae* which is to determine whether a question is governed by company law.¹⁰⁹ But this contention is not supported in the literature in respect of Rome I, because “it is inconsistent with the aim of the Regulation, which is to ensure so far as is possible the equality and uniformity of rights derived from it in the several Member States”.¹¹⁰

“Organs” authority is, again, actual authority which depends on the terms and interpretation of an agreement between the principal and the agent. So the actual authority should be determined in accordance with the proper law of the contract between them.¹¹¹ So, in the case of a corporate organ, as we have showed here, actual authority depends on the corporate constitution and *lex societatis*.

The same rules apply to the circumstances where Company Law specifies one representative having authority of “organs” (as an example, Article 2:240 CC of the Netherlands).

General (agency) rules: Among exclusions is also “the question whether an agent is able to bind a principal, or an organ to bind a company or body corporate, or unincorporated, to a third party” (Article 1 (2) (g)). The Guliano-Lagarde Report makes it clear that the exclusion affects only the relationship between the principal and third parties: the question whether the principal is bound *vis-à-vis* third parties by the acts of the agent in specific cases.¹¹² So among the three legal relationships that arise from a contract concluded by an agent – between principal and agent, between agent and third party and between principal and third party – only the first two are covered by the regulation. The question of the agent’s powers is excluded by the Article 1(2)(g). One of the reasons as it is mentioned in the

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid.*, 75.

¹¹⁰ Richard Plender and Michael Wilderspin, *The European private international law of obligations* (Sweet&Maxwell, 2009), para 5-042.

¹¹¹ *Ruby v Commercial Union* [1933] 150 LT 38 (CA); *Marubeni v Mongolian Government* (No. 1) [2002] 2 All ER (Comm) 873 (Aikens j); *Marubeni v Mongolian Government* (No. 2) [2004] 2 Lloyd’s Rep 198 (Cresswell j).

¹¹² Giuliano-Lagarde Report, [1980] Oj c 282/1, 15.

proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I) for the exclusion are the diversity of the national conflict rules when the Convention (previously before Rome I) was negotiated and the existence of the Hague Convention of 14 March 1978 on the law applicable to agency.¹¹³ In respect of relations between a principal and an agent appropriate law may be contained in the rules of the Regulation, in particular in the Articles 3 and 4. So, if in the absence of a choice, according to Article 4, the law will be determined in accordance with the Article 4 (2), and it may lead to the establishment of an agent.¹¹⁴ But as is shown above this doesn't concern internal corporate principal-agent relations in the company: a company-organs (primary rules and actual authority within the rules, see below).

An issue whether a principal is bound vis-à-vis a third party relates to the relations between a principal and third party. The choice of law rules between a principal and an agent cannot determine the position of the third party regarding the law applicable to relations principal-third party; that is the reason why these relations are excluded from the scope of the Regulation.¹¹⁵ The forum will apply its own rules to determine the applicable law.¹¹⁶ There are two types of authority, as we could examine them earlier, between of corporate actors: mainly actual and apparent is discussed. First of all, the court, applying *lex fori*, should determine whether there is actual or apparent authority of the corporate agent. In fact, there is no need to determine actual authority of organs as it is determined by the *lex societatis*. We have already discussed in the first part on the actual authority of organs: the *lex societatis* will be relevant, as it will be a corporate agency, not consensual. There is however one exception as well, and this is a power of attorney from shareholders. The latter is included to the consensual agency, but, nevertheless, is also governed as we discovered above ("From a

¹¹³ Convention of 14 March 1978 on the Law Applicable to Agency, http://www.hcch.net/in dex_en.php?act=conventions.text&cid=89 (accessed 6 May 2019).

¹¹⁴ Plender, *Op. cit.*, para 5-049.

¹¹⁵ *Ibid*, para 5-050.

¹¹⁶ *Ibid*, para 5-050.

separate Legal Personality to Attribution rules”) by the *lex societatis*. All other cases, in which questions of the power of the agent to bind a company arise, concern apparent authority. We will repeat what was already demonstrated in the conclusion of the section “From a separate Legal Personality to Attribution rules”:

- “Organs” exceeds their actual authority,
- Corporate official (s) having representative authority the same as “organs” according to Article of association, i.e. where it is not specified by law, but only determined by the company itself,
- Other functionaries (not organs) included to the Articles of Association,
- Other agents (e.g. employees or members of “organ”), but with special power of authority granted by the company.

Thus, if court according to *lex fori* determines one of these apparent authorities, the law applicable to the power to bind the company will be determined by the *lex fori*, and is not connected to internal relations (principal-agent). If it is the English court, the power to bind will be determined by the law applicable to a main contract. The law of the main contract, in its turn, is subject to the rules of Rome I. So the law determined by the rules of Rome I will in fact be the law governing the power of the agent to bind a company *vis-à-vis* a third party in this case. This will apply equally to ratification and to intervention of an undisclosed principal.¹¹⁷ The Netherlands, within the *lex fori* and in accordance with its national law, will apply the Hague Convention of 14 March 1978 on the law applicable to agency as the state is one of the few participants of the convention.

b) Piercing of veil:

Despite the fact that choice of law by the parties due to Article 3 (1) is a cornerstone of the Regulation, this is not the case with piercing of veil. Usually contracts don’t include choice of law for piercing. If the agreement includes a choice of law clause regarding the main obligations, which is not

¹¹⁷ Peter Stone, *EU Private International Law* (Edward Elgar, 2006), 300.

appropriate for the piercing claim, it will probably be disregarded.¹¹⁸ As the area of piercing in groups lacks a separate substantive law, and connecting factors responding to the interests of creditors (and state) are important, the ordinary choice of law rules (except the law chosen by parties) applied to substantive law governing the main claim of the case are usually applied also to piercing, for example in case of parent's personal fault in contractual obligations, the *lex contractus* was suggested.¹¹⁹ That probably is appropriate as the connecting factors implied in the Articles 3 (3), and the Article 4 (2), (3), (4), may presumably be concentrated in the place where creditors are located and where the contract was concluded.

As it is shown in result of our investigations of veil piercing in different legal systems, in contractual obligations also voluntary piercing may apply. If voluntary piercing is provided by *lex societatis* of the subsidiary, a parent may be held liable in accordance with the company law, what is not a subject matter of the Regulation Rome I.

Results of the research

We will share the results through the overview of what was important in each of the sections.

We will start from the notion of Lord Hoffmann in the decision of Meridian case: Any proposition about a company necessarily involves a reference to a set of rules. A company exists because there is a rule ... which says that a *persona ficta* shall be deemed to exist and to have certain of the powers, rights and duties of a natural person. But there would be little sense in deeming such a *persona ficta* to exist unless there were also rules to tell on what acts were to count as acts of the company. It is, therefore, a necessary part of corporate personality that there should be rules by which acts are attributed to the company.¹²⁰

¹¹⁸ Crespi, *Op. cit.*, 12.

¹¹⁹ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 662.

¹²⁰ Meridian Global Funds Management Asia Limited v. Securities Commission [1995] 2 AC 500.

And in the same case of Law Lord:

There is in fact no such thing as the company as such, no “ding an sich”, only the applicable rules.¹²¹

Then we have made classification of applicable to the company attribution rules according to which it may be held liable:

I. *Corporate liability in contractual obligations* mainly arises from primary rules and general agency rules, though in the UK secondary rules are applicable. So our initial conclusions, based on the investigations made in the literature on Agency on Private International Law, on law applicable to “power” of different corporate actors (or bodies) to bind the company were as follows:

- *Primary rules*: these rules can be divided into two types, and it is referred to as “corporate agency” created via:
 - 1) “Organs” – law governing internal relations of the corporate structure, *lex societatis*;
 - 2) Corporate official(s) having representative authority the same as “organs” according to Article of association, i.e. where it is allowed by law (as an example, Article 2:240 CC of the Netherlands) – law governing internal relations of the corporate structure, *lex societatis*.
- *General (agency) rules*: these rules are divided into more parts as we will see, and are included to the type of “consensual agency”:
 - 1) “Organs” exceeds their actual authority – here actual authority is transferred to apparent authority and is subject to consensual agency, not corporate, and the law governing external relations is the law applicable to power to bind a company;
 - 2) Corporate official(s) having representative authority the same as “organs” according to Article of association, i.e. where it is not specified by law, but only determined by the company itself - apparent authority, and is subject to corporate agency, and the

¹²¹ Cheong-Ann, *Op. cit.*, 23.

law governing internal relations is the law applicable to power to bind a company;

3) Other functionaries (not organs) included to the Articles of Association – apparent authority, and is subject to consensual agency, not corporate, and the law governing external relations is the law applicable to power to bind a company,

4) Other agents (e.g. employees or members of “organ”), but with special power of authority granted by the company – apparent authority, and is subject to consensual agency, not corporate, and the law governing external relations is the law applicable to power to bind a company;

5) Shareholders’ power of attorney – actual authority and is subject to consensual agency, not corporate, and the law governing internal relations is the law applicable to power to bind a company.

II. *Non-contractual obligations:*

- *General (vicarious) rules:* actions of servants or agents, without representative authority, leading to vicarious liability of the company – the law which is applicable to main obligation;
- *Secondary rules:* these rules are divided into two approaches 1) contextual and 2) functional:
 - 1) contextual approach: construction of legislation is important – the law which is applicable to main obligation applies;
 - 2) functional approach: directing mind theory is still relevant in common law, lex forum will likely to decide on the operational role of the servant or agent in relation to the alleged infringement or wrongdoing and the circumstances in issue, whether servant or agents can be considered as “directing mind”.

Relying on the investigations made in the literature, in the third chapter “General principles of corporate liability and Attribution rules” we also have given examples on the substantive law of piercing existing in some legal systems and on the law applicable to piercing of veil in the group.

However, the area is not scrutinized enough in the literature and there is no unique approach of substantive law separately governing the issues of piercing in the states.

But where specific law on corporate groups exists, it may be applied mandatorily, *loi de police*. Here, as through all examples of applicable law in disputes where a company is involved, the question of distinction between two doctrines “real seat” and “incorporation” arises. Which states’ law on corporate group should be applied: the seat or the place of incorporation? Again the conflict exists, what is mentioned in the literature as well: some states will apply connecting factor of “real seat”, other may apply the *lex societatis* of subsidiary and the latter again leads to two-sided approach – either it is *lex* of real seat or *lex* of the incorporation.

For our further points it was important to stress one more time that *lex societatis* may belong to both of the locations depending of the state’s doctrine: *lex* of real seat or *lex* of the incorporation.

Other essential aspects which are considered in the literature in relation to the law applicable to veil piercing: real seat and incorporation linked to limitation of liability issues, stakeholder’s interests, and recognition of foreign entities...

As we could observed the main rules would be application of *lex societatis*, because primarily the issues related to the subsidiary are connected to its capacity, legal personality, and limited liability. On the other hand, it was discovered by authors that not always *lex societatis* of a subsidiary leads to logical result as the international dispute may concern not only company law issues, but a number of other areas of law, which should not be governed by company law.

Thus, it was suggested in the literature that veil piercing doesn’t have necessarily connection to its capacity, legal personality, and limited liability in relation to subsidiary. It is substantive law which is determined on the basis of legal grounds and theory of the claim. Depending on substantive law and different connecting factors the law applicable to piercing may be found.

For example, the parent corporation is liable as a de facto director of its subsidiary: *lex societatis* or *lex fori concursus* may be applied depending on the rules of underlying company or bankruptcy law. When we were illustrating cases on abuse of the legal personality, naturally first of all *lex societatis* is suggested, but on the other hand, this is also not a good choice in all cases. In the light of different incorporation doctrines, *lex societatis* may lead to other location rather than where the subsidiary acts. This may be against the creditors' interests, for example. So in this regard, *lex loci actus* is an alternative solution. When a parent corporation has personally committed a fault in contract or tort, the *lex contractus* or the *lex loci delicti/damni* should apply. In some cases, as we could see, *lex concursus*, *lex societatis*, or the *lex loci delicti/damni*, *lex contractus* led to similar result.

After such this found and eventually suggested scheme on the law applicable to veil piercing, we turned to the choice-of law rules under Rome I and Rome II. For contractual relations created by the corporate agents, authority types were important, and also the details of legal relations between principal and agent and third party were essential for further investigations (including concepts legal representations, corporate agency, consensual agency). First of all the court, applying *lex fori*, should determine whether there is actual or apparent authority of the corporate agent. In fact, there is no need to determine actual authority of organs as it is determined by the *lex societatis*. For actual authority of organs and power of attorney granted by shareholders - the *lex societatis* will apply and the matter of company law are excluded.. All other cases in which questions of the power of the agent to bind a company arise concern apparent authority. In that case *lex fori* will apply its national law. As we could see, depending on the national law, sometimes again the law appeared to be that determined under Rome I. For example, if it is the English court' jurisdiction, the power to bind will be determined by the law applicable to a main contract. The law of the main contract, in its turn, is subject to the rules of Rome I.

In cases of piercing one of the main circumstances when a parent is held liable under contractual obligations is its personal fault. As chosen by the parties law not necessary meets the requirements of certainty for creditors and location of *lex contractus*, connecting factors, but not chosen law, will play its determining role.

Vicarious liability may be “found” in law which governs main non-contractual obligations, thus the Article 4 of the Rome I Regulation states that the law applicable to non-contractual obligations arising out of a tort shall be the law of the country in which the damage occurs. The parties may choose the law, but here again connecting factors play a role for application of the law of the different state.¹²²

We also considered cases when agents commit a tort (not servants). If they act within the authority, the type of authority should be determined as in contractual obligations and depending on that the law is defined: actual, apparent authority. For the apparent authority, the Article 11 of Rome II gives some directions, but this does not concern the liability under company law, which is excluded from the scope.

Within secondary rules personal fault of the company in tort is found in the relevant legislation which governs the main claim, for which ordinary choice-of-law rules under Rome II are applicable.

Piercing of veil in case of tortuous obligations is quite common. We showed that liability of directors-parents may be within framework of the company or bankruptcy law. Or breach of duties is closely connected with “director’s appointment”, and the latter will be subject to internal corporate relations. When it is the case, such matters are excluded from the scope of Rome II.

Conclusion

We would add in the end that both attribution rules and piercing rules need harmonization. However, while in the case with attribution rules

¹²² Regulation 864/2007 (Rome II) on the law applicable to non-contractual obligation, Article 14.

in a single company reference is made to the agency which is excluded from the scope of Rome I, or to vicarious liability which will be subject to ordinary choice of law rules for main obligations under Rome II, to deal with piercing of veil is not an easy task at all. The main problem is to determine substantive law governing veil piecing. We tried to show the most popular examples in this regard. But it happens that the substantive law on the matter doesn't contain any even approximate "instructions" on the liability where a parent company plays a role. And even today, for example, the economic unity theory of the corporate group has no universal rules, and again, as other piercing rules, it has casuistic nature in the substantive law. This is not a task of private international law to cure deficiencies in substantive law. But its task is, taking into account the current status of the substantive law on the matter, to meet concerns raised in corporate veil piercing cases, being responsive to the interests of the stakeholders (e.g. creditors), and to priorities in national and international policy. Private International Law must have regard to the fact that veil piercing is dealt with various manners in different states.¹²³ In relation to multinational corporations what was stressed many years ago remains actual till present time: "the present legal framework has no comfortable, tidy receptacle for such institution" (meaning, for a multinational enterprise).¹²⁴

Recommendation

In this article, we started from a simple single parent company, and step by step, through the combined analysis of substantive and private international laws, we came to the choice of law rules applicable to veil piercing in corporate groups. Based on the current conclusion and further author's research, the author proposes and is planning to work on the main principles of European Private International Law in relation to veil piercing in global corporations.

¹²³ Vandekerckhove, *Op. cit.*, 713.

¹²⁴ Detlev F. Vagts, "The Multinational Enterprise: A new challenge for Transnational Law," *Harvard Law Review*, vol. 83 (1970): 739, 740.

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The Meaning of Legal Communication in Modern Information Society

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Abstract. The article describes the concept, nature and purpose of the legal communication; analyzes the scientific approaches to legal communication as a phenomenon of legal reality. Noted that legal communication is an interaction about any legal phenomena and processes, the exchange of legal information.

Keywords: legal communication, legal information, legal phenomenon.

In the modern information society, all activities are based on information-related, communicative patterns of behavior. Information society is a society in which the main part of the subjects involved in the process of production, storage or processing of information through communication. Such a society has a number of distinctive characteristics: information, knowledge and technology are of great importance in its life; the number of people involved in the production of information products, communications or information technologies is constantly increasing. In this regard, a global information space is being created, which ensures effective interaction between individuals and groups, since the subjects have unlimited access to the world's information resources. Within this information space, each participant meets his needs for information products or services through communication.

In such conditions, the intensive development of e-democracy, information economy, e-state and government is expected. Interactivity involves dialogue and feedback between hundreds of subjects.

The theory of legal communication has a great scientific innovation potential, which is necessary in the development of the theory of state and law applicable to any legal system. Legal communication is a condition for the positivity of the whole right.

The development of information technologies, the emergence of new ways, forms and methods of dissemination of legal information, which is one of the foundations of legal communication required their scientific understanding and justification. The theory of state and law, being in constant search of the “ideal” type of legal understanding, has been increasingly developing the idea in recent years that only post-classical theories of legal understanding, including the communicative theory of law, are able to objectively perceive and reflect the modern legal reality of the information age.

Here it is necessary to take into account the scientific discussions carried out within the framework of anthropology of law.¹ Legal communication as a phenomenon of legal reality has a complex nature and includes a huge number of aspects to study, ranging from philosophical and legal, to institutional, instrumental aspects of the implementation of organizational and legal mechanisms of legal communication, formalized by the legislator of a particular state.

The analysis of the scientific developments available in the Republic of Belarus allows us to identify two opposite trends in legal communication: due to the awareness and consolidation at the state level of the importance of official legal information for the effective functioning of the state and society and the creation of the state system of legal information, this scientific direction is developing intensively, but the issues of legal communication are not directly affected.²

¹ N. A. Danilova, M. K. Ivina, N. A. Isayev, *Socio-cultural anthropology of law* (Saint-Petersburg: Alef-Press, 2015).

² S. A. Kalinin, “On some prospects of development of the general theory of law in connection with the use of information technologies in law,” in *Law in modern Belarusian society: collection of scientific works*, ed. by V. P. Izotko et al., 165-180 (Minsk: Law and Economics, 2006); M. N. Satolina, “On the issue of changing approaches to the legal

Belarusian researchers are actively involved in the discussion about the advantages and disadvantages of the communicative concept of law,³ consequently, they also touch upon the issues of legal communication (at the same time, they analyze it only in the context of the problems of legal understanding).

Through the practical activities of the Belarusian state body-the National center for legal information of the Republic of Belarus (hereinafter – NCLI) and scientific understanding of its results, there is a need to expand research interest.

Analysis of the practical activities of the NCLI and its competence to create and operate the state system of legal information of the Republic of Belarus reveal the procedure for the implementation by each subject of its right to receive full, reliable, official legal information. Legal information by itself (static aspect) has no significant value unless it is used. And the use (dynamic aspect) of legal information is possible only with the help of special tools, means, that is, through communication, communication. If the communication is a legal one, going on about legal phenomena, it is legal communication.

The term “legal communication” is increasingly used in legal vocabulary, is used in scientific circulation, is mentioned in publications devoted to the coverage of other legal phenomena and problems indirectly related to it, however, what is meant by it, what is its theoretical and legal nature and content remains in the initial stage of development.

The scientific literature on the concept of legal communication has not developed a uniform approach to its understanding. It seems that this is quite objective and is due to the lack of a unified position on the nature of communication in general and social communication in particular.

regulation of social relations in the information society,” *Problems of legal Informatization*, № 1 (2005): 23-26.

³ V. I. Pavlov, “The idea of the legal communication and the contemporary anthropology of law,” *Jurisprudence*, № 5 (2014): 127-135.

Thus, in dictionaries communication “is understood as communication, exchange of thoughts, information, ideas; transfer of a content from one consciousness (collective or individual) to another by means of signs”.⁴ Sometimes communication is equated to communication.

There is no uniform approach to understanding legal communication in the legal literature. At the same time, there is no unity as to what constitutes the essence of legal communication. Thus, the existing scientific approaches to the understanding of legal communication can be divided into three groups, based on the supremacy of a particular feature of this phenomenon. One, when a main characteristic of the legal communication considers itself a legal phenomenon or the legal process, i.e. what it arises about (the static aspect), the other – when they believe that the most important feature expressing the content of legal communication is the process of communication (the dynamic aspect), and then the main task of researchers is to refer to the legal communication only those procedures and procedures of communication that have found direct consolidation in the legislation or other, not necessarily. And the third – when the static and dynamic aspects are of equal importance in determining the content of legal communication, and therefore both signs are dominant.

E. A. Romanova believes that legal communication is a “procedure of interaction of subjects based on legal norms, related to the exchange of legal and other information aimed at satisfying their legitimate interests and needs”.⁵

It follows that legal communication should include only such exchange of legal information, which is aimed at satisfying the legitimate interests and needs of the subjects, therefore, according to the author’s logic, the exchange of legal information without such purpose, for example, for the purpose of legal education, raising the level of legal culture, etc., is

⁴ L. F. Il’icheva, P. N. Fedoseyeva, S. M. Kovaleva i dr., *Philosophical encyclopedic dictionary* (M., 1983), 129.

⁵ Ye. A. Romanova, “Legal communication: General theoretical analysis” (Dissertation abstract for the degree of candidate of legal sciences: 12.00.01, Saratov, 2011), 9.

not covered by this phenomenon and is not legal communication. At the same time, the exchange of information of a non-legal nature, but in order to meet the legitimate interests and needs of the subjects is covered, in the author's opinion, by the phenomenon of legal communication. In addition, the author points out that the procedure for the exchange of legal and other information should be based on the rules of law, therefore, not regulated by the rules of law (and does not require common sense) the order of communication between subjects at the ordinary, not professional level, but concerning legal information, is also not legal communication. And in addition to the noted legal communication, the author refers only to the procedure of exchange of legal and other information, respectively, for example, the procedure for obtaining and disseminating such information falls outside the phenomenon of legal communication, which, in our opinion, is a very vulnerable position and has no arguments. The author refers to the signs of legal communication that it "is a normative established sequence of actions of subjects. Legal interaction is largely formalized, carried out in the process of lawmaking and law enforcement in a special procedural order. Specific procedural forms, legal procedures, enshrined in the sources of law, corresponding to the objectives and purposes of legal communication, are carried out by means of legal means (means-acts and means-regulations), having both mandatory and dispositive character. ... is characterized by a special power-regulatory nature, based on the possibility of using the means of state influence, has a universal character, aimed at ensuring the legitimate interests and needs of the subjects".⁶

The following substantive aspects of the legal communication follow from the definition and disclosed features of the legal communication: this is the order of interaction of subjects based on legal norms, i.e. it is only a normative established sequence of actions of subjects, carried out in a special procedural order with the help of legal means; has a special power-regulatory nature, expressed in the possibility of the use of state coercion; carried out on the exchange of legal and other information (but the author

⁶ Ibid., 15.

separately points to the universal nature of legal communication); always focused, where the goal is the satisfaction of legitimate interests and needs.

At the same time, if we rely on other ideas of the author, set out in the abstract of the thesis, the understanding of legal communication is much wider than follows from the author's definition of the phenomenon under study. Thus, it is noted that for the first time, within the framework of the General theory of state and law, a study of "legal communication as a process of interaction between subjects associated with the transfer of legal information aimed at the realization of their legitimate interests and needs".⁷ There is no longer any indication that the process of interaction must necessarily be based on the rules of law, that other information, along with legal information, is transmitted in legal communication, and in addition, it is no longer about the exchange, but about the transfer of information. In addition, the author notes that "legal communication is an interaction that has a universal character",⁸ thereby significantly expanding (in comparison with the definition) the presence, importance, embeddedness of legal communication in the legal life of society.

The author rightly notes that "the process of legal communication takes into account the individual characteristics of the subjects that determine the level of their involvement, as well as forms of interaction (participation of minors, minors, disabled, disabled, disabled, civil servants, individual entrepreneurs, foreign citizens, etc.)".⁹ However, it is not clear what the author means by the individual characteristics of the subject: it is his personal, business qualities, level of training, or both, or something else. However, it is believed that only the individual characteristics of the subjects determine the level of their involvement in legal communication, it seems, hypertrophied. The degree of involvement of subjects in legal communication may also be influenced by the degree of technical equipment, for example, computer equipment of the subject, since its

⁷ Ibid., 8.

⁸ Ibid., 9.

⁹ Ibid., 15.

presence or absence may determine the ability of the subject to carry out such type of legal communication as legal communication through legal forums. All this makes it impossible to clearly understand the author's position, but the undoubted merit of the author is in itself an appeal to the development of this topic.

Of course, the scope of legal communication is more balanced from the point of view of identifying the boundaries of legal communication and the connections that it covers. The definition proposed by Polyakov, who believes that legal communication is "legal interaction between the subjects that arises on the basis of social interpretation of legal texts as providing them with correlative powers and legal obligations implemented in legal behavior".¹⁰ The author examines legal communication is broader to include any legal interaction of subjects, which, of course, quite reasonably. Although it is impossible not to agree with the criticism of some researchers of Polyakov's ideas that, for example, the basis for the emergence of legal communication is the interpretation of legal texts containing correlation powers and rights.¹¹ There are also other critical statements, there is an active discussion about its advantages and disadvantages, which makes it possible to generalize them by some researchers.¹²

The most important in all this is the fact that due to the development of this type of legal understanding, which is based on a communicative approach to law, legal communication, existing as much as there is a person with such a regulator of social relations as law, has only now become an independent legal phenomenon, which is completely objectively within the boundaries of research interest.

¹⁰ A. V. Polyakov, "Communicative concept of law (Genesis and theoretical and legal justification)" (Thesis for the degree of doctor of law in the form of a scientific report, Saint-Petersburg, 2002), 94.

¹¹ S. I. Arkhipov, "The concept of legal communication," *Russian legal journal*, № 6 (2008): 7-9.

¹² Ye. B. Makushina, "Legal communication as a phenomenon of law and communication," http://www.lib.csu.ru/vch/9/2004_01/027.pdf (accessed 25 October 2018).

This became possible due to the application of the theory of communication among lawyers, which was not common in the Russian-language scientific literature. Scientists noted that “the theory of communications is actively introduced into legal science”, as arguments using the position of Western legal scholars, in particular, the German legal theorist V. Krawietz¹³ believes that “a communicative view of law is a natural consequence of those world events that were prepared throughout the XX century. ... Thanks to new inventions and technical devices, through telecommunications via satellites and the Internet, through the use of means of communication in previously unimaginable sizes, we communicate with each other quickly, regardless of distances and borders. It is also important for communication in the field of law”.¹⁴ The fundamental importance for understanding the theory of communication for law in General is the scientific article of Polyakov.¹⁵

Thus, legal communication is a type of social communication, which has certain features, predetermined by the phenomena and processes about which it arises – legal phenomena and processes, i.e. all that is located in the legal sphere. Any interaction between any of the entities regulated by legal regulations or legal requirements can be attributed to the legal communication. And if we take into account that the life of modern society, especially Western, is strictly regulated by legal norms, any assessment of the situation always takes into account the legal norms, not necessarily by legal experts, and even at the ordinary level, any communication on the basis of and (or) about legal phenomena can be attributed to legal communication.

Moreover, legal communication can include interaction about any legal phenomena and processes, while they can be located both in the legal present (legal reality), and in the legal future, and the legal past.

¹³ W. Krawietz, “Vom Weltsystem des Rechts v Kommunikationstheoretischer Perspektive – ein Deutsch-Russischer Dialog,” in *Kommunikation und Recht in dererenen Wissensgesellschaft – natsional’nyy mezhdunarodnyy?* ed. by W. Krawietz (Berlin, 2003).

¹⁴ A. V. Polyakov, “What is Law?” *Jurisprudence*, № 6 (2012): 199-209.

¹⁵ Id., “Postclassical law and the idea of communication,” *Jurisprudence*, № 2 (2006): 26-43.

The discussion available in the scientific literature on the grounds (content) of legal communication, i.e. on the basis and about what it arises, is one of the most acute aspects in the development of legal communication problems, on which there are many opinions. As such, different researchers justify-the rules of law or the texts of normative legal acts, or legal relations, or rights and obligations, or another. Without going deep and without going into its details, since this aspect requires study within the framework of an independent study, it seems that the discussion will be fruitful, if not to reduce it to the search for the only true basis and to assume that there may be several of them-this is first, secondly, to question that as such can be only the phenomena of the legal sphere, which have material properties, while, for example, legal thoughts, ideas, concepts, etc., i.e. what is ideal, not material, legal can also be the basis for legal communication. It is thought, more precisely in search of the basis (and better – the bases) of legal communication to proceed from idea that “texts, actions on their construction and interpretation, and also the thinking connected with it, understanding and interaction make the content of communication”.¹⁶ Therefore, the content, the basis of legal communication can be the texts of normative legal acts, and the actions of law – making bodies on their creation and interpretation, and legal consciousness, and legal understanding, and procedural legal mechanism of interaction of subjects about the above-mentioned-all this is covered by the phenomenon of legal communication. As noted above, the content of legal communication is not limited to this. It seems that legal communication covers any interaction (communication) of subjects about any phenomena that are in the plane of law, any legal phenomena.

In the absence of a unified approach to the understanding of legal communication, however, most researchers believe that this is the process of transferring legal information from the subjects of law to anyone who is able to perceive legal information and (or) carry out any action with it or on

¹⁶ A. Yu. Babaytsev, “Communication,” in *Postmodernism: an encyclopedic dictionary*, ed. by A. Yu. Babaytsev (Minsk, 2001), 371.

its basis, for example, the process of transferring legal information from the law-making body to the law-enforcement body.

We can agree with the opinion of Polyakov that legal communication implies both the understanding of the meaning of the legal text and the recognition of its validity from the point of view of the legitimacy and the need to follow it.¹⁷

Moreover, the communicative theory of law is one of the variants of integral legal understanding. The methodological foundations of the communicative theory of law include the recognition that law, as a phenomenon, does not exist outside the social subject, outside the social interaction, and this interaction is intersubjective, i.e. existing within the boundaries of the general life world of subjects, as well as communicative, mediated by legal texts. Legal texts mediating legal communication should be legitimized (recognized) by the consciousness of subjects within the boundaries of their life world. Participants of such intersubjective communicative interaction have interdependent rights and obligations. From the standpoint of the communicative theory of the right at the same time represents the idea and the real fact, norms and relationships, individual emotions and social values, the text and its interpretation and implementation. None of these provisions is true in their isolation and abstraction, only within the framework of a holistic perception of the law they acquire their meaning.

No social communication can have any other center than its subject, since any social communication is the interaction of subjects. By their will, in their interests, for their sake it is carried out, they contain its meaning and purpose. So, communication is the interaction between subjects, mediated by the text (sign object). The text is essentially a system of signs created within the framework of culture, which carries a certain meaning and consequences. Thus, legal texts (in particular, legal information), activities for their construction and interpretation, as well as related thinking,

¹⁷ A. V. Polyakov, "What is Law?" *Jurisprudence*, № 6 (2012): 207.

understanding, application and interaction constitute the content of legal communication.

As legal information are the information contained in legal texts (normative legal acts, acts of application and interpretation of law), materials of law enforcement practice, special legal literature, reference and encyclopedic materials. Legal information is reflected in the relevant sources and is fixed with the help of certain techniques, means, methods, rules of legal technique. The main purpose of the legislator is to translate into the "language of law" (code of legal communication) what should regulate and regulate social relations. This is achieved, as already noted, with the help of legal technology.

Next the question of the legal communication system comes. In encyclopedic sources, the system is considered as a set of integrated and regularly interacting or interdependent elements, which is designed to achieve certain goals, the relations between the elements are defined and stable, and the overall performance or functionality of the system is better than that of a simple sum of elements.¹⁸ The structure of the system consists of the most significant components and connections that do not change much in the current operation of the system and ensure the existence of the system and its basic properties. The structure characterizes the organization of the system, stable in time ordering of elements and connections. With regard to this understanding of legal communication is somewhat narrowed, since its structure does not distinguish a clearly established procedure, the process of transfer of legal information.

In the modern information society it is not possible to talk about the system of legal communication, because there is no fully formed organizational structure with the presence of a legally fixed range of powers of the competent authority, whose duties include the functions of regulation, management and control, coordination in this area. It should also be recognized that a significant amount of legal communication is

¹⁸ V. K. Batovrin, *Explanatory dictionary of system and software engineering* (Moscow: DMK Press, 2012).

presented in a huge variety of forms, the purposes of manifestations of legal life. And it cannot be represented by a coherent system, because the very formation of law and its implementation is possible only through legal communication, i.e. the right “lives” if there is communication, otherwise it is “dead”. In addition, based on the doubt that the system of legal communication exists, it is not possible to consider its levels, sublevels, functions, tasks, goals until the end. However, it is possible to analyze the levels, functions, tasks, goals of legal communication itself (not the system of legal communication), as well as to identify its forms and methods.

In this connection we cannot agree with the view that legal communication is associated not primarily with language and/or with a written text as means of communication, in its deep structure (deep structure) it relies on already institutionalization in the long term of interpersonal behavior.¹⁹

NCLI carries out legal communication, in connection with which it is possible to analyze the area of its legal communication, to identify features, to establish differences from other types (for example, judicial and legal) communication, to establish the specifics of forms, methods, means of its implementation, etc. The development of legal communication provides for the accumulation of all legal information (which consists in the formation of reference and other data banks of legal information and covers most information processes in relation to legal acts, including their collection, accounting, processing, systematization, official publication, etc.), as well as the creation and maintenance of the system of communication of information contained in legal acts to state bodies, other legal entities and individuals.

State-authorized bodies and organizations implement legal communication at the international level and at the state (national) level. For example, at the state level, legal communication between the NCLI and public authorities primarily covers the collection, recording, processing,

¹⁹ A. Gromitsaris, “Legal communication in the modern legal system,” *Jurisprudence*, № 6, 311 (2013): 77.

systematization, official publication of legal information. There are several sub-levels: 1) legal communication between NCPI and republican bodies of state administration and other state bodies and organizations; 2) legal communication between NCLI and local authorities and self-government; 3) legal communication between NCLI and individuals, legal entities on the provision of information and consulting services.

Thus, it is possible to speak about the origin of the system of legal communication, the allocation of its elements and a certain control action on them, the purpose of which is to ensure effective interaction of state bodies and organizations, individuals and groups, in the process of which their rights and legitimate interests in obtaining and providing legal information are coordinated and most fully and consistently satisfied. Legal means of communication are telephony, radio, television, the Internet, traditional and electronic media. The state is actively creating and implementing the latest technologies, developing information and communication infrastructure, gradually forming a new culture. Information becomes a real communicative resource, because it can help a person to adapt to life in conditions of uncertainty, to adapt to changes, to develop stereotypes of behavior (including lawful).

The main purpose of legal communication is to ensure effective interaction of state bodies and organizations, individuals and groups, in the process of which their rights and legitimate interests in obtaining and providing legal information are agreed and most fully and consistently satisfied. Thus, legal communication is a legal phenomenon that has a universal character, is based, as a rule, on legal norms that affect the motivational sphere of subjects (individual and collective), determining, ultimately, the nature and direction of their activities, interaction. Legal communication involves the formulation, interpretation of the meaning of the legal text (legal information), its transfer (receipt, distribution), recognition of its validity and application.

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